
LOGICS IN MATHEMATICS

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ABSTRACT

This thesis is devoted to the study of logics and showing their applications in various areas of mathematics. The thesis consists of two parts. The first part begins with an extension of a celebrated result in graph theory (four color theorem) using sentential logic. Then the thesis is extensively dedicated to learning about forcing and independence of CH and \diamond from ZFC (assuming its consistency). Then we explore some of the consequences of these independences in complex analysis (Erdős's problem) and the theory of reals (Suslin's problem). Followed by this we study Solovay's model (where every subset of \mathbb{R} is Lebesgue measurable) and with this, the first part of the thesis comes to an end. The second part portrays applications of continuous model theory in ergodic theory. It begins with a study of model theory for metric structures, followed by theories which formalize the notion of *p.m.p.* actions and free actions. Then the notion of existential theory and weak containment are studied followed by a model-theoretic viewpoint of compact and distal extensions. The last chapter is dedicated to universal ergodic distal systems. The thesis finally concludes with some suggestions regarding areas of related research that are yet to be explored in detail.

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Introduction

Graphs can be used to model many types of relations and processes in physical, biological, social and information systems. Graph theory has extensive applications in various areas of studies like grometric group theory, computer science, linguistics, empirical sciences. This thesis witnesses a generalization of **the four color theorem**. The theorem says that “Every planar map can be colored with four colors.” Using **sentential logic**, this theorem has been generalized to the following: “Suppose we have an infinite (but countable) countries in a planar map. This infinite planar map can be colored with four colors.”

Independence results raise deep philosophical questions about the nature of mathematics. The mathematics generally practised is restricted to things common in all models of ZFC. This thesis aims to go beyond the this restricted vision and explore certain independent statements like the **continuum hypothesis**, **diamond principle** and learn in detail about some of the effects these statements have in “mainstram” mathematics, viz. **Erdős’s problem**, **Suslin’s problem**.

The **Solovay’s model** is a model constructed by R. M. Solovay in which all of the ZF axioms hold, except the axiom of choice. In this model all sets of real numbers are Lebesgue measurable. This thesis explores the construction of Solovay’s model. The construction relies on the existence of an inaccessible cardinal. One can say that the axiom of choice is essential to the proof of the existence of a non-measurable set, granted that the existence of an inaccessible cardinal is consistent with ZFC and assuming consistency of ZFC.

Ergodic theory is a branch of mathematics developed by motivations of the physical world. One can realize *p.m.p.* actions (which is the central theme in the study of ergodic theory) as metric structures. On the other hand, **continuous logic** was primarily

developed as a framework for metric structures. In this thesis, the formalization of *p.m.p.* actions using continuous logic has been explored along with some applications of tools developed in continuous model theory in ergodic theory, like **universal ergodic distal systems**.

CHAPTER-WISE ORGANIZATION:

- Chapter 3: This chapter discusses an application of sentential logic in graph theory and gives an alternative proof of the compactness theorem using concepts from general topology.
- Chapter 4: This chapter is devoted to describing the machinery of forcing (a technique for showing independences) in classical logic and using it to create a model of ZFC.
- Chapter 5: This chapter has been spent in proving the independence of CH and \diamond from ZFC using forcing.
- Chapter 6: This chapter potrays applications of the independence of CH and \diamond in “mainstram” mathematics.
- Chapter 7: This chapter explores the construction of Solovay’s Model.
- Chapter 8: This chapter discusses continuous logic and model theory for metric structures.
- Chapter 9: This chapter is spent in formalization of probability-measure-preserving actions, a central theme for the study of ergodic theory.
- Chapters 10, 11: These chapters are devoted to studying the applications of continuous model theory in developing the theory of weak containments, compact extensions and distal extensions.
- Chapter 12: This chapter discusses a largest ergodic distal extension of an ergodic system.

Notational convention

Throughout the thesis, we denote the logical implication and logical ‘if and only if’ by the notations \rightarrow and \leftrightarrow respectively; and the usual implications and ‘if and only if’ in mathematical proofs by \implies and \Leftrightarrow respectively.

ROAD MAP

Background needed

Thesis material

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Part 1

Chapter 3

Interplay between sentential logic and mathematics

In this chapter, we will provide an interesting application of compactness theorem of sentential logic in graph theory. We briefly recall sentential logic as follows:

- A formal language into which we can translate some English sentences.
- Given an infinite sequence of distinct objects (symbols), names are assigned as follows:

Symbol	Verbose name	Remarks
\neg	negation symbol	English: not
\wedge	conjunction symbol	English: and
\vee	disjunction symbol	English: or
\rightarrow	conditional symbol	English: If...then...
A_n	n^{th} sentence symbol	-

- Sentential formulas are built using formula building operations ($\epsilon_{\neg}, \epsilon_{\wedge}, \epsilon_{\vee}, \epsilon_{\rightarrow}$) finite number of times.
- Truth Assignment: A function $v : \{A_n | n \in \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow \{F, T\}$. v can be extended to all sentential formulas and we call this extension \bar{v} .

One might refer to [4] (Chapter 1) for more details on sentential logic. We recall the compactness theorem.

Theorem 3.0.1 (Compactness). *Let Σ be an infinite set of sentential formulas such that for any finite subset Σ_0 of Σ , there is a truth assignment (valuation function) that satisfies every member of Σ_0 . Then there is a truth assignment that satisfies every member of Σ .*

3.1 Generalizing four-colour theorem

The following generalization of four-colour theorem was presented as an exercise in [4]: Before proceeding, we will briefly review planar graphs and for more details on graph theory and planar graphs, one can refer to [13] and [14] respectively.

Definition 3.1.1 (Graph). *A graph G consists of a set V of vertices and a set E of edges, each edge being associated to an unordered pair of vertices by a function $f: E \rightarrow V \times V$ defined as $f(e)=\{v,w\}$, $v,w \in V$.*

In this case we call v and w the ends of the edge e and we also say v and w are adjacent.

Definition 3.1.2 (Path, connected graph). *A **path** in a graph consists of an alternating sequence of vertices and edges, $\{v_0, e_1, v_1, \dots, v_{n-1}, e_n, v_n\}$ where $f(e_i) = \{v_{i-1}, v_i\}$ (for each i). A graph is **connected** if any two vertices can be joined by a path.*

One can draw a graph G in an n -dimensional Euclidean space by taking points as vertices and curves as edges. Now G is said to be ‘embedded’ in the space if it can be drawn in such a way that no edges intersect except for a end-vertex in common. We can now define planar graphs as follows:

Definition 3.1.3 (Planar graph). *A graph G is said to be planar if it can be embedded in \mathbb{R}^2 .*

In 1977, it was proved that every connected, loopless planar map (can be thought of as \mathbb{R}^2 divided in regions by the planar graph) can be colored with four colors. Of course, the definition of “map” requires that there be only finitely many countries. Now we extend the concept as follows:

Theorem 3.1.4. *Suppose we have an loopless, connected, infinite (but countable) planar map with countries $C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n, \dots$. This infinite planar map can be colored with four colors.*

Proof. The above theorem can be proved using sentential logic.

We take four infinite collections of sentence symbols, the complement of whose union is also infinite, and call these collections $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{G}, \mathcal{Y}$ respectively. For simplicity of notation, let us assume that:

$\mathcal{R} = \{R_n | n \in \mathbb{N}\}, \mathcal{B} = \{B_n | n \in \mathbb{N}\}, \mathcal{G} = \{G_n | n \in \mathbb{N}\}, \mathcal{Y} = \{Y_n | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$. We use the above sentence symbols as the following translations:

R_n : Country C_n is coloured red.

B_n : Country C_n is coloured blue.

G_n : Country C_n is coloured green.

Y_n : Country C_n is coloured yellow.

Now, we consider the following sentential formulas for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$(R_n \vee B_n \vee G_n \vee Y_n) \wedge ((\neg R_n) \vee (\neg B_n)) \wedge ((\neg R_n) \vee (\neg G_n)) \wedge ((\neg R_n) \vee (\neg Y_n)) \\ \wedge ((\neg B_n) \vee (\neg G_n)) \wedge ((\neg B_n) \vee (\neg Y_n)) \wedge ((\neg G_n) \vee (\neg Y_n)).$$

This formula basically means that every country has a unique colour.

We call the above sentential formula ϕ_n . Let $\Sigma_1 = \{\phi_n | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$. Now let A_{mn} be a sentence symbol from the complement of $\mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{B} \cup \mathcal{G} \cup \mathcal{Y}$, $\forall n, m \in \mathbb{N} (m \neq n)$, having the following translation:

A_{mn} : C_m and C_n are adjacent in the planar map.

Now we consider the following sentential formula for every $m, n \in \mathbb{N}, (m \neq n)$:

$$A_{mn} \rightarrow (\neg((R_m \wedge R_n) \vee (B_m \wedge B_n) \vee (G_m \wedge G_n) \vee (Y_m \wedge Y_n)))$$

We call this sentential formula ψ_{mn} , which translates into the sentence saying that if two countries are adjacent, then they have different colours. Let $\Sigma_2 = \{\psi_{mn} | m, n \in \mathbb{N}, m \neq n\}$.

Let $\Sigma = \Sigma_1 \cup \Sigma_2$. Now using four colour theorem, we see that clearly, Σ is finitely satisfiable.

Applying Theorem 3.0.1, we have that Σ is satisfiable.

$\implies \exists$ a valuation function v such that $v|_{\Sigma}(x) = T, \forall x \in \Sigma$.

$\implies v(\phi_n) = T \implies C_n$ is *exactly* one of the colours and $v(\psi_{mn}) = T \implies$ if C_m, C_n are adjacent countries, then they do not have the same colour.

\implies each country C_1, C_2, \dots is coloured in exactly one of the four colours (red, blue, green, yellow) and none of the adjacent countries in the planar map have the same colour. \square

3.2 Why call it compactness theorem?

In the previous section, we had become familiar with the statement of compactness theorem for sentential logic and also witnessed an interesting application of it. The word

“compact” immediately makes us think of general topology where most of us encountered the word “compactness” for the first time. So, the natural question that arises is: Why the name “compactness” for the compactness theorem of sentential logic? An answer to this question can be provided by giving an alternative proof of compactness theorem using concepts from general topology related to compactness, particularly Tychonoff’s theorem. We first recall Tychonoff’s theorem:

Theorem 3.2.1 (Tychonoff). *If (X_α, τ_α) are compact topological spaces for each $\alpha \in A$, then $X = \prod_{\alpha \in A} X_\alpha$, equipped with the product topology is compact.*

Now, we will use Theorem 3.2.1 to prove compactness theorem for sentential logic (Theorem 3.0.1):

Proof. Let M be the collection of all sentence symbols in the elements of Σ . We consider the topological space $\{T, F\}$, endowed with discrete topology. Clearly, the above space is compact. We consider the following space: $A = \{T, F\}^M$ equipped with product topology. Applying Theorem 3.2.1, we see that A is compact.

Now, let f be a sentential formula in Σ . We consider the subset S_f of A defined as $S_f = \{v \in A | \bar{v}(f) = T\}$, where \bar{v} is a valuation function obtained by extending v . Clearly, since $\{T, F\}$ is endowed with discrete topology and the number of sentence symbols in f are finite, S_f is closed. Now, Σ is finitely satisfiable

\implies for every finite subset Σ_0 of Σ , $\exists v \in A$ such that $\bar{v}(\Sigma_0) = \{T\}$

\implies if $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k \in \Sigma$, then

$$(3.1) \quad S_{\Sigma_0} := \bigcap_{i=1}^k S_{f_i} \neq \phi.$$

We also observe that $S_{\Sigma_0} = \{v \in \{T, F\}^M | \bar{v}(\Sigma_0) = \{T\}\}$.

Since a topological space X is compact iff it has finite intersection property (which says that if \mathcal{F} is a collection of closed sets in X having the property that every *finite* subcollection G of \mathcal{F} is such that $\bigcap_{g \in G} g \neq \phi$, then $\bigcap_{f \in \mathcal{F}} f \neq \phi$), we have that A has finite intersection property.

Now, we consider the collection $S = \{S_f | f \in \Sigma\}$ of closed sets in A . Using (3.1) and the finite intersection property of A , we conclude that $\bigcap_{f \in \Sigma} S_f \neq \phi$.

$\implies \exists v \in \bigcap_{f \in \Sigma} S_f$, and an extension of v gives us our required truth assignment. \square

Chapter 4

Forcing

Forcing is a technique for proving consistency and independence results. It was first used by Paul Cohen in 1963, to prove the independence of the axiom of choice and the continuum hypothesis from Zermelo-Fraenkel set theory.

In this chapter, we study the machinery developed for forcing, for more details on which, we refer to [18]. We need basic knowledge of logic and set theory for proper understanding of this chapter and for which, one might refer to [4], [3].

4.1 Relativization, reflection, absoluteness

We briefly recall some basic concepts from set theory since we shall be extensively working with these as we proceed.

Definition 4.1.1 (Transitivity). *A set X is transitive if $x \in X \implies x \subseteq X$.*

Definition 4.1.2 (Ordinals). *An ordinal is a transitive set totally ordered by \in .*

Theorem 4.1.3. *If α, β are ordinals then either $\alpha \in \beta, \beta \in \alpha$ or $\alpha = \beta$. Every well-ordered set is order-isomorphic to a unique ordinal.*

Definition 4.1.4 (Cardinal). *A cardinal is an ordinal that cannot be put in bijection with any preceding ordinal.*

Now we move on to the main content of this chapter. We will often state or provide an intuitive idea of the proofs of most of the standard results. For more details, one can refer to [18], [8].

Let ϕ be a formula and M be a set.

Definition 4.1.5 (Relativization). *The relativization of ϕ to M is the formula $\phi|_M$ obtained by restricting all quantifiers in ϕ to range over M .*

Definition 4.1.6 (Absoluteness). *A formula $\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is said to be absolute in M if $\forall x_1 \in M \forall x_2 \in M \dots \forall x_n \in M (\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \longleftrightarrow \phi|_M(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n))$.*

For a sentence ϕ , one can prove the following in ZFC:

Theorem Scheme 4.1.7 (Reflection Principle). *There is a countable transitive set M such that $\phi \longleftrightarrow \phi|_M$.*

The following theory is used for making forcing arguments: It is called **ZFC⁺**. The language of ZFC⁺ consists of the language of set theory with one additional constant symbol **M**.

The non-logical axioms of ZFC⁺ are the following:

- Every non-logical axiom of ZFC.
- The assertion that **M** is countable and transitive.
- The relativization of every non-logical axiom of ZFC to **M**.

Metatheorem 4.1.8. *If ZFC is consistent then so is ZFC⁺.*

Proof. If ZFC⁺ is inconsistent then some finite set of ZFC axioms cannot hold in a countable transitive set, contradicting Theorem Scheme 4.1.7. □

In the following chapters, a typical forcing argument, will be aimed at “enlarging” **M** to another countable transitive set **M[G]** (in which every axiom of ZFC holds) while working in ZFC⁺. In doing so we shall try to ensure that some formula, like the CH or \diamond holds, or doesn’t hold in **M[G]**. The following metatheorem provable in Peano Arithmetic (PA) will thereby ensure the fulfillment of our required independence or consistency results as the case may be :

Metatheorem 4.1.9. *Let ϕ be a sentence in the language of set theory. Suppose that in ZFC⁺, we can define a set N and prove both the relativization of ϕ to N and the relativisation of every axiom of ZFC to N . Then if ZFC is consistent, so is ZFC + ϕ . (Note that, for our purposes this N will always be $M[G]$).*

4.2 Forcing notions and generic extensions

Definition 4.2.1. *Let P be a set.*

1. (*Extension*) *If $p, q \in P$ and $q \supseteq p$, then q is an extension of p .*
2. (*Compatible*) *$p, q \in P$ are said to be compatible if there exists $r \in P$ such that $r \supseteq p$ and $r \supseteq q$.*
3. (*Dense*) *A subset D of P is said to be dense if for all $p \in P$, there exists $q \in D$ such that $q \supseteq p$.*

Definition 4.2.2 (Forcing notion). *Any non-empty set $P \in \mathbf{M}$ ordered partially by \subseteq is said to be a forcing notion for \mathbf{M} .*

Definition 4.2.3 (Ideal). *Let P be a forcing notion. $G \subseteq P$ is said to be an ideal of P if G satisfies the following:*

1. (*Downward stability*) *If $p \in G$ and there is $q \in P$ such that $p \supseteq q$ then $q \in G$.*
2. (*Directedness*) *If $q_1, q_2 \in G$ then there is $p \in G$ such that $p \supseteq q_1, q_2$.*

We note that G may not belong to \mathbf{M} .

Definition 4.2.4 (Generic ideal). *An ideal G is generic relative to \mathbf{M} if $\forall D \in \mathbf{M}$, D is dense $\implies D \cap G$ is non empty.*

We have the following theorem for generic ideals which will be required while proving the fundamental theorem of forcing:

Theorem 4.2.5. *Let P be a forcing notion and let $p \in P$. Then there is a generic ideal of P containing p .*

Proof. Let $(D_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be an enumeration of all dense subsets of P in \mathbf{M} . We choose $p_n \in D_n$ in such a way that $p_0 \subseteq p_1 \subseteq \dots p_n \dots$ by density of each D_n and let

$$G = \{p \in P \mid p \subseteq p_n \text{ for some } n\}$$

Clearly, G has downward stability and $p_n \in G, \forall n \in \omega \implies G$ intersects $D_n, \forall n \in \omega$. Now, if $p, q \in G$, since $\{p_n\}$ is increasing, $\exists k \in \omega$ such that $p, q \subseteq p_k \implies p_k$ is a common extension. Hence, G is a generic ideal and it contains p . \square

Definition 4.2.6 (*P*-name heirarchy, *P*-names). The *P*-name heirarchy (N_α) , with α ranging over the ordinals in \mathbf{M} , is recursively defined as follows:

The sets $\tau \in \mathbf{M}$ are elements of $N_\alpha \iff$

1. $\tau \subseteq (\bigcup_{\beta < \alpha} N_\beta) \times P$.
2. If $p \supseteq q$ and $\langle \sigma, q \rangle \in \tau$ then $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau$.

The sets τ are called *P*-names and the least α such that $\tau \in N_\alpha$ is called the name rank of τ , often denoted as $nr(\tau)$.

We fix a generic ideal G .

Definition 4.2.7 (Value of a *P*-name). The value τ^G of a *P*-name τ is defined recursively on the name rank by

$$\tau^G = \{\sigma^G \mid \sigma \in \tau^{-1}(G)\}$$

Definition 4.2.8 (Generic extension of \mathbf{M}). The generic extension $\mathbf{M}[G]$ of \mathbf{M} corresponding to G is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}[G] = \{\tau^G \mid \tau \text{ is a } P\text{-name}\}$$

Definition 4.2.9. A *P*-name \check{x} for each x in \mathbf{M} is defined recursively on the rank of x by the formula

$$\check{x} = \{\langle \check{u}, p \rangle \mid u \in x, p \in P\}$$

and *P*-name Γ is defined as

$$\Gamma = \{\langle \check{p}, q \rangle \mid p, q \in P, p \subseteq q\}.$$

The following proposition can be proved by induction and straight-forward computation:

Proposition 4.2.10. We have $\check{x}^G = x, \forall x \in \mathbf{M}$ and $\Gamma^G = \Gamma$. Thus, $\mathbf{M} \subseteq \mathbf{M}[G]$. $\mathbf{M}[G]$ is countable, transitive and contains the same ordinals as \mathbf{M} .

4.3 Fundamental theorem of forcing

In this section, we let P be a fixed forcing notion but we shall **not** fix a generic ideal. Now let $\tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n$ be P -names and $\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots x_n)$ any formula in the language of set theory with free variables $x_1, x_2, \dots x_n$. The natural question that one can ask in this context is the following “how much effect does G have on the truth of $\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots x_n)$ in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ and what exactly are the properties of G which influence it’s truth in $\mathbf{M}[G]$?” Clearly, there are cases where the presence of a single element p of $P \in G$ assures that $\phi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G \dots \tau_n^G)$ holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. For example if we take the formula $\exists y(y \in z)$, it is clear that for Γ , the P -name of G , it holds. The fundamental theorem looks to investigate the relation between the truth of formulas in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ and the properties of G influencing them.

Definition 4.3.1. *We say that an element $p \in P$ forces a formula $\phi(\tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n)$ (denoted as $p \Vdash \phi(\tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n)$) \iff for every generic ideal G containing p , $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G \dots \tau_n^G)$.*

For each formula ϕ , the assertion that p forces $\phi(\tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n)$ is a statement about p and τ_i which can be made in the language of ZFC^+ .

Let σ_1, σ_2 be two P -names and let $nr(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ denote the maximum of their name ranks. Now, we recursively define a transfinite sequence of sets (F_α) for α , an ordinal in \mathbf{M} , as $F_\alpha \subseteq P \times N_\alpha^2$ and it satisfies the following conditions:

$$\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2 \rangle \in F_\alpha \iff$$

1. For every $\langle \sigma_1, q_1 \rangle \in \tau_1$ with $q_1 \supseteq p$, there exists $\langle \sigma_2, q_2 \rangle \in \tau_2$ such that $q_2 \supseteq q_1$ and $\langle q_2, \sigma_1, \sigma_2 \rangle \in F_{nr(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)}$.
2. For every $\langle \sigma_2, q_2 \rangle \in \tau_2$ with $q_2 \supseteq p$, there exists $\langle \sigma_1, q_1 \rangle \in \tau_1$ such that $q_1 \supseteq q_2$ and $\langle q_1, \sigma_1, \sigma_2 \rangle \in F_{nr(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)}$.

We note that the recursion can be performed because $nr(\sigma_1) < nr(\tau_1)$ and $nr(\sigma_2) < nr(\tau_2)$. Now $\tau_1, \tau_2 \in N_\alpha \implies nr(\tau_1, \tau_2) \leq \alpha \implies nr(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) < nr(\tau_1, \tau_2) \leq \alpha \implies nr(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) < \alpha$.

For better understanding of the above definition of the sequence, we compute explicitly the first two terms of the sequence as follows:

- For $\alpha = 0$, we have $N_\alpha = \emptyset \implies F_0 = \emptyset$.
- For $\alpha = 1$, we have $N_1 = \{\emptyset\}$ and only one P -name of name rank 1 i.e. $\tau = \emptyset \implies F_1 = P \times N_1^2$, since the two conditions are vacuously true.

We know that any two elements in a generic ideal has a common extension in it. So we often replace any two elements with their common extension and from now on, we shall call this process a “**directness argument**”.

Since F_α is defined recursively using concepts which are already absolute, it is easy to observe that the definition of F_α is absolute for \mathbf{M} . In other words, the forcing relation for the formula $x_1 = x_2$ is *definable* in \mathbf{M} .

The following fact about generic ideals is often used to ensure that certain specific elements are present in $\mathbf{M}[G]$:

Lemma 4.3.2. *Let G be a generic ideal of P , let $D \subseteq \mathbf{M}$ be a subset of P , and suppose every element of G is compatible with some element of D . Then G must intersect D .*

Proof. Let D' be the set of all $p \in P$ which either extend some element of D or are incompatible with every element of D i.e.

$$\forall p \in P (p \in D' \leftrightarrow ((\exists q \in D (p \supseteq q)) \vee (\forall q \in D \neg (\exists r \in D (r \supseteq q \wedge r \supseteq p)))))$$

Then clearly, $D' \in \mathbf{M}$ because D' as it is defined using the axioms of ZFC relativized to \mathbf{M} .

Claim: D' is dense in P .

Proof of claim: We observe that if $p \in P$ and if $\exists q \in D$ such that $q \supseteq p$, then since we clearly have $D \subseteq D'$, hence, $q \in D'$. And if $p \in D'$, the case is trivial. Hence, we always have an extension of $p \in P$, since p can either be extended or be an extension of some element or be incompatible with every element of D . Therefore, our claim is proved.

Since G is a generic ideal and D' is dense and an element of \mathbf{M} , we have $G \cap D' \neq \emptyset$. Let $z \in G \cap D'$. $\implies \exists y \in D$ such that $z \supseteq y$ or z is incompatible with every element of D . From the hypothesis, we see that the second case can never hold. So using the downward stability property of G , we have $y \in G \cap D$. \square

Corollary 4.3.3. *Let G be a generic ideal of P .*

1. *If $D \in \mathbf{M}$ is dense above some $p \in G$, then G must intersect D .*
2. *If $G \subseteq A \in \mathbf{M}$ then there exists $p \in G$ such that every extension of p lies in A .*

Proof. 1. We fix $p \in G$. We know that by directness, every element of G is compatible with p , i.e., lies below an extension of p . So if D is dense above p , then every element in G has an extension in D . Hence, every element of G is compatible with some element of D . Thus, using Lemma 4.3.2, we have that G must intersect D .

2. If $G \subseteq A$, then G doesn't intersect $P \setminus A$, and by Lemma 4.3.2, there must be an element of G which is incompatible with every element of $P \setminus A$. If not, then $\forall z \in G$ there exists $y_z \in P \setminus A, y_z \supseteq z$ or $z \supseteq y_z$. This implies that every element of G is compatible with some element of $P \setminus A$ ($\in \mathbf{M}$). So by Lemma 4.3.2, we have that G must intersect $P \setminus A$ which is contradictory, since $G \subseteq A$.

So let $p \in G$ be such that p is incompatible with every element of $P \setminus A \implies \forall q \in P$ if $q \supseteq p$ then $q \in P \setminus A \implies p$ is compatible with an element of $P \setminus A$ which is a contradiction. Hence, $q \in A$.

□

We finally have the much awaited case of the fundamental theorem as follows:

Theorem 4.3.4. *Let τ_1 and τ_2 be two P -names of name rank atmost α .*

1. *A generic ideal G of P satisfies $\tau_1^G = \tau_2^G$ if and only if some $p \in G$ forces $\tau_1 = \tau_2$.*
2. *An element $p \in P$ forces $\tau_1 = \tau_2$ if and only if $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2 \rangle \in F_\alpha$.*

Proof. We proceed by induction on α . For $\alpha = 0$, there are no P -names of name rank 0, so the above statement follows vaccuously. Now, we assume that 1 and 2 hold $\forall \beta < \alpha$. The following two claims (and the analogous assertions with the roles of τ_1 and τ_2 reversed) contain the core elements of the proof:

We define $A \subseteq P$ by letting $q_1 \in A$ if for each σ_1 with $\langle \sigma_1, q_1 \rangle \in \tau_1, \exists \langle \sigma_2, q_2 \rangle \in \tau_2$ such that $q_2 \supseteq q_1$ and $q_2 \Vdash \sigma_1 = \sigma_2$. For any generic ideal G of P we claim the following:

- (a) If $\tau_1^G \subseteq \tau_2^G$, then $G \subseteq A$.
- (b) If every extension of some $p \in G$ is in A then $\tau_1^G \subseteq \tau_2^G$.

We prove the claims as follows:

(a): let $\tau_1^G \subseteq \tau_2^G$. Let $q_1 \in G$ and let $\langle \sigma_1, q_1 \rangle \in \tau_1$. Then $\sigma_1^G \in \tau_1^G \subseteq \tau_2^G \implies \exists \langle \sigma_2, q_2 \rangle \in \tau_2$ such that $q_2 \in G$ and $\sigma_1^G = \sigma_2^G$ and we assume that $q_2 \supseteq q_1$ by directness. By induction hypothesis on part 1 of the theorem, $\exists p \in G$ such that $p \Vdash \sigma_1 = \sigma_2$, so by directness, we have $q_2 \Vdash \sigma_1 = \sigma_2$ (since all ideals have downward stability, so $q_2 \in G \implies p \in G$) $\implies q_1 \in A$. $\implies G \subseteq A$. Hence, (a) is proved.

(b): We suppose that A contains every extension of some $p \in G$. Now every element of τ_1^G has the form σ_1^G for some $\langle \sigma_1, q_1 \rangle \in \tau_1$ with $q_1 \in G$; by directness, we assume $q_1 \supseteq p$. Since every extension q'_1 of q_1 belongs to A (because they are extensions of p as well) and satisfies $\langle \sigma_1, q'_1 \rangle \in \tau_1$, it follows that the set

$$S = \{q_2 \in P \mid \exists P \text{ - name } \sigma_2 \text{ such that } \langle \sigma_2, q_2 \rangle \in \tau_2 \text{ and } q_2 \Vdash \sigma_1 = \sigma_2\}$$

is dense above q_1 . This follows clearly from the definition of A . By induction hypothesis of part 2 of the theorem, we have

$$\forall x \in P (x \in S \iff (\exists P \text{ - name } \sigma_2 ((\langle \sigma_2, x \rangle \in \tau_2) \wedge (\langle x, \sigma_1, \sigma_2 \rangle \in F_{nr(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)})))$$

Since, each F_α belongs to \mathbf{M} , we have S belongs to \mathbf{M} . Using Corollary 4.3.6(1), G must intersect S . Let $q_2 \in S \cap G$. $\implies \sigma_1^G = \sigma_2^G \in \tau_2^G \implies \tau_1^G \subseteq \tau_2^G$. Hence, (b) is proved.

We are now ready to proceed with the proof of the theorem. The reverse direction of part 1 follows from the definition. For the forward direction, let G be a generic ideal and suppose $\tau_1^G \subseteq \tau_2^G$. According to the claim(a), we have $G \subseteq A$. Using induction hypothesis on part 2 of the theorem, we have that $A \in \mathbf{M}$. This can be shown with similar arguments as done for S . Using Corollary 4.3.6(2), we get an element $p \in G$ all of whose extensions lie in A . Then, from claim (b) we have p forces $\tau_1 \subseteq \tau_2$. A similar argument shows that if $\tau_2^G \subseteq \tau_1^G$ then there exists $p' \in G$ that forces $\tau_2 \subseteq \tau_1$. Thus, if $\tau_1^G = \tau_2^G$ then any common extension of p and p' will force $\tau_1 = \tau_2$, which proves 1.

For the forward direction of part 2, suppose that p forces $\tau_1 = \tau_2$. We must show that $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2 \rangle \in F_\alpha$. Now for any $q_1 \supseteq p$ we can find a generic ideal G that contains q_1 (Theorem 4.2.5) and then claim (a) yields that $q_1 \in A$. So, every extension of p indeed belongs to A . Now condition 1 in the definition of F_α as well as the inductive hypothesis says that every extension of p belongs to A . So, condition 1 in the definition of F_α is verified for $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2 \rangle$. With similar arguments, one can verify condition 2 as well and hence, conclude that $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2 \rangle \in F_\alpha$.

For the reverse direction of part 2 of the theorem, let $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2 \rangle \in F_\alpha$ and let G be a generic ideal that contains p . We must show that $\tau_1^G = \tau_2^G$. But again, condition 1 in the definition of F_α says that every extension of p belongs to A , so claim (b) yields $\tau_1^G \subseteq \tau_2^G$ and by condition 2 we get $\tau_2^G \subseteq \tau_1^G$. Hence, our proof is done. \square

We will now generalize Theorem 4.3.7 to arbitrary formulas. As in the previous section, we fix a forcing notion P . The remaining cases are easier because working in \mathbf{M} , we can define the forcing relation for the formula $x_1 \in x_2$ in terms of the forcing relation for $x_1 = x_2$, and the forcing relations for complex formulas can be constructed from the forcing relations for their constituent formulas. So we no longer need the induction on α employed in the definition of F_α when the forcing relation for $x_1 = x_2$ was being defined

in terms of itself (i.e. we defined the relation for names of higher ranks with the help of those with lower ranks, where the relation was supposed to be already defined).

Let ϕ be a formula in the language of set theory. In \mathbf{M} , we define a transfinite sequence of sets (F_α^ϕ) which describe the forcing relation for ϕ . If ϕ was an atomic equality, then this follows from the last section. Otherwise, let n be the number of unquantified variables in ϕ — since we rename variables at will, there is no harm in assuming these are the variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n — and depending on whether ϕ has the form $x_1 \in x_2, \neg\psi, \psi_1 \rightarrow \psi_2$ or $(\forall x)\psi(x, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, we define $F_\alpha(\subseteq P \times N_\alpha^n)$ as

$$\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n \rangle \in F_\alpha^\phi \iff$$

(\in) The set $S = \{q \in P \mid \exists P\text{-name } \sigma \text{ such that } \langle \sigma, q \rangle \in \tau_2 \text{ and } q \Vdash \tau_1 = \sigma\}$ is dense above p ;

(\neg) No extension of p forces $\psi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$;

(\rightarrow) $\forall q \supseteq p (q \Vdash \psi_1(x_1, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow \exists r \supseteq q (r \Vdash \psi_2(x_1, \dots, x_n)))$;

(\forall) For any P -name τ , the set $\{q \mid q \Vdash \psi(\tau, \tau_1, \dots, \tau_n)\}$ is dense above p .

Each of these definitions can be framed in \mathbf{M} because each refers to a forcing relation that we will be able to inductively define in \mathbf{M} . The induction is based on the complexity of the formula ϕ .

For each ϕ the following statement is provable in ZFC^+ :

Theorem Scheme 4.3.5 (Fundamental theorem of forcing). *Let $\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n$ be P -names of name rank at most α .*

1. *For any generic ideal G of P we have $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G) \iff \exists p \in G$ such that $p \Vdash \phi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$.*

2. *An element $p \in P$ forces $\phi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \iff \langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n \rangle \in F_\alpha^\phi$.*

Proof. The case where ϕ is an atomic equality was proven in Theorem 4.3.7. Otherwise, depending on whether ϕ has the form $x_1 \in x_2, \neg\psi, \psi_1 \rightarrow \psi_2$ or $(\forall x)\psi(x, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, we define A to be the set $q \in P$ such that

(\in) $\exists \langle \sigma, q' \rangle \in \tau_2$ such that $q' \supseteq q$ and $q' \Vdash \tau_1 = \sigma$;

(\neg) $q \not\vdash \psi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$;

(\rightarrow) $q \not\vdash \psi_1(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \vee \exists r \supseteq q (r \Vdash \psi_2(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n))$;

(\forall) For every P -name $\tau, \exists r \supseteq q$ such that $r \Vdash \psi(\tau, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$.

We observe that in each case $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n \rangle \in F_\alpha^\phi \iff \forall q \supseteq p, q \in A$. Let us see this explicitly for the formula $x_1 \in x_2$.

Let $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2 \rangle \in F_\alpha^{x_1 \in x_2}$.

$\implies S = \{q \in P \mid \exists P\text{-name } \sigma \text{ such that } \langle \sigma, q \rangle \in \tau_2 \text{ and } q \Vdash \tau_1 = \sigma\}$ is dense above p .

Let $r \supseteq p \implies \exists m \in S$ such that $m \supseteq r \implies r \in A$.

Conversely, if every extension of p belongs to A , then let r be an extension of p . Now $r \in A \implies \exists \langle \sigma, q' \rangle \in \tau_2$ such that $q' \supseteq r$ and $q' \Vdash \tau_1 = \sigma \implies q' \in S \implies S$ is dense above p . So we have $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2 \rangle \in F_\alpha^{x_1 \in x_2}$. The other cases follow similarly.

Now, for any generic ideal G of P we claim the following:

(a) $\mathbf{M}[G] \Vdash \phi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G) \rightarrow G \subseteq A$.

(b) If every extension of some $p \in G$ is in A , then $\mathbf{M}[G] \Vdash \phi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$.

The proof of the above claim is as follows:

- $\phi = x_1 \in x_2$.

(a) Let $\mathbf{M}[G] \Vdash \tau_1^G \in \tau_2^G$ and let $p \in G$. Now $\tau_1^G \in \tau_2^G \implies \exists k \in G$ such that $\langle \sigma, k \rangle \in \tau_2, \sigma^G = \tau_1^G$.

Now using Theorem 4.3.7(1), $\exists g \in G, g \Vdash \tau_1 = \sigma$ and by directness, g is an extension of p and k . $\implies \langle \sigma, g \rangle \in \tau_2, g \supseteq p, g \Vdash \tau_1 = \sigma \implies p \in A$.

(b) Let $p \in G$ and every extension of p belongs to A .

Let $D = \{q' \supseteq p \mid \exists \langle \sigma, q' \rangle \in \tau_2 \wedge q' \Vdash \tau_1 = \sigma\}$. Now $r \supseteq p \implies r \in A \implies \exists k \supseteq r \supseteq p, k \in D \implies D$ is dense over p . Using Theorem 4.3.7(2) and Corollary 4.3.6(1), $D \in \mathbf{M}$ and $\exists z \in G \cap D \implies \exists \langle \sigma, z \rangle \in \tau_2$ and $z \Vdash \tau_1 = \sigma \implies \tau_1^G = \sigma^G \in \tau_2^G$.

- Let $\phi = \neg\psi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$.

(a) Let $\mathbf{M}[G] \Vdash \neg\psi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G) \implies \mathbf{M}[G] \not\vdash \psi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$.

Let $p \in G$. If $p \Vdash \psi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$ then $\mathbf{M}[G] \Vdash \psi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$ which is contradictory. Hence, $p \not\vdash \psi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \implies G \subseteq A$.

(b) Let $p \in G$ and every extension of p belongs to A .

If $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$ then by using induction of the complexity of the formula on the above theorem scheme, we have that $\exists q \in G$ such that $q \Vdash \psi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. By directness, we can assume that q is an extension of p . Thus, $q \notin A$ which is a contradiction.

• Let $\phi = \psi_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow \psi_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$.

(a) Let $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi_1(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G) \rightarrow \psi_2(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$ and $p \in G$.

$p \Vdash \psi_1(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \implies \mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi_1(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$

$\implies \mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi_2(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$. If $\forall r \supseteq p, r \not\Vdash \psi_2(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$

$\implies \forall r \in G, r \supseteq p, r \not\Vdash \psi_2(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$.

Applying induction of complexity of the formulas on the above theorem scheme, by inductive hypothesis, we have that $\exists q \in G$ such that $q \Vdash \psi_2(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$. By directness, we assume that $q \supseteq p$ and by downward stability of G , we have that $q \Vdash \psi_2(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$ which is contradictory to the above arguments. Hence, $\exists r \in G, r \supseteq p, r \Vdash \psi_2(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \implies p \in A$.

(b) Let $p \in G$ and every extension of p belongs to A .

We again apply induction on the complexity of the formula. If $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi_1(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$, then by inductive hypothesis, $\exists q \in G, q \Vdash \psi_1(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$. By directness, we assume $q \supseteq p \implies q \in A \implies$ the set $D = \{r \supseteq q \mid r \Vdash \psi_2(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)\}$ is dense over q . Using inductive hypothesis of complexity of formulas on statement 2 of the theorem, we have $D \in \mathbf{M}$ and then by Corollary 4.3.6(1), we have that $\exists z \in G \cap D \implies z \Vdash \psi_2(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \implies \mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi_2(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G) \implies \mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi_1(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G) \rightarrow \psi_2(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$.

• Let $\phi = (\forall x)\psi(x, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$

(a) Let $\mathbf{M}[G] \models (\forall x)\psi(x, \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$.

Let $p \in G$. Let τ be a P -name. We have $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi(\tau^G, \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$. Again, by using inductive hypothesis of complexity of formulas on the above theorem scheme, we have that $\exists q \in G$ such that $q \Vdash \psi(\tau, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$. By directness, we assume that $q \supseteq p$ and by downward stability of G , we have that $q \Vdash \psi(\tau, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$. Hence, for every P -name $\tau, \exists q \supseteq p$ such that $q \Vdash \psi(\tau, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \implies p \in A$.

(b) Let $p \in G$ and every extension of p belongs to A . Let τ be a P -name. Now $D = \{r \supseteq p \mid r \Vdash \psi(\tau, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)\}$ is dense over p and by inductive hypothesis on statement 2 of the theorem scheme, $D \in \mathbf{M}$. So by Corollary 4.3.6(1) $\exists z \in G \cap D \implies z \Vdash \psi(\tau, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$. Again by inductive hypothesis on statement 1 of the theorem scheme, we have $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \psi(\tau^G, \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$. Since τ was arbitrarily chosen, we have $\mathbf{M}[G] \models (\forall x)\psi(x, \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$.

Hence (a) and (b) are proved. We now proceed with the proof of the theorem scheme. The reverse direction of part 1 is trivial. For the forward direction, let G be a generic ideal of P and $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$. According to claim (a), we have $G \subseteq A$ and by inductive hypothesis on part 2 of the theorem Scheme, we have $A \in \mathbf{M}$. By Corollary 4.3.6(2), $\exists p \in G$ such that every extension of p lies in A . So from claim (b) we have $p \Vdash \phi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$. This completes the proof of part 1.

For the forward direction of part 2, let us assume that $p \Vdash \phi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$ and $q \supseteq p$. \exists a generic ideal G containing $q \implies q \Vdash \phi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \implies \mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$. By claim (a), we have $G \subseteq A \implies q \in A \implies \langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n \rangle \in F_\alpha$.

For the reverse direction, let $\langle p, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n \rangle \in F_\alpha$ and let G be a generic ideal containing p . Now from the definition of F_α every extension of p lies in A . So, by claim (b), we have $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi(\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$. Since, G was chosen arbitrarily, we conclude that $p \Vdash \phi(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$. \square

4.4 $\mathbf{M}[G]$ - A model of ZFC

In this section, we shall see that $\mathbf{M}[G]$ satisfies all axioms of ZFC and hence, is a model of ZFC.

We restate the axioms of ZFC informally before proceeding to achieve the aim of this section:

1. Extensionality: Two sets are equal if they have same elements.
2. Pairing: For all x and y , there exists a sets whose elements are x and y .
3. For any set of sets, there is a set which is their union.
4. Power set: For all x , there is a set whose elements are the subsets of x .
5. Infinity: There is a set x such that $\phi \in x$ and for every u , if $u \in x$, then $u \cup \{u\} \in x$.

6. Foundation: Every non-empty set has an ϵ -minimal element.
7. Choice: Every set of non-empty sets has a choice function.
8. Separation scheme: For all x , there exists y whose elements are those $u \in x$ for which $\phi(u)$ holds.
9. Replacement Scheme: For all x , if for every $u \in x$ there is a unique v such that $\phi(u, v)$ holds, then there is a set y obtained by replacing each $u \in x$ with the corresponding v .

We will now show that $\mathbf{M}[G]$ satisfies the axioms of ZFC. Using the fundamental theorem, one can easily show that $\mathbf{M}[G]$ satisfies the separation, replacement and choice axioms, the details of which we shall explore in due course.

Theorem Scheme 4.4.1 (Separation). *For any set $\tau^G \in \mathbf{M}[G]$ and parameters $\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G \dots \tau_n^G \in \mathbf{M}[G]$, the set*

$$y = \{u \in \mathbf{M}[G] \mid \mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi(u, \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G \dots \tau_n^G)\}$$

belongs to $\mathbf{M}[G]$.

Proof. Let τ be a P -name. We define

$$\pi = \{\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau \mid p \Vdash \phi(\sigma, \tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n)\}$$

Now let $\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n, \tau$ have name rank at most α . From Theorem Scheme 4.3.8(2), we have that $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \pi \iff \langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau \wedge \langle p, \sigma, \tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n, \tau \rangle \in F_\alpha^\phi$. Now $F_\alpha^\phi, \tau \in \mathbf{M} \implies \pi \in \mathbf{M}$. Hence, π is a P -name.

Claim: $\pi^G = y$.

Proof of Claim: Let $\sigma^G \in \pi^G \implies \exists p \in G$ such that $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \pi \implies \langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau, p \Vdash \phi(\sigma, \tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n) \implies \sigma^G \in \tau^G, \mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi(\sigma^G, \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G \dots \tau_n^G) \implies \sigma^G \in y \implies \pi^G \subseteq y$.

Conversely, let $u \in \tau^G$ and suppose $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi(u, \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G \dots \tau_n^G)$. Then $u = \sigma^G$ for some $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau, p \in G$. By Theorem Scheme 4.3.8(1), $\exists q \in G, q \Vdash \phi(\sigma, \tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n)$. Again by directness, we can assume p is an extension of q and thus, $p \Vdash \phi(\sigma, \tau_1, \tau_2 \dots \tau_n) \implies \langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \pi \implies u = \sigma^G \in \pi^G \implies y \subseteq \pi^G$. Hence, the claim is proved.

This concludes the proof of Theorem Scheme 4.4.1. □

Definition 4.4.2. *Let τ be a P -name. We define*

$$\tilde{\tau} = \{\langle \sigma, p \rangle \mid \sigma \subseteq \tau \text{ is a } P\text{-name and } p \in P\}$$

We observe that $\tilde{\tau} \in \mathbf{M}$ and hence, is a P -name $\implies \tilde{\tau}^G \in \mathbf{M}[G]$.

Theorem 4.4.3 (Power Set). *For any $\tau^G \in \mathbf{M}[G]$ we have $P(\tau^G) \cap \mathbf{M}[G] = \tilde{\tau}^G \in \mathbf{M}[G]$.*

Proof. Let $\sigma^G \in \tilde{\tau}^G \implies \langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tilde{\tau}$ and $p \in G \implies \sigma \subseteq \tau$.

Claim 1: $\sigma^G \subseteq \tau^G$ and $\sigma^G \in \mathbf{M}[G]$.

Proof of Claim: Since σ is a P -name, it is clear that $\sigma^G \in \mathbf{M}[G]$. Let $\psi^G \in \sigma^G \implies \exists q \in G$ such that $\langle \psi, q \rangle \in \sigma \subseteq \tau \implies \psi^G \in \tau^G \implies \sigma^G \subseteq \tau^G$. Hence, claim 1 is proved.

So, we have $P(\tau^G) \cap \mathbf{M}[G] \supseteq \tilde{\tau}^G$.

Conversely, let $\pi^G \subseteq \tau^G$ for some P -name π . We define the P -name

$$\pi' = \{\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau \mid p \Vdash \sigma' \in \pi\}.$$

using Theorem Scheme 4.3.8(2). Clearly, $\pi' \subseteq \tau \implies \langle \pi', p \rangle \in \tilde{\tau}, \forall p \in P \implies \pi'^G \in \tilde{\tau}^G$.

Claim 2: $\pi'^G = \pi^G$.

Proof of Claim 2: Let $\sigma'^G \in \pi'^G \implies \exists p \in G$ such that $\langle \sigma', p \rangle \in \pi' \implies \langle \sigma', p \rangle \in \tau, p \Vdash \sigma' \in \pi \implies \sigma'^G \in \pi^G \implies \pi'^G \subseteq \pi^G$.

Now let $\sigma^G \in \pi^G \subseteq \tau^G \implies \exists q \in G$ such that $\langle \sigma', q \rangle \in \tau$ and $\sigma^G = \sigma'^G$. By directness, we have $q \Vdash \sigma' = \sigma \in \pi \implies \langle \sigma', p \rangle \in \pi'$ and hence, $\sigma^G = \sigma'^G \in \pi'^G$ thus proving Claim 2. Hence, $P(\tau^G) \cap \mathbf{M}[G] \subseteq \tilde{\tau}^G$, thus concluding the proof. \square

The proof of the replacement scheme presented here uses a version of the cumulative heirarchy in $\mathbf{M}[G]$.

Definition 4.4.4. *Let α be an ordinal in \mathbf{M} . We define*

$$\tilde{V}_\alpha = \{\sigma^G \mid \sigma \in N_\alpha\}.$$

and $\tilde{V}_{<\alpha} := \bigcup_{\beta < \alpha} \tilde{V}_\beta$ and $N_{<\alpha} := \bigcup_{\beta < \alpha} N_\beta$.

Corollary 4.4.5. *We have $\tilde{V}_\alpha = P(\tilde{V}_{<\alpha}) \cap \mathbf{M}[G]$ for every ordinal $\alpha \in \mathbf{M}$.*

Proof. For each α we define $\tau_\alpha = \{\langle \sigma, p \rangle \mid \sigma \in N_\alpha \text{ and } p \in P\}$. We let $\tau_{<\alpha} = \bigcup_{\beta < \alpha} \tau_\beta$.

Claim: $\tilde{\tau}_{<\alpha} = \tau_\alpha$.

Proof of Claim: Let $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tilde{\tau}_{<\alpha} \implies \sigma \subseteq \bigcup_{\beta < \alpha} \tau_\beta$ is a P -name \implies if $\langle \psi, q \rangle \in \sigma$ then $nk(\psi) < \alpha \implies \sigma \in N_\alpha \implies \langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau_\alpha \implies \tilde{\tau}_{<\alpha} \subseteq \tau_\alpha$.

Let $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau_\alpha \implies \sigma \in N_\alpha \implies \forall \langle \psi, q \rangle \in \sigma, \psi \in N_{<\alpha} \implies \langle \psi, q \rangle \in \tilde{\tau}_{<\alpha} \implies \sigma \subseteq \tilde{\tau}_{<\alpha} \implies \langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tilde{\tau}_{<\alpha} \implies \tilde{\tau}_{<\alpha} \supseteq \tau_\alpha$, thus proving the claim.

Now, from the definitions, we have $\tilde{V}_\alpha = \tau_\alpha^G$ and $\tilde{V}_{<\alpha} = \tau_{<\alpha}^G$. By using Theorem 4.4.3, the conclusion follows. \square

We can now verify the validity of the replacement scheme in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. For every formula ϕ in the language of set theory with free variables among u, v, x_1, \dots, x_n , the following is provable in ZFC^+ :

Theorem Scheme 4.4.6 (Replacement). *Let τ^G be a set in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ and let $\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G$ be parameters. Suppose that for each $u \in \tau^G$ there is a unique $v \in \mathbf{M}[G]$ such that $\phi(u, v, \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G, \dots, \tau_n^G)$ holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. Then the set formed by replacing each $u \in \tau^G$ with the corresponding v belongs to $\mathbf{M}[G]$.*

Proof. For every $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau$ if the least ordinal in \mathbf{M} exists such that for some $\pi \in N_{\alpha_{\sigma,p}}, p \Vdash \phi(\sigma, \pi, \tau_1, \dots, \tau_n)$, we denote it by $\alpha_{\sigma,p}$. By Theorem Scheme 4.3.8 and the replacement axiom relativized to \mathbf{M} , these ordinals constitute a set in \mathbf{M} , and hence their supremum (union) α is also an ordinal in \mathbf{M} . By separation in $\mathbf{M}[G]$, it is enough to check that the set we are trying to construct is contained in \tilde{V}_α . That is, for each $u \in \tau^G, v$ must belong to \tilde{V}_α . We know that $u = \sigma^G$ for some $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau, p \in G$ and $v = \pi^G$ for some P -name $\pi \implies \exists q \in G$ such that $q \Vdash \phi(\sigma, \pi, \tau_1, \dots, \tau_n)$ by Theorem Scheme 4.3.8. By directness we can assume that $\langle \sigma, q \rangle \in \tau \implies \exists \pi' \in N_\alpha$ such that $q \Vdash \phi(\sigma, \pi', \tau_1, \dots, \tau_n) \implies \pi'^G = \pi^G$ (uniqueness) and we have $\pi^G \in \tilde{V}_\alpha$. \square

Definition 4.4.7. *Let τ_1, τ_2 be two P -names. We define*

$$up(\tau_1, \tau_2) = \{\langle \sigma, p \rangle \mid \sigma \in \tau_1 \cup \tau_2, p \in P\}.$$

And we define $op(\tau_1, \tau_2) = up(up(\tau_1, \tau_1), up(\tau_1, \tau_2))$.

We observe that $up(\tau_1, \tau_2), op(\tau_1, \tau_2)$ are both P -names and $up(\tau_1, \tau_2)^G = \{\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G\}$, $op(\tau_1, \tau_2)^G = \langle \tau_1^G, \tau_2^G \rangle$. Hence, we see that the definition of $op(\tau_1, \tau_2)$ is motivated by Kuratowski's definition of 'ordered pairs' i.e. $\langle a, b \rangle := \{\{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$.

Theorem 4.4.8. *The axioms of **extensionality, pairing, union, infinity, and foundation** are true in $\mathbf{M}[G]$.*

Proof. Using Proposition 4.2.10, we have that $\mathbf{M}[G]$ is transitive and hence, **extensionality** follows clearly from the definition of transitivity. Now $\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G \in \mathbf{M}[G] \implies \{\tau_1^G, \tau_2^G\} \in \mathbf{M}[G]$ from Definition 4.4.7 which implies that **pairing** axiom holds. Let τ be any P -name. Then

$$\check{\tau} = \{\langle \pi, p \rangle \mid \exists \sigma \text{ such that } \langle \pi, p \rangle \in \sigma \text{ and } \langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau\}$$

is clearly, a P -name.

Claim: $\check{\tau}^G = \bigcup_{\sigma^G \in \tau^G} \sigma^G$.

Proof of Claim: Let $\pi^G \in \check{\tau}^G \implies \exists g \in G$ such that $\langle \pi, g \rangle \in \check{\tau}$

$\implies \exists \sigma$ such that $\langle \pi, g \rangle \in \sigma$ and $\langle \sigma, g \rangle \in \tau \implies \pi^G \in \sigma^G \in \tau^G$

$\implies \pi^G \in \bigcup_{\sigma^G \in \tau^G} \sigma^G$.

Let $\pi^G \in \bigcup_{\sigma^G \in \tau^G} \sigma^G \implies \pi^G \in \sigma^G$ for some $\langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau$, $p \in G$. Also, $\exists q \in G$ such that $\langle \pi, q \rangle \in \sigma$. By choosing a common extension r of p, q in G , we have $\langle \pi, r \rangle \in \sigma$, $\langle \sigma, r \rangle \in \tau \implies \langle \pi, r \rangle \in \check{\tau} \implies \pi^G \in \check{\tau}^G$, thus proving the claim.

This shows us that the **union** axiom holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. From Proposition 4.2.10, we have that $\mathbf{M} \subseteq \mathbf{M}[G]$. Using the fact that $\mathbf{N}^{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{N}$, we conclude that $\mathbf{M}[G]$ contains an infinite set and hence, **infinity** axiom holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. \square

Theorem 4.4.9. *The **axiom of choice** holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$.*

Proof. We fix a value of a P -name $\tau^G \in \mathbf{M}[G]$ and well order the P -name τ in \mathbf{M} . Then clearly, $\psi = \{\langle op(\langle \check{\sigma}, p \rangle, \sigma), p \rangle \mid \langle \sigma, p \rangle \in \tau\}$. is a P -name and $\psi^G = \{\pi^G \mid \exists g \in G \text{ such that } \langle \pi, g \rangle \in \psi\}$. Now $\langle \pi, g \rangle \in \psi \implies \pi = op(\langle \check{\sigma}, g \rangle, \sigma)$ for some $\langle \sigma, g \rangle \in \tau \implies \pi^G = \langle \langle \check{\sigma}, g \rangle^G, \sigma^G \rangle$. So ψ^G is a function f that maps a subset of τ onto τ^G . Since $\mathbf{M}[G]$ satisfies the ZF axioms, we embed τ^G into τ in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ by the map $g : x(\in \tau^G) \rightarrow$ the least element of $f^{-1}(x)$. τ is well-ordered, so we can induce a well-ordering on τ^G via f . Therefore, every element in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ can be well-ordered. Hence, given any set of non-empty sets in $\mathbf{M}[G]$, one takes their unions and well-orders it and then selects a least element from each of the subsets. Thus, axiom of choice holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. \square

All our above work therefore ensures that $\mathbf{M}[G]$ satisfies all the ZFC axioms. In other words, we have the following metatheorem which is provable in PA:

Metatheorem 4.4.10. *ZFC⁺ proves the statement “If G is a generic ideal of a forcing notion then $\mathbf{M}[G] \Vdash \phi$ ” for every axiom ϕ of ZFC.*

We conclude this chapter with an important note. The entire machinery of forcing can be developed with exactly the same constructions by replacing the partial order \subseteq in the forcing notion with any partial order.

Chapter 5

Independent statements of ZFC

We will in this chapter establish the independence of various statements from ZFC using the technique of Forcing. By the Metatheorem 4.1.9, the relative consistency of ϕ with the ZFC axioms (i.e. $\text{ZFC consistent} \implies \text{ZFC} + \phi \text{ consistent}$) can be proved, if we can produce a forcing notion for which we can prove in ZFC^+ that $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \phi$, for some generic ideal G of this forcing notion. We start with the continuum hypothesis(CH). So, in order to prove the independence of continuum hypothesis, we need to produce a model of ZFC which satisfies CH and another one which satisfies $\neg \text{CH}$.

5.1 Forcing CH

In this section, we will prove that CH is relatively consistent with ZFC. This result was first proven by Gödel (using his constructible universe) but here we will be seeing an alternative proof using forcing to create a model of ZFC where CH holds.

We shall first recall the statement of CH.

Continuum Hypothesis: $2^{\aleph_0} = \aleph_1$.

Let us now proceed to prove the relative consistency of CH with ZFC.

A forcing notion is heuristically considered to be a family of “partial constructions” of a desired object. Since, in order to establish the relative consistency of CH, we need to create a bijection between $P(\mathbb{N})$ and \aleph_1 we define the following:

Definition 5.1.1 (Finite partial bijection). *A finite partial bijection between a set A to a set B is a bijection f between a finite subset of A and a finite subset of B .*

Let P_1 be the set of all finite partial bijections between $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}}$ and $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$. Clearly,

(P_1, \subseteq) is a forcing notion. Let G be a generic ideal of P_1 . Since any two functions in G have a common extension, we have that all functions in G are “compatible as functions” so that for any two functions f, f' we can take their union which will again be a function f'' . Also, union of a directed family of bijections is also a bijection between a subset of $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}}$ and a subset of $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$. For each $A \in P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}}$, the set of all finite partial bijection with A in its domain is a dense set belonging to \mathbf{M} . So G must contain such a function which implies that domain of $f'' (= \bigcup G)$ is $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}}$ and by similar arguments range of f'' is $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}} \implies f''$ is a bijection between $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}}$ and $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$. But we want $\mathbf{M}[G]$ to contain a bijection between $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$ and $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$. Ordinals are absolute between \mathbf{M} and $\mathbf{M}[G]$, however cardinals aren't since new bijections may appear in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. The set of natural numbers is also absolute, so $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}} \subseteq P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$. However, the challenge is that new subsets of natural numbers may appear in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. For example, we can define a set using the bijection f'' as $A = \{n \in \mathbb{N} \mid f''(n) < \omega\}$. Clearly, A is defined in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ so it belongs to $\mathbf{M}[G]$.

Claim: $A \notin \mathbf{M}$.

Proof of Claim: Let $B \subseteq \mathbb{N}, B \in \mathbf{M}$. Let us define the following set:

$$D_B = \{f \in P_1 \mid \exists n \in \text{dom}(f) \text{ such that } n \in B, f(n) \geq \omega \text{ or } f(n) < \omega, n \notin B\}.$$

Clearly, $D_B \in \mathbf{M}$ and is dense in P_1 because the finite partial functions can be extended. So G intersects $D_B \implies \exists n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$n \in A \iff f''(n) < \omega \iff n \notin B.$$

Since B is arbitrary, the proof is done. So, we have proved the following proposition:

Proposition 5.1.2. *Forcing with finite partial bijections introduces new subsets of natural numbers in $\mathbf{M}[G]$.*

The above arguments therefore presents before us a serious difficulty in proving that CH holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ i.e. f'' won't work here. So, we try to circumvent this problem by using “countable partial bijections” instead of finite ones.

Definition 5.1.3 (Countable partial bijections). *A countable partial bijection between two sets A and B is a bijection f between a countable subset of A and a countable subset of B .*

Let P_2 be the set of all countable partial bijections between $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}}$ and $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$. A feature of P_2 which allows us to circumvent this situation is as follows:

Definition 5.1.4. A set P is ω closed if the union of every infinite (but countable) sequence $p_0 \subseteq p_1 \subseteq \dots$ of elements of P belongs to P .

Clearly, we have $\mathbf{M} \models P_2$ is ω closed because countable union of an increasing sequence of countable partial bijections is a countable partial bijection. In the next lemma we show that this property of P_2 prevents new functions with domain \mathbb{N} (and hence new subsets of natural numbers) from appearing in $\mathbf{M}[G]$.

Lemma 5.1.5. Let P be a forcing notion such that $\mathbf{M} \models P$ is ω closed, let G be a generic ideal of P , and let $X \in \mathbf{M}$. Then any function $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow X$ in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ is already in \mathbf{M} .

Proof. Let $f : (\mathbb{N} \rightarrow X) \in \mathbf{M}[G]$ and τ be a P -name for f . Using Theorem Scheme 4.3.8(1) and Proposition 4.2.10 $\exists p \in G$ such that $p \Vdash \tau : \check{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \check{X}$ is a function. Let $T = \{\langle q, n, x \rangle \in \subseteq P \times \mathbb{N} \times X \mid q \Vdash \text{op}(\check{n}, \check{x}) \in \tau\}$.

By Theorem Scheme 4.3.8(2), $T \in \mathbf{M}$.

Claim: For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $K_n := \{q \in P \mid \exists x \in X \text{ such that } \langle q, n, x \rangle \in T\}$ is dense over p .

Proof of Claim: Let p' extend p and G' be a generic ideal containing $p' \implies \mathbf{M}[G'] \models \tau^{G'} : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow X$ is a function, by downward stability of G' .

Hence, $\exists x \in X$ such that $\langle n, x \rangle \in \tau^{G'} \implies \text{op}(\check{n}, \check{x})^{G'} \in \tau^{G'} \implies \exists q \in G'$ such that $q \Vdash \text{op}(\check{n}, \check{x}) \in \tau$ (using Theorem Scheme 4.3.8) and by directness, q extends p' , thus proved.

In \mathbf{M} , by using the above claim, for any extension p' of p , we choose an infinite sequence (p_n) in P and a corresponding sequence (x_n) in X such that $p' \subseteq p_0 \subseteq p_1 \dots$ and $p_n \Vdash \text{op}(\check{n}, \check{x}_n) \in \tau, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$. Since $\mathbf{M} \models P$ is ω closed $\implies p^* = \bigcup p_n \in P \implies p^* \Vdash \text{op}(\check{n}, \check{x}_n) \in \tau, \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \implies \mathbf{M}[G'] \models \langle n, x_n \rangle \in \tau^{G'}$ for all generic ideal G' containing p^* . Now $p^* \in G' \implies p \in G$ and $p \Vdash \tau : \check{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \check{X}$ is a function. So we have $\tau^{G'} = (x_n)$ or all generic ideal G' containing p^* . Let us define the set

$$S = \{f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow X \mid f \in \mathbf{M}\}.$$

Clearly $S \in \mathbf{M}$ and we have $p' \subseteq p^* \Vdash \tau \in \check{S}$. Since p' was chosen arbitrarily, we conclude that the set D of elements of P that force $\tau \in \check{S}$ is dense above p . So by Theorem Scheme 4.3.8, $D \in \mathbf{M}$ and hence, by Corollary 4.3.6(1), we have that G intersects $D \implies \exists q \in G, q \Vdash \tau \in \check{S} \implies \mathbf{M}[G] \models f \in S \implies f \in \mathbf{M}$. \square

We are now ready to take the first independence proof of this document into our stride. In other words we are well-equipped enough to prove the relative consistency of CH with ZFC.

Theorem 5.1.6 (Forcing CH). *Let P be a set of all $f \in \mathbf{M}$ such that $\mathbf{M} \models$ “ f is a countable partial bijection” and let G be a generic ideal of P . Then the continuum hypothesis holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$.*

Proof. From Lemma 5.1.5, $\mathbf{M}[G]$ doesn't introduce new functions with domain $\mathbb{N} \implies \mathbf{M}[G]$ doesn't introduce new subsets of $\mathbb{N} \implies P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}} = P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$. Also due to the same reason of no new functions, $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$ remains uncountable in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ i.e. $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}} = \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$. Now Proposition 4.2.10 gives us that $G \in \mathbf{M}[G] \implies$ the union of all functions in G , i.e. a bijection f'' between a subset of $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}}$ and a subset of $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$ belongs to $\mathbf{M}[G]$. For each $A \in P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}}$, the set of functions in P with A is an element of its domain is dense and belongs to \mathbf{M} and for each $\alpha \in \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$, the set of functions in P with α is an element of its range is dense and belongs to \mathbf{M} . So from the definition of generic ideals, f'' must be a bijection between $P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}} = P(\mathbb{N})^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$ and $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}} = \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$. Thus, CH holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. \square

Hence, by Metatheorem 4.1.9, Theorem 4.2.5, Metatheorem 4.4.10 and Theorem 5.1.6, we can argue the following in PA:

Metatheorem 5.1.7. *Consistency of ZFC implies that of ZFC + CH.*

5.2 Forcing \neg CH

This section is devoted to the proof of the fact that \neg CH is also relatively consistent with ZFC. Cohen actually developed forcing as an attempt to prove this theorem, but it was later found out that a plethora of other independence results can be proved using this tool. This result along with the one developed in the last section tells us that CH is independent of ZFC (assuming consistency of ZFC).

The objective here is to allow for the appearance of \aleph_2 distinct new subsets of \mathbb{N} in the new model. Naturally this is same as adding a new subset of $\mathbb{N} \times \aleph_2$ which is in fact equivalent to adding a new function $f : \mathbb{N} \times \aleph_2 \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$. This obviously makes the set P' of *finite partial functions* from $\mathbb{N} \times \aleph_2^{\mathbf{M}}$ into $\{0, 1\}$ to be a potential candidate for the forcing notion. One of the structural properties of this set is the following :

Definition 5.2.1. *A joint-antichain in a set P is a family of pairwise incompatible elements. P is c.c.c. if every joint-antichain in P is countable.*

Here, c.c.c. is an abbreviation of ‘countable chain condition’. We will see that P is c.c.c. in Lemma 5.2.5 and Theorem 5.2.6. The importance of c.c.c. is the it allows us to

approximate functions (with domain and codomain \mathbf{M}) in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ with functions in \mathbf{M} as follows:

Lemma 5.2.2. *Let P be a forcing notion such that $\mathbf{M} \models P$ is c.c.c., let G be a generic ideal of P , let $X, Y \in \mathbf{M}$, and let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a function in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. Then there is a function $g: X \rightarrow P(Y)$ in \mathbf{M} such that for each $x \in X$ we have $f(x) \in g(x)$ and $\mathbf{M} \models$ “ $g(x)$ is countable”.*

Proof. Let τ be a P -name for f . So we have $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \tau^G : \check{X}^G \rightarrow \check{Y}^G$ is a function. By Theorem Scheme 4.3.8(1), $\exists p \in G, p \Vdash \tau : \check{X} \rightarrow \check{Y}$ is a function. For $x \in X$ we define

$$g(x) = \{y \in Y \mid \exists q \supseteq p, q \Vdash \text{op}(\check{x}, \check{y}) \in \tau\}.$$

Then $g \in \mathbf{M}$, and we have $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \text{op}(\check{x}, f(\check{x}))^G \in \tau^G \implies \exists q \in G, q \subseteq p$ (directedness), $q \Vdash \text{op}(\check{x}, f(\check{x})) \in \tau \implies f(x) \in g(x)$. We claim that $\mathbf{M} \models$ “ $g(x)$ is countable”.

Proof of Claim: Working in \mathbf{M} , for each $y \in g(x), \exists q_y \supseteq p, q_y \Vdash \text{op}(\check{x}, \check{y}) \in \tau$. Then the q_y 's are all incompatible because they all extend p and any generic ideal containing more than one of them contains p as well by downward stability. But $p \Vdash \tau : \check{X} \rightarrow \check{Y}$ is a function \implies the corresponding y 's aren't distinct. So they must be incompatible. Since, $\mathbf{M} \models P$ is c.c.c. $\implies M \models$ “ $g(x)$ is countable.” \square

From Proposition 4.2.10, \mathbf{M} and $\mathbf{M}[G]$ have the same ordinal and every cardinal in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ is a cardinal in \mathbf{M} but the converse is generally not the case because new functions appear in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. So, those forcing notions for which the converse is true are so well-behaved that they deserve better nomenclature.

Definition 5.2.3. *A forcing notion P preserves cardinals if \mathbf{M} and $\mathbf{M}[G]$ have the same cardinals for every generic ideal G of P .*

Theorem 5.2.4. *Let P be a forcing notion such that $\mathbf{M} \models$ “ P is c.c.c.” Then P preserves cardinals.*

Proof. If G is a generic ideal of P and α is an infinite ordinal in \mathbf{M} such that $\mathbf{M}[G] \models$ “ α is not a cardinal”. then $\exists \beta < \alpha$ and a surjection $f : \beta \rightarrow \alpha$ in $\mathbf{M}[G]$. Now $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbf{M}$, so the hypothesis of Lemma 5.2.2 is satisfied $\implies \exists g : \beta \rightarrow P(\alpha)$, a function in \mathbf{M} which satisfies the conditions in the lemma. Since f is surjective and $f(x) \in g(x)$ and $g(x)$ is countable, we have

$$\mathbf{M} \models \text{card}(\alpha) = \text{card}(\bigcup_{\gamma \in \beta} g(\gamma)) \leq \aleph_0 \cdot \text{card}(\beta) = \text{card}(\beta).$$

This means that α is not a cardinal in \mathbf{M} . Hence, the proof is done. \square

We now take up the task of proving that the forcing notion of finite partial functions is c.c.c, because it will give us sufficient leverage in tackling the problem. This will be done by the following lemma which is proved using graph theory. For a basic understanding of graph theory one can take a look at [13].

Lemma 5.2.5 (Δ -system lemma). *Let X be an uncountable family of finite sets. Then there is an uncountable subset Y of X and a set R such that $A \cap B = R$ for any distinct $A, B \in Y$.*

Proof. For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we define $X_k = \{A \in X \mid \text{card}(A) = k\} \implies \exists k \in \mathbb{N}, X_k$ is uncountable. We fix such a k . Now $\forall A \in X_k, \phi \in A$, and any set with more than k elements is not a subset of A . So there must be some set R (of maximum possible size) such that $0 \leq \text{card}(R) < k$ which is a subset of uncountable many elements of $X_k \implies x \notin R \implies$ only countable many elements of X_k are supersets of $R \cup \{x\}$. We fix such an R and let $X'_k = \{A \in X_k \mid R \subseteq A\}$.

We now define a graph whose vertices are elements of X'_k and if $A \cap B \neq R$ then we have an edge between them. For each $A' \in X'_k, A' \setminus R$ is finite and from our previous arguments each $x \in A' \setminus R$ can only be elements of countable many vertices. Combining these two facts, we have that each vertice has countably many neighbours.

Now we enumerate some of these vertices as $\{v_\alpha \mid \alpha < \aleph_1\}$ and at each stage, we will already have selected a countable family of vertices $\{v_\beta \mid \beta < \alpha\}$, each of them have countably many neighbours, so by uncountability of $\{v_\alpha \mid \alpha < \aleph_1\}$, we choose a new vertex which is not a neighbour of any of the previously chosen vertices.

Thus, we can find an uncountable family of sets in X'_k , no two of which are neighbours implying that their intersection equals R . \square

Here, Y is the Δ – system and R is a root.

Theorem 5.2.6. *Let P be the set of all finite partial functions from $\mathbb{N} \times \aleph_2^M$ into $\{0, 1\}$. Then P is c.c.c.*

Proof. We will work in \mathbf{M} . Let S be an uncountable subset of P and let $X = \{\text{dom}(f) \mid f \in S\}$. We observe that X is uncountable since power set of any finite set is finite so it supports only finitely many functions into $\{0, 1\}$, \implies any countable family of finite sets

can be domains of only finitely many functions into $\{0, 1\} \implies S$ must be countable, which isn't the case.

Since Lemma 5.2.5 is provable in ZFC, it holds in \mathbf{M} , so we can apply it to X to find an uncountable subset Y of X and a finite set (root) $R \subseteq \mathbb{N} \times \aleph_2$ such that $A \cap B = R, \forall A, B \in Y, A \neq B$. We then form a corresponding infinite set $T \subseteq S$, by choosing for each $A \in Y$, one $f \in S, \text{dom}(f) = A \implies \text{dom}(f) \cap \text{dom}(g) = R \forall f, g \in T, f \neq g$. Since R is finite, there are only finitely many functions from R to $\{0, 1\} \implies \exists f, g \in T, f \neq g$, such that $f|_R = g|_R \implies f, g$ are compatible. So we can conclude that any uncountable subset of P contains compatible elements. Thus, working in \mathbf{M} , we conclude P is c.c.c. \square

We now have all the machinery to show $\neg CH$ is relatively consistent with ZFC.

Theorem 5.2.7. *Let P be the set of all finite partial functions from $\mathbb{N} \times \aleph_2^{\mathbf{M}}$ into $\{0, 1\}$. Let G be a generic ideal of P . Then the continuum hypothesis fails in $\mathbf{M}[G]$.*

Proof. Using Theorems 5.2.6 and 5.2.4, we have $\aleph_2^{\mathbf{M}} = \aleph_2^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$ and by Proposition 4.2.10, we have $G \in \mathbf{M}[G] \implies$ union of all elements in G , which is also a function f' due to definition of G , is an element of $\mathbf{M}[G]$. Moreover, for each $\langle n, \alpha \rangle \in \mathbb{N} \times \aleph_2^{\mathbf{M}}$, the set of all finite partial functions with $\langle n, \alpha \rangle$ in its domain is dense and belongs to \mathbf{M} , so $\text{dom}(f') = \mathbb{N} \times \aleph_2^{\mathbf{M}}$. For each ordinal $\alpha < \aleph_2$, we define

$$A_\alpha = \{n \in \mathbb{N} \mid f'(n, \alpha) = 1\}$$

And for any $\alpha, \beta < \aleph_2$, we define

$$D_{\alpha\beta} = \{f \in P \mid \exists n \text{ in } \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } \langle n, \alpha \rangle, \langle n, \beta \rangle \in \text{dom}(f) \text{ and } f(n, \alpha) \neq f(n, \beta)\}$$

Clearly, $D_{\alpha\beta} \in \mathbf{M}$ and is dense. So by definition of generic ideals, G intersects $D_{\alpha\beta} \implies A_\alpha \neq A_\beta, \forall \alpha, \beta < \aleph_2, \alpha \neq \beta$. Since $A_\alpha \in \mathbf{M}[G] \implies \mathbf{M}[G] \models$ “there are $\aleph_2^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$ distinct subsets of \mathbb{N} ”. \square

By Metatheorem 4.1.9, Theorem 4.2.5, Metatheorem 4.4.10 and Theorem 5.2.7, we can prove the following metatheorem in PA:

Metatheorem 5.2.8. *If ZFC is consistent, then so is ZFC + $\neg CH$.*

5.3 Forcing diamond principle (\diamond)

In this section, we shall come across another statement (\diamond) and see that this statement is independent of ZFC (assuming its consistency). This statement is rather unlike CH due to the fact that it is a very combinatorial statement. But this statement has a pretty great significance in the study of various topological questions. We will use the relative consistency of $\neg CH$ (as shown in the last section) in order to derive the consistency of $\neg\diamond$ (Theorem 5.3.9). But as of now, we shall start out with a few definitions we need for stating the principle.

Definition 5.3.1 (Tree). A **tree** is a poset T containing a least element 0_T and has the property that for every $x \in T$, $x^<$ is well ordered.

The height of $x \in T$ is the ordinal isomorphic to $x^<$. A **level** of T is the set of all vertices of a given height. The **height of T** is the smallest ordinal that exceeds the height of all of its elements.

A **branch** of T is a maximal totally ordered subset. An **antichain** is a set of pairwise incompatible elements.

Definition 5.3.2 (Complete $\aleph_1 - \aleph_1$ tree). The complete $\aleph_1 - \aleph_1$ tree is a tree which is built by starting with one base vertex at level 0, putting \aleph_1 vertices above it at level 1, putting \aleph_1 vertices above each of those at level 2 and so on, through all levels $\alpha < \aleph_1$.

Every vertex at level α is nothing but an injective function $f : \alpha \rightarrow \aleph_1$ and paths all the way up the tree correspond, to a function $\tilde{f} : \aleph_1 \rightarrow \aleph_1$. It is noteworthy that at limit levels, the function is a union of those occurring below it.

The diamond principle deals with the problem of trying to obstruct all the paths up the complete $\aleph_1 - \aleph_1$ tree by deleting a single vertex at every non-zero level. But we have \aleph_1 different limit ordinal levels occurring in the complete $\aleph_1 - \aleph_1$ tree. The limit levels cause the greatest deal of problem when we try to circumvent our way up the tree by avoiding the removed vertices, since the vertex that should occur at a limit level is already determined by the vertices that have occurred below it. It is this type of continuity that causes us to face this problem and render us unable to conclude anything about this principle.

Definition 5.3.3. A subset C of \aleph_1 is **closed** if the supremum of every countable subset of C belongs to C . It is **unbounded** if for every $\beta < \aleph_1$ there exists $\alpha \in C$ such that $\alpha > \beta$. A **club** subset is one which is both closed and unbounded.

Definition 5.3.4 (Diamond principle). *The diamond principle \diamond is the assertion that one vertex can be chosen from each level of the complete $\aleph_1 - \aleph_1$ tree in such a way that for every club subset C of \aleph_1 , every path up the tree passes through one of the chosen vertices at a level belonging to C .*

More formally, \diamond states that there is a transfinite sequence of functions $h_\alpha : \alpha \rightarrow \aleph_1, \alpha < \aleph_1$ such that for any club subset $C \subseteq \aleph_1$ and any function $f : \aleph_1 \rightarrow \aleph_1$, $\exists \alpha \in C$ such that $f|_\alpha = h_\alpha$. The transfinite sequence chosen is called a *total vertex selection*.

Definition 5.3.5 (Stationary set). *A set $A \subseteq \aleph_1$ is said to be stationary if it intersects every club subset.*

An example of a stationary set is the set $\{\alpha \in \aleph_1 \mid \alpha > \beta\}$ for some $\beta \in \aleph_1$. The diamond principle can be restated as the assertion that for any path f , the set $\{\alpha \mid f|_\alpha = h_\alpha\}$ is stationary. The example in this paragraph and the above restatement leads us to conclude that stationary sets are unbounded. Relativizing to \mathbf{M} , we define the following:

Definition 5.3.6 (Partial vertex selection). *A sequence of the form $p = \{h_\beta : \beta \rightarrow \aleph_1 \mid \beta < \alpha\}, \alpha < \aleph_1$ is called a partial vertex selection and α is the **height** of p , denoted as $ht(p)$.*

Theorem 5.3.7. *Let P be the set of all $p \in \mathbf{M}$ such that $\mathbf{M} \models$ “ p is a partial vertex selection from the complete $\aleph_1 - \aleph_1$ tree” and let G be a generic ideal of P . Then the diamond principle holds in $\mathbf{M}[G]$.*

Proof. Recalling Definition 5.1.4, we have $\mathbf{M} \models$ “ P is ω closed.” From Proposition 4.2.10, we have that \mathbf{M} and $\mathbf{M}[G]$ have same ordinals. And every ordinal in both \mathbf{M} and $\mathbf{M}[G]$ less than $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$ are in bijection with \mathbb{N} and by Lemma 5.1.5, if $\mathbf{M}[G]$ contains a bijection between $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$ and \mathbb{N} then that bijection must belong to \mathbf{M} which is contradictory. Hence, we conclude that $\aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$ is the least uncountable ordinal in $\mathbf{M}[G] \implies \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}} = \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}[G]}$. Now $\bigcup_{g \in G} g$ is a total vertex selection $\{h_\alpha \mid \alpha < \aleph_1\}$. We shall see that this using this transfinite sequence, we get $\mathbf{M}[G] \models \diamond$. Let Γ be a P -name for this sequence. Let

$$\hat{\Gamma} = \{\langle \pi, p \rangle \mid \exists \sigma' \text{ such that } \langle \pi, p \rangle \in \sigma' \text{ and } \langle \sigma', p \rangle \in \Gamma\}$$

Clearly, $\hat{\Gamma}$ is a P -name. Let $f : \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}} \rightarrow \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$ be a function in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ and let $C (\subseteq \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}) \in \mathbf{M}[G]$ be a club subset. We claim that $\exists \alpha \in C$ such that $f|_\alpha = h_\alpha$. Now $f \in \mathbf{M}[G] \implies f = \tau^G$, for some P -name τ . Similarly, let σ be a P -name for C . Using Theorem Scheme 4.3.8, $\exists g \in G, g \Vdash$ “ $\tau : \check{\aleph}_1^{\mathbf{M}} \rightarrow \check{\aleph}_1^{\mathbf{M}}$ is a function and σ is a club subset of $\check{\aleph}_1^{\mathbf{M}}$.” We claim that

for any $q \supseteq p$ such that $ht(p) = \alpha, \exists \beta > \alpha$, a function $g : \alpha \rightarrow \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}} \in \mathbf{M}$, and an extension r of q such that $ht(r) \geq \beta, r \Vdash (\check{\beta} \in \sigma) \wedge (\tau|_{\check{\alpha}} = \check{g})$.

Proof of Claim: Let G' be a generic ideal containing q . Since $p \Vdash$ “ σ is unbounded”, $\exists q' \in G', \exists \beta > \alpha, q' \Vdash \check{\beta} \in \sigma$. Also, let $g = \tau^{G'}|_{\alpha}$. Using Lemma 5.1.5, $g \in \mathbf{M} \implies$ using Theorem Scheme 4.3.8, $\exists q'' \in G', q'' \Vdash \tau|_{\check{\alpha}} = \check{g}$. By directness, $\exists r \in G, r \supseteq q$ that forces both the above conditions. Again applying directness with an element of G' of height atleast β , we conclude the proof of the claim.

We fix $q \supseteq p$ and construct a sequence in \mathbf{M} $p_0 \subseteq p_1 \subseteq \dots; p_i \in P$ as follows: We define $p_0 = q$. Let p_n be given and let $ht(p_n) = \alpha_n$. We use the above claim to find p_{n+1} of height atleast $\beta_n (> \alpha_n)$ satisfying the conditions of the claim by replacing ‘ p ’ with p_n in the statement of the claim.

Let $p^* = \bigcup p_n \implies ht(p^*) = sup\alpha_n = sup\beta_n = \alpha^*. \forall n \in \mathbb{N}, p^* \Vdash \check{\beta}_n \in \sigma$. Since $p \Vdash$ “ σ is closed”, we have that $p^* \Vdash \check{\alpha}^* \in \sigma$. Let $g^* = \bigcup g_n \implies p^* \Vdash \tau|_{\check{\alpha}^*} = \check{g}^*$. Let q' be the partial vertex selection of height $\alpha^* + 1$ which extends p^* by one additional element $g^* : \alpha^* \rightarrow \aleph_1^{\mathbf{M}}$ at level α^* . Then any generic ideal G' containing q' gives rise to a total vertex selection whose value at α^* is $g^*(= \tau^{G'}|_{\alpha^*})$ i.e. q' forces $\widehat{\Gamma}$ to match τ at some level in σ , since $\widehat{\Gamma}$ evaluates to the union of sets in Γ^G .

The set containing all such q' 's is dense above p and it belongs to \mathbf{M} . By Corollary 4.3.6(1), $q'(\in G) \supseteq q$ such that q' forces $\widehat{\Gamma}$ to match τ at some level in σ . Hence, $\exists \alpha \in C$ such that $f|_{\alpha} = h_{\alpha}$. So, in $\mathbf{M}[G]$ the set $\{\alpha | f|_{\alpha} = h_{\alpha}\}$ is stationary. \square

By Metatheorem 4.1.9, Theorem 4.2.5, Metatheorem 4.4.10 and Theorem 5.2.7, the following is provable in PA:

Metatheorem 5.3.8. *If ZFC is consistent, then so is ZFC + \diamond .*

On the other hand, we have the following theorem:

Theorem 5.3.9. $\diamond \rightarrow CH$.

Proof. We know the diamond Principle asserts that in the complete $\aleph_1 - \aleph_1$ tree there exists $\langle v_{\alpha} | \alpha < \aleph_1 \rangle$, a sequence of vertices such that $\forall C$ (club subset) and $\forall P$ (path up the tree) the set $\{\alpha < \aleph_1 | v_{\alpha} \in P\}$ is stationary. So let $A \subseteq \omega$ and P_A be a path up the tree such that $\forall n < \omega$, the vertex of at the n^{th} level of P_A is the restriction of the indicator function of A to n i.e. $(P_A)_n = \psi_A|_n \implies \exists \alpha > \omega$ such that $v_{\alpha} \in P_A$, by taking the club subset to be $\{\beta < \aleph_1 | \beta \geq \omega + 1\}$. Now $B \subseteq \omega, A \neq B, v_{\alpha} \in P_A \cap P_B \implies (v_{\alpha})|_{\omega} = (P_A)_{\omega} = (P_B)_{\omega} \implies$

$\psi_A = \psi_B \implies A = B$. Hence, the map $f : P(\omega) \rightarrow \aleph_1$ defined as $f(A) = \alpha$, where we get α by the above argument, is injective $\implies |P(\omega)| \leq \aleph_1 \implies |P(\omega)| = \aleph_1 \implies \text{CH}$. \square

From Theorem 5.3.9, one can conclude that $\neg \text{CH} \rightarrow \neg \diamond$. Since $\neg \text{CH}$ is relatively consistent with ZFC, one can again conclude that by Metatheorem 4.1.9, Theorem 4.2.5, Metatheorem 4.4.10 and Theorem 5.2.7, the following is provable in PA:

Metatheorem 5.3.10. *If ZFC is consistent, then so is ZFC + $\neg \diamond$.*

Hence, we conclude that the diamond Principle is independent of ZFC (assuming consistency of ZFC).

Chapter 6

Independent statements and mathematics

Since we know that continuum hypothesis (CH) and the diamond principle are independent of ZFC (assuming consistency of ZFC), we will explore some consequences of these results in problems arising in “mainstream mathematics” in this chapter.

6.1 Erdős’s problem

This section is devoted to an answer given by Paul Erdős to a question asked by John Wetzel which relates the continuum hypothesis to entire functions in a surprising way. Wetzel asked the following:

Wetzel’s question: Let F be a family of distinct entire functions with the property that, for each $x \in \mathbb{C}$, the functions in F map x to a countable set of values. In his doctoral dissertation, Wetzel asked whether this assumption implies that F is necessarily itself countable.

However, Erdős showed that the answer to Wetzel’s question is yes if and only if the continuum hypothesis is false. But we have seen in the previous chapter that CH is independent of ZFC. This leads us to conclude that Wetzel’s question is independent to ZFC.

The statement made by Erdős regarding Wetzel’s question is also known as the Erdős’s problem. Before we get to the problem, we shall state some results which show what happens under slightly different hypothesis and also motivates Erdős’s problem. First we see a similar situation in case of \mathbb{R} .

Proposition 6.1.1. *There is a family F of 2^{\aleph_0} distinct C^∞ functions on \mathbb{R} such that for each $r \in \mathbb{R}$, the set of values $\{f(r) | f \in F\}$ is of cardinality at most 2.*

So, we see that if Wetzel restricted himself to real line and smooth functions, his question would have a negative answer.

Erdős credited an anonymous mathematician for the following proposition which restricts Wetzel's question to the finite case:

Proposition 6.1.2. *Let F be the family of entire analytic functions such that for each $z \in \mathbb{C}$, the set of values $\{f(z) | f \in F\}$ is finite. Then F is finite.*

The next proposition shows what happens if we restrict Wetzel's question to a particular family of entire functions - polynomials.

Proposition 6.1.3. *Let F be an uncountable family of polynomials. Then except for at most finitely many complex numbers, the set of values $\{f(z) | f \in F\}$ is uncountable.*

We now turn towards the solution given by Paul Erdős to Wetzel's question. This is also known as the Erdős's problem. The following is the statement of the Erdős's problem. His solution uses the following results from basic complex analysis:

- (Identity theorem) If the set of points at which two entire functions agree has a cluster point, then they must be equal.
- If an infinite sequence of entire functions converges uniformly on compact sets then the limit function is also entire analytic.
- (Proposition 6.1.2) Any uncountable subset of complex numbers must have a cluster point.

Theorem 6.1.4 (Erdős). *The continuum hypothesis is true if and only if there is an uncountable family F of entire functions such that for each $z \in \mathbb{C}$, the set of values $\{f(z) | f \in F\}$ is countable.*

Proof. (\Leftarrow) Suppose CH fails. Let $\{f_\alpha | \alpha < \aleph_1\}$ be a transfinite sequence of distinct entire functions.

Claim: $\exists z_0 \in \mathbb{C}$ such that $\{f_\alpha(z_0) | \alpha < \aleph_1\}$ is uncountable.

We define for $\alpha, \beta \in \aleph_1, \alpha \neq \beta$,

$$S_{\alpha, \beta} = \{z \in \mathbb{C} | f_\alpha(z) = f_\beta(z)\}.$$

Using the facts from complex analysis mentioned above, we have that two distinct entire functions cannot have same values at uncountably many points. So, each $S_{\alpha,\beta}$ is countable. Then $\bigcup_{\alpha \neq \beta} S_{\alpha,\beta}$ is a union of $\aleph_1^2 (= \aleph_1)$ [\cdot : \aleph_1 is infinite] countable sets and hence, has cardinality atmost \aleph_1 . Since we have assumed that CH fails and cardinality of $\mathbb{C} = 2^{\aleph_0} \implies \exists z_0 \in \mathbb{C}, z_0 \notin \bigcup_{\alpha \neq \beta} S_{\alpha,\beta}$
 \implies All functions f_α take distinct values at z_0 .
 $\implies \{f_\alpha(z_0) | \alpha < \aleph_1\}$ is uncountable.

Hence, our claim is proved.

Since this can be done for any set of exactly \aleph_1 entire functions, it obviously can be done for sets of entire functions higher cardinalities by taking a subset of cardinality \aleph_1 and repeating the above argument.

(\implies) Suppose CH holds. So, the complex plane can be enumerated as $\mathbb{C} = \{z_\alpha | \alpha < \aleph_1\}$. We will construct a transfinite sequence $\{f_\beta | \beta < \aleph_1\}$ of distinct entire functions such that $f_\beta(z_\alpha) \in \mathbb{Q} + i\mathbb{Q}, \forall \beta > \alpha$.

Since the set $\{f_\beta(z_\alpha) | \beta \leq \alpha\}$ is countable because $\alpha < \aleph_1$ (the first uncountable cardinal) and the set $\{f_\beta(z_\alpha) | \beta > \alpha\}$ is contained in the countable set $\mathbb{Q} + i\mathbb{Q}$, we will have that for every $z_\alpha \in \mathbb{C}, \{f_\beta(z_\alpha) | \beta < \aleph_1\}$ is countable.

We construct f_β inductively. For finite n , we take $f_n : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ defined as $f_n(z) = \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (z - z_i)$. We observe that for $i < n, f_n(z_i) = 0 \in \mathbb{Q} + i\mathbb{Q}$. If $\omega \leq \beta < \aleph_1$ and we have constructed f_γ for all $\gamma < \beta$, then the set $\{f_\gamma | \gamma < \beta\}$ is countable so it can be reordered as an infinite sequence (g_n) . Similarly, the countable set $\{z_\alpha | \alpha < \beta\}$ can be reordered as (w_n) . We have to find an entire function f_β satisfying

1. $f_\beta(w_n) \in \mathbb{Q} + i\mathbb{Q}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$.
2. $f_\beta(w_n) \neq g_n(w_n), \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Condition 2. ensures that $f_\beta \neq f_\gamma, \forall \gamma < \beta$. A function f_β with the desired properties can be chosen in the form

$$f_\beta(z) = \epsilon_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \epsilon_n \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (z - w_i)$$

where $|\epsilon_n| < \frac{1}{2^{n+1}(n+|w_n|)}$.

For any compact set $K (\subseteq \mathbb{C}), \exists n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $z \in K \implies |z| \leq k, \forall k \geq n$. And for $|z| \leq k (\in \mathbb{N}), |\epsilon_k \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (z - w_i)| < 2^{-k}$.

$\implies \forall z \in K, \forall k \geq n, |\epsilon_k \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (z - w_i)| < 2^{-k}$.

Hence, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \epsilon_n \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (z - w_i)$ converges uniformly on compact sets, and by the facts mentioned above, f_β is an entire function.

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we choose ϵ_n inductively as follows:

Choose $f_\beta(w_0) = \epsilon_0 \in \mathbb{Q} + i\mathbb{Q} \setminus \{g_0(w_0)\}$ such that $|\epsilon_n| < \frac{1}{2^{|w_0|}}$.

We know that, $f_\beta(w_n) = \epsilon_0 + \epsilon_1(w_n - w_0) + \dots + \epsilon_n \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (w_n - w_i)$.

Let $\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_1(w_n - w_0) + \dots + \epsilon_{n-1} \prod_{i=0}^{n-2} (w_n - w_i) = r + ir' \in \mathbb{C}$. Using density of \mathbb{Q} , $\exists q + iq' \in \mathbb{Q} + i\mathbb{Q} \setminus \{g_n(w_n)\}$ such that

$$\left| \frac{(q-r)+i(q'-r')}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (w_n - w_i)} \right| < \frac{1}{2^{n+1}(n+|w_n|)}.$$

So, by choosing $\epsilon_n = \frac{(q-r)+i(q'-r')}{\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (w_n - w_i)}$, we have $f_\beta(w_n) = q + iq'$. This completes the construction. Hence, by principle of transfinite induction, the proof of (\implies) is done. \square

So, we conclude that the statement “there is an uncountable family F of entire functions such that for each $z \in \mathbb{C}$, the set of values $\{f(z) | f \in F\}$ is countable” **is independent of ZFC** (assuming consistency of ZFC).

6.2 Suslin’s problem

Before beginning this section, the reader might take a look at [8](Chapter 4- The Ordering of \mathbb{R}). We begin with the following theorem:

Theorem 6.2.1 (Cantor). *Any totally ordered unbounded dense set which is complete and separable is order isomorphic to \mathbb{R} .*

Now, Suslin’s problem deals with the following property:

Definition 6.2.2 (Topologically c.c.c.). *A totally ordered set is said to be topologically c.c.c. if there is no uncountable collection of disjoint open intervals.*

Remark 6.2.3. *We observe that the reason of defining the concept of topologically c.c.c. as in Definition 6.2.2 is because one can consider two subsets of a totally ordered set to be ‘compatible’ if their intersection is non-empty. Now recalling Definition 5.2.1, we see that every joint-antichain in a topologically c.c.c. set is countable which implies that the set is c.c.c.*

We also observe that separability implies topologically c.c.c. because if a totally ordered set S has a countably dense subset D , then every element of a collection of disjoint

open intervals in S contains atleast one element of D which is not an element of any other member of the collection of disjoint open intervals which clearly implies that the collection of disjoint open intervals is countable because D is countable. So topologically c.c.c. is a weaker property than seperability. **Suslin's problem** is the statement that replaces the seperability condition in Theorem 6.2.1 by topologically c.c.c.

Definition 6.2.4 (Suslin lines). *A totally ordered set that is dense, unbounded, complete and topologically c.c.c., but not seperable, is called a Suslin line.*

Assuming the consistency of ZFC, one can show that the existance of Suslin lines is independent of ZFC. This tells us that if Suslin lines exist in some model of ZFC, then the assertion of Suslin's problem is false because due to order isomorphism, the Suslin line must be seperable which is not true. And in models where Suslin lines do not exist, the assertion of Suslin's problem is true due to Theorem 6.2.1, thus showing the **independence of Suslin's problem from ZFC**.

In this section, we shall see an application of the diamond principle to show how Suslin lines exist, a result due to Jensen. We begin with the following definition:

Definition 6.2.5 (Normal Suslin Tree). *A normal Suslin tree is a tree with the following properties:*

1. *Its height is \aleph_1 .*
2. *Every antichain is countable.*
3. *Every vertex has infinte many immediate successors.*
4. *Every vertex has extensions at all higher levels.*
5. *At limit levels, no two vertices have the same set of predessors.*

A normal Suslin tree has no uncountable branches. If B is a branch of a normal Suslin tree, then for each vertex $v \in B, \exists u \notin B$ such that u immediately succeeds v (using Definition 6.2.5(3)). We collect all these u 's and call this set C .

Claim: C is an antichain.

Proof of Claim: Let $v, v' \in B, ht(v) = \alpha < ht(v') = \beta$ and let $u, u' (\in C)$ immediately succeed v, v' respectively. Then $ht(u) = \alpha + 1, ht(u') = \beta + 1$. If u, u' are compatible then due to their heights, $u < u'$. Now, $u^{<}$ is well-ordered and $v < u < u', v < v' <$

$u' \implies u \leq v'$ due to their heights. Since $u'^{<}$ is well-ordered, if $ht(u) = ht(v')$ then $u = v'$ which is contradictory since $u \notin B$. And if $ht(u) < ht(v')$, then due to the fact that $u'^{<}$ is well-ordered, we have $u < v'$. So, let us collect all elements less than v' in $u'^{<}$ that are greater than u . Again by well-ordering of $u'^{<}$, $\exists v_0, u < v_0$ such that v_0 is the least element of the above collection. Now every element $w, v < w < v_0$ is less than u . The above argument is depicted as follows:

By maximality of B , we have that u belongs to B which is again contradictory. Hence, u, u' are incompatible and so, C is an antichain, thus proving the claim.

By Definition 6.2.5(2), C is countable and since C and B have a bijection between them, we conclude that B is countable.

We have the following lemma:

Lemma 6.2.6. *If normal Suslin trees exist then Suslin lines exist.*

Proof. Let T be a normal Suslin tree and let v be a vertex of T . Let I_v be the set of immediate successors of v . Clearly, I_v is an antichain because any two elements being compatible would result in one of them not being an 'immediate' successor of v . By Definition 6.2.5(2) and (3), I_v has cardinality \aleph_0 . So let \prec_v be an ordering on I_v which makes it order-isomorphic to \mathbb{Q} . Let L be the set of all branches of T and let B, B' be two distinct branches of T . By property (5), the first level where B, B' differ is at a successor level. So there is a vertex v belonging to B and B' such that v', v'' are immediate successors of B, B' respectively. We define $B \prec B' \iff v' \prec_v v''$, and observe that (L, \prec) is a **totally ordered** set.

Claim: L is **dense** and **unbounded**.

Proof of Claim: Let $B, B' \in L, B \prec B'$ and let v be a vertex in B and v', v'' be immediate successors of v such that $v' \in B, v'' \in B', v' \neq v''$. $\implies \exists v''' \in I_v, v' \prec_v v''' \prec_v v''$ (by density of \mathbb{Q}). Let B'' be a branch containing $v'''^{<}$ (exists because $v'''^{<}$ is well-ordered). Clearly, $B \prec B'' \prec B' \implies L$ is dense. Now since \mathbb{Q} is unbounded, for v' , an immediate

successor of a vertex v of a branch B , $\exists v'', v''' \in I_v, v'' \prec_v v' \prec_v v''' \implies$ one can find branches B', B'' containing $v'' \prec, v''' \prec$ respectively $\implies B' \prec B \prec B'' \implies L$ is unbounded, thus proving the claim.

Claim: L is **topologically c.c.c.**

Proof of Claim: Let $\{J_u\}$ be a collection of disjoint open intervals of L . For each u , let $B_1, B_2 \in J_u, B_1 \prec B_2; B_3, B_4 \in J_{u'}, B_3 \prec B_4$. Since, the intervals are disjoint, without loss of generality, we take $B_2 \prec B_3$. Without loss of generality, we have the following situation:

Now, w'_u 's are chosen using the density property of rationals for each interval and clearly, the w'_u 's are all distinct because the intervals are disjoint and they are incompatible because $w_u \prec w_{u'} \implies v_2, w_u \in w_{u'} \prec$. By well ordering property of $w_{u'} \prec$, and using the fact that v_2, w_u are immediate successors of v and hence, are of same height, we have $v_2 = w_u$, giving us a contradiction, hence, the set of all w'_u 's (call it S) is an antichain and by property (2), we have that S is countable, and hence, $\{J_u\}$ is countable, thus proving the claim.

Claim: L is **not seperable**.

Proof of Claim: Let D be a countable subset of L . Now, we observed before this Lemma that every branch is countable, hence using countability of D and the above fact, we have an ordinal $\alpha < \aleph_1$ (greater than the union of the ordinals at which the branches in D terminate). Let v be a vertex at level α and v', v'' be two distinct immediate successors of v . Let B, B' be two branches containing $v' \prec, v'' \prec$ respectively and without loss of generality, let $B \prec B'$. Then $S \cap (B, B') = \emptyset \implies S$ is not dense. Since S was arbitrary, we conclude that L is not seperable, hence proving the claim.

Finally, **completing** L via Dedekind cuts gives a Suslin line L' . This can be done as follows. If D is a countable dense subset of L' , then the elements of D that do not belong to L have sequences in L converging to them which implies that L must be seperable, which isn't the case. So L' is not seperable. L' is topologically c.c.c. because if $\{J_u\}$ is a collection of open disjoint intervals in L' , then $\{J_u \cap L\}$ is a collection of open disjoint intervals in $L \implies \{J_u \cap L\}$ is countable and by density of L in L' , we have that $\{J_u\}$ is countable $\implies L'$ is topologically c.c.c., thus giving us a Suslin line. \square

Assuming the diamond principle, we shall construct a normal Suslin tree which will imply existence of Suslin lines by Lemma 6.2.6. Before doing so, we need the following lemma which will play a key role in proving the above statement:

Lemma 6.2.7. *Let T be a tree of height \aleph_1 , let A be a maximal antichain in T , and for each $\alpha < \aleph_1$ let T_α be a subtree of T consisting of all vertices of height less than α . Suppose that each T_α is countable. Then*

$$C = \{\alpha \mid A \cap T_\alpha \text{ is a maximal antichain in } T_\alpha\}$$

is a club subset of \aleph_1 .

Proof. $A \cap T_\alpha$ is clearly an antichain in T_α , $\forall \alpha < \aleph_1$.

Claim: C is **closed**.

Proof of Claim: Let $\{\alpha_n\}_{n \in \omega}$ be a sequence in C and let $\alpha = \bigcup_{n < \omega} \alpha_n \implies \forall x \in T_\alpha, \exists n \in \mathbb{N}, x \in T_{\alpha_n}$ and by maximality of $A \cap T_{\alpha_n}, \exists y \in A \cap T_{\alpha_n}$ such that x is compatible with y . Thus every element of T_α is compatible with some element of $A \cap T_\alpha \implies A \cap T_\alpha$ is a maximal antichain in $T_\alpha \implies \alpha \in C$, thus proving our claim.

Claim: C is **unbounded**.

Proof of Claim: Let $\alpha_1 < \aleph_1. \implies T_{\alpha_1}$ is countable and every element of T_{α_1} is comparable to some element of A , by maximality of A . So there exists an ordinal $\alpha_2 (\geq \alpha_1)$ (which can be found by taking union of the heights of every element of A to whom elements of T_{α_1} is compatible) such that every element of T_{α_1} is compatible with some element of T_{α_2} . Similarly, one can find $\alpha_3, \alpha_4 \dots$ and obtain a sequence $\{\alpha_n\}_{n < \omega}$. Let $\alpha = \bigcup_{n < \omega} \alpha_n$, we thus have that every element of T_α is compatible to some element in $T_\alpha \cap A \implies T_\alpha \cap A$ is maximal $\implies \alpha (\geq \alpha_1) \in C \implies C$ is unbounded, proving the claim. From the above two claims, we conclude that C is a club subset of \aleph_1 . \square

Theorem 6.2.8. *Assume \diamond . Then Suslin lines exist.*

Proof. Since we have assumed $\diamond, \exists \langle h_\alpha : \alpha \rightarrow \aleph_1 \mid \alpha < \aleph_1 \rangle$, a sequence of vertices in the complete $\aleph_1 - \aleph_1$ tree such that for any function $f : \aleph_1 \rightarrow \aleph_1$, the set $\{\alpha \mid f|_\alpha = h_\alpha\}$ is stationary. Let $A_\alpha = h_\alpha^{-1}(1) \subseteq \alpha, \forall \alpha < \aleph_1$ and $A \subseteq \aleph_1$. So if we let $f : \aleph_1 \rightarrow \aleph_1$ to be the characteristic function of A , then $f|_\alpha^{-1}(1) = A \cap \alpha$ and $f|_\alpha = h_\alpha \implies f|_\alpha^{-1}(1) = h_\alpha^{-1}(1) = A_\alpha \implies S = \{\alpha \mid A_\alpha = A \cap \alpha\}$ is stationary.

We shall see a construction of a normal Suslin tree T whose vertices are precisely the countable ordinals which shall be taken in order i.e. every time a new vertex is added, it

will be the first ordinal not yet used. We shall ensure that every subtree T_α shall satisfy the following:

1. T_α will be countable.
2. For any $\beta, \beta' < \alpha$, every vertex of height β will lie below a vertex of height β' .

The last condition ensures that if α is a limit ordinal then every vertex v in T_α belongs to a branch in T_α whose height is α .

The construction of the tree is as follows: Let 0 be the base vertex constituting the subtree T_1 . Assuming that $T_{\alpha+1}$ has been constructed for some α , the $\alpha+1$ level of the tree is constructed by adding \aleph_0 immediate successors to each vertex at level α . By induction hypothesis, $T_{\alpha+1}$ had countable many vertices and since, we are adding countable many new vertices, so (1) is preserved. Also, since by hypothesis every vertex of height less than α lies below a vertex of height α , (2) is satisfied.

Now let α be a limit ordinal and we have constructed T_α . If A_α (defined as earlier) is not a maximal antichain in T_α , then for each $v \in T_\alpha$, we choose a branch containing v of height α (using (2)) and add one vertex at level α to lie above each of these branches. Since T_α is countable and only countable many vertices have been added, (1) is preserved and clearly, from the construction, (2) is preserved as well. If A_α is a maximal antichain in T_α , then $\forall v \in T_\alpha, \exists a_v \in A_\alpha$ such that v, a_v are compatible. So v lies either above or below some element in A_α , so the same construction as before can be done but in this

case, one makes sure that the branch of height α contains an element of A_α , for each v , thus completing the construction of T .

In order to verify that T is a normal Suslin tree, we observe that except for property (2) in Definition 6.2.5, other conditions are satisfied. So we claim the following:

Claim: Every antichain in T is countable.

Proof of Claim: Let $A \subseteq T$ be a maximal antichain. By Lemma 6.2.7, $C = \{\alpha | A \cap T_\alpha \text{ is a maximal antichain in } T_\alpha\}$ is a club. Also, the set $\{\alpha \in C | T_\alpha = \alpha\}$ is a club. This is because showing closure property is trivial because we do union of equal sets and for checking unboundedness, we observe that $\forall \alpha, \alpha \subseteq T_\alpha$ and one gets equality at the supremum of any sequence (α_n) with the property that $T_{\alpha_n} \subseteq \alpha_{n+1}, \forall n < \omega$. From \diamond and the fact that S is stationary, we conclude that $\exists \alpha$ such that $A_\alpha = A \cap T_\alpha$ is a maximal antichain in T_α . Then the construction of the α -th level of T ensures that every vertex at level α lies above some element of $A \cap T_\alpha$. So $A \cap T_\alpha$ must be a maximal antichain in T , and by maximality of A , we have $A = A \cap T_\alpha \implies A$ is countable, thus proving (2) and hence, we conclude that T is a normal Suslin tree.

By Lemma 6.2.6, it is enough to show that a normal Suslin tree exists. □

Since \diamond is relatively consistent with ZFC (assuming consistency of ZFC), we have found a model of ZFC where Suslin lines exist which implies that in this model, the assertion of Suslin doesn't hold.

One can also construct a model of ZFC in which Suslin lines do not exist, thus showing the independence of Suslin's assertion from ZFC. We haven't included this construction in the thesis and have broadly stated the steps involved in the proof as follows:

1. Martin's Axiom(MA): If P is non-empty c.c.c. poset and $\{D_\alpha | \alpha < 2^{\aleph_0}\}$ is a family of dense subsets of P , then there is an ideal of P that intersects every D_α .
2. (Metatheorem) If ZFC is consistent, then so is ZFC + MA + " $2^{\aleph_0} = \aleph_2$ ".
3. If Suslin lines exist then Suslin trees exist.
4. MA + " $2^{\aleph_0} = \aleph_2$ " \implies Suslin lines do not exist.

Chapter 7

Solovay's Model

Mathematics in its infancy was considered in the western world to be the manifestation of ultimate truth and was regarded as supreme science. Other empirical sciences were at that time considered to yield results which were debatable. This was demonstrated by an inscription in Plato's house, "Let no one ignorant or less informed about geometry enter this place."

However as time passed, mathematicians started building complicated and highly counter-intuitive objects such as the Banach-Tarski paradox. Such objects relied on one controversial axiom, the choice axiom. The controversy was due to the fact that one couldn't describe adequately the objects so created by this axiom, but could only talk about its properties, often leading to such counter-intuitive constructions.

This was followed by a three-fold split in the mathematical community based on the following opinions:

1. The choice axiom is excessively strong and is making mathematics shift away from reality. So one should look for a slightly weaker axiom.
2. We don't intend to discard choice axiom, but try to form a definable heirarchy of sets, which are supposed to not lead to such queer constructions. The objective was to squeeze as much mathematics to work inside this heirarchy as possible.
3. Mathematics should be studied in its own right and be not bothered about such concerns posed by one's empirical expectations.

Of these, the second school led to the birth of descriptive set theory, which has immense contributions in fields such as ergodic theory and other branches of mathematics developed

as a result of influence from empirical sciences. The Solovay's model is a bridge between the first two schools of thought, even though it seems that it is more inclined towards the first. This chapter has been primarily developed from [16] and [2].

7.1 Levy collapse and smallest models

Definition 7.1.1 (Inaccessible cardinal). *A cardinal κ is said to be inaccessible (or strongly inaccessible) if for any cardinal $\lambda < \kappa$, a subset of κ of size λ cannot have its supremum to be κ and for any cardinal $\beta < \kappa$, $2^\beta < \kappa$.*

In this chapter we shall work in the theory ZFC^{++} which consists of all the axioms of ZFC^+ along with the axiom of existence of an inaccessible cardinal relativized to M . We assume the standard fact that the consistency of ZFC implies consistency of ZFC^{++} .

The Levy collapse is such a forcing notion, which makes an inaccessible cardinal in the ground model become \aleph_1 in the forcing extension.

Let $P = \{f \mid f \subseteq (\mathbb{N} \times \kappa) \times \kappa, f \text{ is finite function and } f(n, \lambda) < \lambda, \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } \forall \lambda \in \kappa\}$. Now if M is a model of ZFC in which there is an inaccessible cardinal κ , and G is a generic ideal, then we have the following theorems:

Theorem 7.1.2. *For any $\lambda < \kappa$, in $M[G]$, λ is countable.*

Proof. Let for any $\alpha \in \kappa$, $f_\alpha = \{(n, \beta) \mid ((n, \alpha), \beta) \in G\}$. Clearly f_α is a function, since $\bigcup G$ is a function. Now let $D_{\lambda, n} = \{f \mid (n, \lambda) \in \text{dom}(f)\}$. Clearly, $D_{\lambda, n}$ is dense. So $\text{dom}(f_\lambda) = \mathbb{N}$. Now for $\beta < \lambda$, let $D_\beta = \{f \mid \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } f(n, \lambda) = \beta\}$. Again D_β is dense. Thus, $\beta \in \text{ran}(f_\lambda) \implies f_\lambda : \omega \rightarrow \lambda$ is a surjection. \square

Theorem 7.1.3. *In $M[G]$, $\kappa = \aleph_1$.*

Proof. In order to prove this, we just need to show that κ is a cardinal in $M[G]$. Like in Theorem 5.2.4, $\kappa - c.c.$ forcing notions (those in which every antichain is of cardinality strictly less than κ) preserves cardinals $\geq \kappa$. So, we will prove that P is $\kappa - c.c.$. Then we can use Theorem 7.1.2 to conclude the proof.

Without loss of generality, let $A \subseteq P$ be a maximal antichain. We now construct a sequence of ordinals as follows: Let $\zeta_0 = \omega$ and $P^\zeta = \{f \mid f \subseteq (\omega \times \zeta) \times \zeta, f \text{ is finite function and } f(n, \lambda) < \lambda, \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } \forall \lambda \in \zeta\}$ where ζ is an ordinal. Suppose we have defined $\zeta_i < \kappa$. Then by inaccessibility, $\text{card}(P^{\zeta_i}) < \kappa$. Now for each $h \in P^{\zeta_i}$ by maximality of A , we

can find $f_h \in A$ such that h and f_h are compatible, and $\zeta(h)$ such that $f_h \in P^{\zeta(h)}$ and $\zeta_i < \zeta(h) < \kappa$. Since $|\{\zeta(h) | h \in P^{\zeta_i}\}| < \kappa$, $\sup\{\zeta(h) | h \in P^{\zeta_i}\} < \kappa$. We call this supremum ζ_{i+1} and in this way we form a sequence $\{\zeta_i | i < \omega\}$. Let $\zeta_\omega = \sup\{\zeta_i | i < \omega\}$.

Claim: $A \subseteq P^{\zeta_\omega}$.

Proof of claim: If $\exists g \in A \setminus P^{\zeta_\omega}$, let $g|_{\omega \times \zeta_\omega} = g'$. Since g' is finite, $g' \in P^{\zeta_i}$, for some $i \in \omega$. This implies that $\exists g'' \in A \cap P^{\zeta_{i+1}}$ such that g'' and g' are compatible. Since $g'' \subseteq (\omega \times \zeta_\omega) \times \zeta_\omega$, g'' is compatible with g , thus contradicting the fact that A is an antichain. So $A \subseteq P^{\zeta_\omega}$, thus proving the claim.

Now $|P^{\zeta_\omega}| < \kappa$. So P is $\kappa - c.c.$ and hence, κ is a cardinal in $M[G]$. □

Suppose we have $x \in M[G]$ and we want to construct a model N of ZFC such that $x \in N$, $M \subseteq N$ and for any model K of ZFC satisfying these two conditions, $N \subseteq K$. Here we shall describe the construction and refer the reader to [8] for further details.

Let $L' = \{\in, U\}$ be a new language in which \in is the usual \in of set theory and U is a unary predicate symbol. From now on, while working in $M[G]$, we shall use the language L' , unless otherwise stated.

For a P -name σ and $p \in P$, we say $p \Vdash U(\sigma) \iff p \Vdash \exists x(\sigma = \check{x})$. In other words, $p \Vdash U(\sigma) \iff \forall G$ generic ideal ($p \in G \leftrightarrow \sigma^G \in M$). We let $L_0[x, M] = \phi$, $L_{\beta+1}[x, M] = \text{Set}$ consisting of subsets of $L_\beta[x, M]$ definable from x and for any limit ordinal δ , $L_\delta[x, M] = \bigcup_{\beta < \delta} L_\beta[x, M]$. We note that the above construction takes place in $M[G]$. We will understand the significance of the above construction in the subsequent sections.

7.2 Measurability and Borel heirarchy

We recall the following lemma:

Lemma 7.2.1. *A subset A of \mathbb{R} is measurable if and only if there is a Borel set B such that $\mu(A \Delta B) = 0$.*

In order to consider measurability, one needs to look at the Borel sets of $M[G]$ and try to find a way to create a model in which only those subsets of \mathbb{R} are there for which the Lemma 7.2.1 holds.

We have a certain advantage while dealing with Borel sets. No matter which model of ZFC we work in, one thing remains common, which is the fact that Borel sets can

be “heirarchically” arranged in levels where the sets occuring at lower levels are simpler in definition than those at higher levels. The construction is as follows: The 0^{th} level consists of open bounded intervals; suppose we have constructed the levels for all ordinals $\beta < \delta$. Then the δ^{th} level consists of countable union of sets occuring in levels below δ and complements of them. It can be seen that there is no need to proceed this construction beyond levels of countable ordinals as no new sets are added in uncountable stages.

Now certainly it is the reals in each model which determine what the Borel sets in each model are, but does the above common framework help us to find some links between Borel sets in these models? One can answer this question using Kleene’s theorem (Theorem 7.2.3).

Definition 7.2.2 (Π_1^1 Formula). *A Π_1^1 Formula is a formula of the form $\forall f\psi$, where $f : \omega \rightarrow \omega$ is a function and ψ has quantification over non-negative integers only.*

Theorem 7.2.3 (Kleene). *If M, N are two models of ZFC such that $M \subseteq N$, then for any formula ϕ , if ϕ is Π_1^1 , then it is absolute for M and N .*

In order to adapt the framework into that of Kleene’s theorem, we do the following coding: Let $a \rightarrow \bar{a}$ be the natural bijection between ω and \mathbb{Q} . Now let $f \in \omega^\omega$.

- If $f(0) \equiv 0(mod3)$, then f codes $(f(\bar{1}), f(\bar{2}))$ (open interval) if $f(\bar{1}) < f(\bar{2})$ otherwise codes $(f(\bar{2}), f(\bar{1}))$.
- If $f(0) \equiv 1(mod3)$ then f codes $\bigcup_{f_r} B_{f_r}$, where $f_r(x) = f(2^r(2x + 1)), \forall x, r \in \omega$ provided the f_r s code borel sets B_r .
- If $f(0) \equiv 2(mod3)$, then if $g \in \omega^\omega, g(n) = f(n + 1)$ codes B_g , then f codes $\mathbb{R} \setminus B_g$.

One can easily verify that the elements used from ω^ω for the above coding in turn codes the entire Borel σ -algebra. This coding not only adapts the framework to suit Kleene’s theorem but also codes up the Borel sets in a model by reals present in that model. Now we make some adjustments to find a way of using Kleene’s theorem.

The idea is that if we take a Borel set and try to go down the heirarchy, then we shall reach the 0^{th} level after a finite number of steps. Let $g \in \omega^\omega$. Then one can ‘approximate’ g by finite partial functions from ω to ω . So we consider the collection of functions of the form $s : n \rightarrow \omega, n \in \omega$. We map s to $p_1^{s(0)+1} \cdot p_2^{s(1)+1} \dots p_n^{s(n-1)+1}$, where p_n is the n^{th} prime; and the empty sequence goes to 1. The reason for doing this is that we want to make

the approximation process of g by such functions to be coded up by functions in ω^ω and non-negative integers only.

We define $\phi(g, -) : \omega \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \omega^\omega$ inductively as follows:

- $\phi(g, 1) = g$

For $n > 1$, let the sequence corresponding to n be $\langle s(0), s(1), \dots, s(k-1) \rangle$. We call the integer corresponding to $\langle s(0), s(1), \dots, s(k-2) \rangle$ to be m .

- If $\phi(g, m)(0) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, then $\phi(g, n) = 0$, the constant function.
- If $\phi(g, m)(1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, then $\phi(g, n)(x) = \phi(g, m)(2^{s(k-1)}(2x+1)), \forall x \in \omega$.
- If $\phi(g, m)(0) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then $\phi(g, n)(x) = \phi(g, m)(x+1), \forall x \in \omega$, where m is as in last case.

Clearly, if g codes a Borel set, so does $\phi(g, n), \forall n \in \omega$. Now for $g : \omega \rightarrow \omega$, we define $\bar{g} : \omega \rightarrow \omega$ as, $\bar{g}(n) = p_1^{g(0)+1} \cdot p_2^{g(1)+1} \dots p_n^{g(n-1)+1}, \bar{g}(0) = 1$. Let

$$A_1(g) := \forall f \in \omega^\omega \exists n \in \omega (\phi(g, \bar{f}(n)) = 0)$$

Theorem 7.2.4. *Let $g \in \omega^\omega$. Then g codes a Borel set if and only if $A_1(g)$ holds.*

Proof. (\Leftarrow) Suppose g doesn't code a Borel set. Then $g(0) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $2 \pmod{3}$. If $g(0) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then $\exists r \in \omega$ such that g_r doesn't code a Borel set. So let $f(0) = r$. If $g(0) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then we put $f(0) = 0$. We repeat the same check for $\phi(g, \bar{f}(0))$ and accordingly select $f(1)$ and so on... So inductively we have found a function $f \in \omega^\omega$ such that $\neg \exists n \in \omega (\phi(g, \bar{f}(n)) = 0) \implies$ If $A_1(g)$ holds then g codes a Borel set.

(\implies) Follows from induction on the minimum level at which a Borel set occurs in the heirarchy. □

We observe that $A_1(g)$ is a Π_1^1 formula. So using Kleene's theorem, if M is a model of ZFC and $g \in M$ and N is another model of ZFC containing M , then g codes a Borel set in M if and only if it does so in N .

Definition 7.2.5. *If x is a real, $g, h \in \omega^\omega$ then we define a formula $A_4(g, h, x)$ as follows:*

1. *If $\phi(g, n)(0) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \phi(g, n)(1) = i$ and $\phi(g, n)(2) = j$, then $h(n) = 1 \iff x \in (\bar{i}, \bar{j})$ (or (\bar{j}, \bar{i}) as the case may be).*

2. $\phi(g, n)(0) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, let the sequence corresponding to n be $\langle s_0, s_1, \dots, s(k-1) \rangle$ and m be the number corresponding to $\langle s_0, s_1, \dots, s(k-2) \rangle$ and $m_j = p_k^{j+1}$, $j \in \omega$. Then $h(n)=1 \iff h(n.m_j)$ for some j .
3. If $\phi(g, n)(0) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, $h(n)=1 \iff h(m)=0$.
4. $h(n)=0$ or $1 \forall n \in \omega$

We note that in 2. $h(n) = 1 \iff x \in$ The Borel set coded by atleast one of $\phi(g, n)_j$ and 3. implies $h(n) = 1 \iff x \notin \mathbb{R} \setminus B_{\phi(g, m)}$. So we see that A_4 has quantification involved only in 2. and 4. and they are over j and n which are in ω . So $\forall h(A_4(g, h, x) \wedge A_1(g)) \leftrightarrow x \in B_g$ and $\forall h(A_4(g, h, x))$ is a Π_1^1 formula. So $\forall h(A_4(g, h, x) \wedge A_1(g))$ is provably equivalent to a Π_1^1 formula. So by Kleene's theorem, for $x, g \in M, x \in B_g^M \leftrightarrow x \in B_g^N \implies B_g^M = B_g^N \cap M$.

Corollary 7.2.6. For x and $g \in M, x \notin B_g^M \leftrightarrow x \notin B_g^N$.

Corollary 7.2.7. For $f, g \in \omega^\omega$, there are Π_1^1 formulas $A_6(f, g), A_5(f, g)$ which state that $B_f \subseteq B_g, B_f = B_g$ respectively.

The crux of these provable equivalences lies in the fact that for a finite number of functions $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n \in \omega^\omega$ there is a natural function $f \in \omega^\omega$ which takes all of these into account.

The theorems developed so far can be used to establish a connection between the Borel σ algebra of a model M and the Borel σ algebra of a bigger model N as follows:

Suppose $B \in M$ is a Borel set. Then $\exists f \in \omega^\omega$ such that f codes B_f in M . Now $\because M \subseteq N, f$ will code some Borel set, say B_f^N in N . Now $f \rightarrow B_f$ is a function, and if $g \in M$ also codes B , then $B_f = B_g$. So we can map B to B_f^N to form a function from the Borel σ -algebra of M to that of N . We describe this map by $B \rightarrow B^\sharp$. We list down some properties of this map which follow from its definition and some other properties of this map.

1. $(\bar{i}, \bar{j})^\sharp = (\bar{i}, \bar{j})^N$.
2. $(\bigcup_{n \in \omega} A_n)^\sharp = \bigcup_{n \in \omega} A_n^\sharp$
3. $(\mathbb{R} \setminus A)^\sharp = \mathbb{R}^N \setminus A^\sharp$.
4. $[\bar{i}, \bar{j}]^\sharp = [\bar{i}, \bar{j}]^N$.

5. From 1., 2. and separability, open sets are mapped to open sets.
6. From 3. and 5., closed sets are mapped to closed sets.
7. From 6. and that $A_5(f, g)$ is Π_1^1 , compactness is also preserved by this map.

We shall now prove the most important theorem of this section.

Theorem 7.2.8. *The map $B \rightarrow B^\sharp$ preserves the Lebesgue outer measure of sets, and hence preserves Lebesgue measurability and Lebesgue measure of the measurable sets.*

Proof. We use the fact that any open set can be expressed as a countable disjoint union of open intervals with rational endpoints. From the above properties, we have $\mu(\sqcup_{i=1}^n(\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i)) = \Sigma_{i=1}^n(\bar{b}_i - \bar{a}_i) = \mu((\sqcup_{i=1}^n(\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i))^\sharp)$, μ is Lebesgue measure. If U is an open set such that $U = \sqcup_{i=1}^\infty(\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i)$ and $\mu(U) = \sup_{n \in \omega}(\mu(\sqcup_{i=1}^n(\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i))) = \sup_{n \in \omega}(\Sigma_{i=1}^n(\bar{b}_i - \bar{a}_i)) = \sup_{n \in \omega}(\mu((\sqcup_{i=1}^n(\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i))^\sharp)) = \mu(U^\sharp)$. \square

Now using outer regularity, we can say that the Lebesgue measure of every Borel set is preserved.

Corollary 7.2.9. *Measure 0 set is an absolute notion. Hence, measurability is also absolute.*

So, the entire development in this section says that if a Borel set in N has a Borel code in M , then we see that the Lebesgue measure of this set is same as that which is coded by that code in M . Thus, we make a definition for such sets.

Definition 7.2.10. *A Borel set is said to be rational over M , if it has a Borel code in M .*

Now $\omega < \kappa$ and by inaccessibility, $2^{2^\omega} < \kappa$. So in $M[G]$, since $\kappa = \aleph_1$, $\{B^\sharp : \mu(B) = 0\}$ is countable. So $\cup\{B^\sharp : \mu(B) = 0\}$ is a measure 0 set in $M[G]$ and adding(or removing) a subset of it to (or from) a set of reals in $M[G]$ doesn't change its measurability. It is the reals in the complement of it, which we need to worry about.

Definition 7.2.11 (Random Real). *A real x is said to be random if and only if there is no set of measure zero rational over M such that x belongs to it.*

7.3 Random reals and Boolean algebra of Borel sets

We define an equivalence relation \sim on the Borel σ - algebra \mathbb{B} in M as follows: We say that two Borel sets B_1, B_2 are such that $B_1 \sim B_2 \iff \mu(B_1 \Delta B_2) = 0$, μ is the Lebesgue measure. Now let \mathbb{B}/\sim denote the set of all equivalence classes. The Boolean Algebra operations are defined as follows:

- $[B_1] \vee [B_2] = [B_1 \cup B_2]$
- $[B_1] \wedge [B_2] = [B_1 \cap B_2]$
- $[B_1]^* = [\mathbb{R} \setminus B_1]$ (complementation in Boolean algebras)

We state the following standard facts here:

Theorem 7.3.1. $(\mathbb{B}/\sim, \vee, \wedge, [\phi], [\mathbb{R}], *)$ forms a Boolean algebra.

Theorem 7.3.2. $(\mathbb{B}/\sim, \vee, \wedge, [\phi], [\mathbb{R}], *)$ is a complete Boolean algebra in M .

Theorem 7.3.3. For any $S \subseteq \mathbb{B}/\sim, \exists S_0 \subseteq S$ such that S_0 is countable and $\vee S_0 = \vee S$.

Definition 7.3.4. A function $h : \mathbb{B}/\sim \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is said to be completely additive, homomorphism if

- $h([B_1] \vee [B_2]) = h([B_1]) \vee h([B_2])$
- $h([B_1] \wedge [B_2]) = h([B_1]) \wedge h([B_2])$
- $h([B_1]^*) = (h([B_1]))^*$
- $h(\vee S) = \vee h(S)$

for each $[B_1], [B_2] \in \mathbb{B}/\sim, S \subseteq \mathbb{B}/\sim$.

We note that for any non-constant completely additive function, $[\phi] \rightarrow 0$.

We had mentioned in Chapter 4 that the entire machinery of forcing can be developed with exactly the same constructions by replacing the partial order \subseteq in the forcing notion with any partial order. So now we have the following definition:

Definition 7.3.5. The ordering \leq on the forcing notion $\mathbf{P} = (\mathbb{B}/\sim) \setminus [\phi]$ is defined as $[B_1] \leq [B_2] \iff B_1 \supseteq B_2, \forall [B_1], [B_2] \in \mathbf{P}$.

We note that this this ordering is the reverse of the Boolean Algebra ordering.

Theorem 7.3.6. *Completely additive functions preserve the Boolean Algebra Order.*

Theorem 7.3.7. *For a non-constant completely additive homomorphism h , $h^{-1}(\{1\})$ is a generic ideal in M , and for any generic ideal \bar{G} of \mathbf{P} , if we define $h' : \mathbb{B}/\sim \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as $h'([B]) = 1$ if and only if $[B] \in \bar{G}$, then h' is a non-constant completely additive homomorphism.*

Proof. Suppose $h : \mathbb{B}/\sim \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be a non-constant completely additive homomorphism. Then if $[B_1], [B_2] \in h^{-1}(\{1\})$, then $h([B_1]) = 1 = h([B_2])$.

Now $h([B_1] \wedge [B_2]) = h([B_1]) \wedge h([B_2]) = 1 \wedge 1 = 1$. Also $[B_1] \wedge [B_2] \geq [B_1], [B_2]$. Again for $[B] \in h^{-1}(\{1\})$, $[B_1] \leq [B] \implies h([B_1]) = 1$, since h preserves Boolean Algebra order. From Theorem 7.3.6, $h([B_1]) = 1 \implies h^{-1}(\{1\})$ is an ideal.

Claim: If $D \subseteq P$ is dense then $D \cap h^{-1}(\{1\})$ is non-empty.

Proof of Claim: If possible let $D \cap h^{-1}(\{1\}) = \phi$. Then $h(d) = 0, \forall d \in D$. This implies $h(\vee D) = \vee h(D) = 0$. Let $\vee D = d_0 \implies h(d_0^*) = 1 \implies d_0^* \neq [\phi] \implies d_0^* \in P \implies \exists$ an extension of d_0^* in D . Let that extension be d . But then d is an extension of both $d_0, d_0^* \implies d = [\phi] \in P$, which is contradictory. Thus, our *claim is proved*.

So we have shown that $h^{-1}(\{1\})$ is a generic ideal. Now if we let \bar{G} be a generic ideal and define $h' : \mathbb{B}/\sim \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as $h'([B]) = 1 \iff [B] \in \bar{G}$. Then by a routine calculation, one can check that $h'([B_1] \vee [B_2]) = h'([B_1]) \vee h'([B_2]); h'([B_1] \wedge [B_2]) = h'([B_1]) \wedge h'([B_2]); h'([B_1]^*) = (h'([B_1]))^*$ and that h' is non-constant. We claim that $h'(\vee S) = \vee h'(S), \forall S \subseteq \mathbb{B}/\sim$.

Proof of Claim: For any $S \subseteq \mathbb{B}/\sim$, either $S \cap \bar{G} = \phi$ or $S \cap \bar{G} \neq \phi$. If $S \cap \bar{G} = \phi$, let $\vee S = s_0, D = \{p \in P \mid \exists s (s \in \bar{S} \wedge p \geq s) \text{ or } p \text{ is incompatible with } s_0\}$, \bar{S} is the upward closure of S . If for any $p' \in P, p'$ is incompatible with $s_0 \implies p' \in D$. If p' is compatible with s_0 , then p', s_0 have a common extension, say $p'' \implies p'' \in \bar{S} \implies p'' \in D \implies D$ is dense $\implies D \cap \bar{G} \neq \phi$. By downward stability of $\bar{G}, S \cap \bar{G} \neq \phi$, which is a contradiction. So, $S \cap \bar{G} = \phi \implies s_0 \notin \bar{G}$. So $h'(S) = \{0\} \implies h'(\vee S) = h'(s_0) = 0 = \vee h'(S)$. If $S \cap \bar{G} \neq \phi$, downward stability gives us $\vee S \in \bar{G}$. So we have $h'(\vee S) = 1 = \vee h'(S)$, completing the proof of the claim as well as of the theorem. \square

Before we move on the next theorem, we fix a notational issue. If x is a real, then instead of writing $L[x, M]$, we will write $M[x]$ for convinience.

Theorem 7.3.8. *For a generic ideal \bar{G} of \mathbf{P} , $\exists x$ a random real, such that $M[x] = M[\bar{G}]$.*

Proof. We define $h : \mathbb{B}/\sim \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as $h([B]) = 1 \iff [B] \in \bar{G}$. Now we consider the set $\{r \in \mathbb{Q} | h([(r, \infty)]) = 1\}$. A routine check shows that this set defines a left Dedekind cut. We call this real x . Then $x \in M[\bar{G}]$, as we have defined it from $\bar{G} \implies M[x] \subseteq M[\bar{G}]$. Again $\bar{G} = \{[B] | x \in B^\sharp\}$. This proof is a standard induction argument which can be found in [16].

So we have that \bar{G} can be defined from x . So $M[\bar{G}] \subseteq M[x].x$ is a random real follows from the fact that, if $x \in B^\sharp, \mu(B^\sharp) = 0$ then due to absoluteness, $\mu(B) = 0$ too, then $[B] = [\phi]$ and then $[\phi] \in \bar{G}$ contradicting the fact that h is non-constant. \square

The next theorem which we shall prove is a very strong one. In our preliminary studies about forcing, we saw that for a formula ϕ , if $p \Vdash \phi$, then $p \in G \rightarrow M[G] \models \phi$. But $M[G] \models \phi \not\rightarrow p \in G$. However, in case of \mathbf{P} , it is very different. We state the theorem as follows:

Theorem 7.3.9. *For any formula ϕ of the language L' , $\exists b_0 \in \mathbf{P}$ such that for any generic ideal \bar{G} of \mathbf{P} , $M[\bar{G}] \models \phi \leftrightarrow b_0 \in \bar{G}$.*

Proof. For the formula ϕ , let $\bigvee \{p \in \mathbf{P} | p \Vdash \phi\} = b_0$. Then we just need to show that $b_0 \in \bar{G} \leftrightarrow \{p \in \mathbf{P} | p \Vdash \phi\} \cap \bar{G}$ is non-empty. Let $T = \{p \in \mathbf{P} | p \Vdash \phi\}$. Let \bar{T} be the upward closure of T . Let $D = \{p \in \mathbf{P} | \exists t (t \in \bar{T} \wedge p \geq t) \text{ or } p \text{ is incompatible with } b_0\}$. As in the proof of the previous theorem, we can show that D is dense. So $\bar{G} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. So $b_0 \in \bar{G} \implies \exists t \in \bar{T}$ and $p \in G$ such that $p \geq t \implies \bar{G} \cap T \neq \emptyset \implies \exists t \in \bar{G} (t \Vdash \phi) \implies M[G] \models \phi$.

Conversely, if $M[G] \models \phi, \exists t \in T \cap \bar{G}$. By downward stability $b_0 \in \bar{G}$, completing the proof. \square

Let us consider the set $C = (M^{\mathbf{P}} \setminus \{\Gamma\}) \cup \{\hat{x}\}$ where $M^{\mathbf{P}}$ is the collection of all \mathbf{P} -names in M and $\Gamma = \{(\check{p}, p) | p \in \mathbf{P}\}, \hat{x} \in M \setminus M^{\mathbf{P}}$. We define a map $f_x : C \rightarrow M[G]$ corresponding to a real x in $M[G]$ be defined as $f_x(\hat{x}) = x$. Let $G_x = \{[B] | x \in B^\sharp\}$. Now G_x will be an ideal. For any $\sigma \in M^{\mathbf{P}} \setminus \{\Gamma\}, f_x(\sigma) = \sigma^{G_x}$. We note that if x is a random real, then $\text{ran}(f_x) = M[x] = M[G_x]$. We now consider C to be a set of constant symbols, and corresponding to a random real x , f_x to be an interpretation of them into $M[x]$. So if we consider the language $\{\in\} \cup C$, then we have the following theorem:

Theorem 7.3.10. *If ϕ is a sentence of $\{\in\} \cup C$, not including \hat{x} , then $\exists [B] \in P$ corresponding to ϕ , such that $M[x] \models \phi \leftrightarrow x \in B^\sharp$. Here x is a random real.*

Proof. Clearly since ϕ doesn't involve \hat{x} , $M[x] \models \phi \leftrightarrow M[G_x] \models \phi$. Now from the previous theorem, $\exists b_0$ such that $M[G_x] \models \phi \leftrightarrow b_0 \in G_x$. Now $b_0 = [B]$ say. Then $b_0 \in G_x \leftrightarrow [B] \in G_x \leftrightarrow x \in B^\sharp$. \square

7.4 Building the Solovay's model

Definition 7.4.1. A subset U of \mathbb{R} in $M[G]$ is said to be *M R definable* if there is a formula $\phi(v_1, v_2, v_3), x \in M$ and a real $t \in M[G]$ such that $M[G] \models \forall y(\phi(x, t, y) \leftrightarrow y = U)$.

Theorem 7.4.2. Every *M R definable* subset of \mathbb{R} is Lebesgue measurable in $M[G]$.

Proof. Let $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be *M R definable*. Let $\phi(v_1, v_2, v_3)$ be a formula, $x \in M$ and a real $t \in M[G]$ such that $M[G] \models \forall y(\phi(x, t, y) \leftrightarrow y = U)$. Now we can find a formula $\phi_1(v_1, v_2, v_3)$ such that $M[G] \models \forall z(\phi_1(x, t, z) \leftrightarrow z \in U)$. Let $M_1 = M[t]$. Then we can find a formula $\phi_2(v_1, v_2)$ such that $M[G] \models \forall y(\phi_2((x, t), y) \rightarrow y \in U)$. Now for any real y of $M[G]$, $M[G] = M_1[y][G']$, where G' is a $M_1[y]$ generic ideal of P . Now $M_1[y][G'] \models \phi_2((x, t), y) \rightarrow y \in U$. And $M_1[y][G'] \models \phi_2((x, t), y) \leftrightarrow M_1[y] \models 0 \Vdash \phi_2((x, t), y)$. One can refer to [8] for the proofs of the above standard facts. Let $\phi_3 = 0 \Vdash \phi_2((x, t), y)$. Then \exists a Borel set $B \in M$, such that if y is a random real, $M_1[y] \models \phi_3 \iff y \in B^\sharp$. So for any random real y , $y \in U \leftrightarrow y \in B^\sharp \implies U \Delta B^\sharp \subseteq \{t \mid t \text{ is not a random real}\}$. But in $M[G]$, $U \Delta B^\sharp$ is a measure zero set $\implies U$ is Lebesgue measurable in $M[G]$. \square

Definition 7.4.3. 1. $x \in M[G]$ is said to be *definable from a sequence of ordinals (DFS O)* if there is a formula $\phi(v, y)$ and a function $f \in M[G]$ from ω to ON (ordinals) such that $M[G] \models \forall y(\phi(f, y) \rightarrow y = x)$.

2. $x \in M[G]$ is said to be *heriditarily definable from a sequence of ordinals(HDFS O)* if $\forall y \in T(x)$ (transitive closure), y is *HDFS O*.

Theorem 7.4.4 (Myhill, Scott). *There is a single formula $\phi(v, y)$ such that $x \in M[G]$ is *HDFS O* if and only if $\exists f \in M[G]$ and $f : \omega \rightarrow ON$ such that $M[G] \models \phi(f, x)$.*

Definition 7.4.5. $N = \{x \in M[G] \mid x \text{ is } HDFS O\}$.

Theorem 7.4.6. N is transitive.

Theorem 7.4.7. N is a model of *ZF*.

Proof. Extensionality holds in N , because it is transitive. Foundation holds in all classes. The rest of the axioms define new sets from existing ones. Hence, they will hold in N . [∴ if we define x from f and y from x , we can define y from f]. \square

Let us now state the axiom of dependent choice(DC):

$$\forall X \forall R ((R \subseteq X \times X \wedge \forall x (x \in X \rightarrow \exists y (x, y) \in R)) \rightarrow \exists h (h : \omega \rightarrow X \wedge \forall n \in \omega (h(n), h(n+1)) \in R))$$

Lemma 7.4.8. *If $h : \omega \rightarrow N$ is a function, then $h \in N$.*

Proof. Let for $x \in N$, $\gamma(x)$ be the least ordinal λ such that $\exists f \in M[G], f : \omega \rightarrow \lambda$ and $M[G] \models \phi(f, x)$ for the formula ϕ as in Theorem 7.4.4. Let $\gamma = \sup\{\gamma(h(n)) | n \in \omega\}$. We choose a well ordering $<$ of the collection of functions from ω to γ in $M[G]$. Let f_n be the $<$ -least function such that $M[G] \models \phi(f_n, h(n))$. So $F = \{f_n | n \in \omega\}$ defines h . Now if we let $g : \omega \rightarrow \gamma$ be such that $g(2^m 3^n) = f_m(n), \forall m, n \in \omega$ and 0 elsewhere, then g defines F . So g defines $h \implies h \in N$. \square

Theorem 7.4.9. *DC holds in N .*

Proof. Let X, R be as in statement of DC. Since AC holds in $M[G]$, we can get a $h : \omega \rightarrow X$ as above in the statement of DC, such that $h \in M[G]$. But $X \subseteq N$. So $h : \omega \rightarrow N$, and using the previous lemma, $h \in N$. \square

Theorem 7.4.10. *$N \models$ Every set of reals is Lebesgue measurable.*

Proof. Clearly if f is a function from ω to ON in $M[G]$, f is M R definable. So if $U \in N$ is a subset of \mathbb{R} , then it is definable from such an f . So U is M R definable. Hence \exists Borel sets B and B' such that $U \Delta B \subseteq B'$ and B' is of measure 0.

Now there are the Borel codes of B and B' say f_1 and f_2 which define them. Then $B, B' \in N$ and preservation of Lebesgue measure gives that $U \Delta B$ is of measure 0 in N too. Hence, U is Lebesgue measurable in N . \square

Part 2

Chapter 8

Model theory for metric structures

8.1 Metric structures

This section is devoted to the concept of metric structures. We will first introduce the notion of metric structures along with some examples where we will also see how structures of first-order logic can be realized as metric structures.

Definition 8.1.1 (Metric Structure). *A metric structure \mathcal{M} consists of a set I along with the following:*

- $\{M_i = (M'_i, d_i) \mid i \in I, M_i \text{ is a complete metric space of finite diameter}\}$,
- *Relations: For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x = (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n) \in I^n$, a set $R_x = \{f : M_{i_1} \times M_{i_2} \times M_{i_n} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f \text{ is a uniformly continuous function on a bounded subset of } \mathbb{R}\}$*
- *Functions: For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x = (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n) \in I^n$, a set $F_x = \{f : M_{i_1} \times M_{i_2} \times M_{i_{n-1}} \rightarrow M_{i_n} \mid f \text{ is a uniformly continuous function.}\}$*
- *Constants: For each $i \in I$, a subset C_i of M_i .*

One may write down a metric structure as:

$$\mathcal{M} = ((M_i)_{i \in I}, (R_x)_{x \in \bar{I}}, (F_x)_{x \in \bar{I}}, (C_i)_{i \in I})$$

where $\bar{I} = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} I^n$.

In the subsequent chapters, we will see the use of single-sorted metric structures i.e. metric structures \mathcal{M} where I is a singleton. However, multi-sorted metric structures occur

extensively in various areas of mathematics. We will witness some of these instances in the following examples:

1. A complete, bounded metric space (M, d) with no additional structures. (we note that the collections mentioned in Definition 8.1.1 may be empty.)
2. The closed unit ball $B(0,1)$ of a Banach space X over \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C} : Here we take $I = \{0\}$ (any singleton will do) ; $C_0 = \{\mathbf{0}_X\}$; $R_0 = \{\|\cdot\|_X : \|\cdot\|_X \text{ is the norm}\}$; $F_{(0,0,0)} = \{f_{ab} : M_0^2 \rightarrow M_0 | a, b \in \mathbb{R}(\mathbb{C}), |a| + |b| \leq 1, f_{ab}(x, y) = ax + by\}$, where $M_0 = B(0, 1)$. The other sets mentioned in definition 8.1.1 are empty. In fact, for simplicity we only write down the sets which are non-empty and the other collections are assumed to be empty.
3. The Banach space X over \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C} : X can be viewed as a many-sorted structure, with a sort for each closed ball of positive integer radius centered at $\mathbf{0}_X$ i.e. $I = \mathbb{N}$, $M_n = B(0, n)$ (the metric being the restriction),
 $C_1 = \{\mathbf{0}_X\}$, $F_{(1,1,1)} = \{f_{ab} : M_1^2 \rightarrow M_1 | a, b \in \mathbb{R}(\mathbb{C}), |a| + |b| \leq 1, f_{ab}(x, y) = ax + by\}$, where $M_1 = B(0, 1)$, $R_n = \{\|\cdot\|_X : \|\cdot\|_X \text{ is the norm}\}$,
 $F_{(m,n)} = \{f_a : M_m \rightarrow M_n | a \in \mathbb{R}(\mathbb{C}), |a| \leq \frac{n}{m}, f_a(x) = ax\}$, $\forall m, m', n \in I$ and $m < m'$.
4. Hilbert space over \mathbb{R} : We have the same structure as in the Banach space with some additions due to the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$. For each $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$R_{m,n} = \{\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{mn} : B(0, m) \times B(0, n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} | \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{mn} \text{ is the restriction of the inner product}\}.$$

Clearly, range of $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{mn}$ is a closed, bounded subset of \mathbb{R} (using Cauchy-Schwarz inequality and completeness property of the closed balls).

5. Banach Algebras: Here also, we have the same structure as in the Banach space along with some additions for 'capturing' the notion of multiplication (often denoted by ' \cdot '). If the algebra has a multiplicative identity, we add it as a constant in C_1 . We add to each $F_{(1,1,1)}$, the following function, $g : B(0, 1) \times B(0, 1) \rightarrow B(0, 1)$ defined as $g(x, y) = x \cdot y$. Now, because of the presence of the other functions defined in the Banach space structure, one can use g to 'multiply' any two elements of the Banach algebra which can be carried out as follows: Let x, y be any

two elements of the Banach Algebra. We see that $x \cdot y = f_{mn}(g(f_{\frac{1}{n}}(x), f_{\frac{1}{m}}(y)))$, where $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\|x\| < n, \|y\| < m$ and $f_{mn} \in F_{(1, mn)}, f_{\frac{1}{n}} \in F_{(n, 1)}, f_{\frac{1}{m}} \in F_{(m, 1)}$.

6. C^* Algebras: We have the same structure as in the Banach algebra and for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, to $F_{(n, n)}$, we add the restriction of the $*$ operation to $B(0, n)$ (which can be done because of the C^* identity).
7. **An observation:** Since the above examples deal with structures having an underlying vector space, we naturally think whether it is possible to realize any vector space V over a field F as a metric structure. This is an easy observation since any set can be realised as a metric space by endowing it with the discrete metric d . So, (V, d) is a metric space which is in fact, complete and bounded. Now, we take a singleton set $I = \{0\}$ and define $M_0 = V, F_0 = \{f_{ab} : V^2 \rightarrow V \mid a, b \in F, f_{ab}(x, y) = ax + by\}$ and $C_0 = \{0\}$.
8. Now, one can use First-Order logic to capture the notion of vector spaces. This hints to the fact that any L -structure S where L is a language in first-order logic can be realized as a metric structure by endowing it with the discrete metric. This can be achieved by taking $I = \{0\}$ (any singleton), $M_0 = (S, d)$, d is the discrete metric. Clearly, (S, d) is complete and bounded. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we take $F_{(0, 0, \dots, (n\text{-times}), \dots, 0)}$ to be the collection of the interpretations in S of the n -ary function symbols in L . And we define $R_{(0, 0, \dots, (n\text{-times}), \dots, 0)} = \{f_R : S^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\} \mid R \text{ is an interpretation of a relation symbol in } L, f_R((s_1, \dots, s_n)) = 0 \text{ if } (s_1, \dots, s_n) \in R \text{ and } f_R((s_1, \dots, s_n)) = 1 \text{ otherwise}\}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$. Clearly, all the functions in the above collections are uniform continuous, because d is discrete. And we let C_0 be the set of all constants in S .

Definition 8.1.2 (Modulus of Uniform Continuity). *Let $(M, d), (M', d')$ be metric spaces. Let $s : M \rightarrow M'$ be a function. $\delta_s : (0, 1] \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is a modulus of uniform continuity for s if for all $\epsilon \in (0, 1]$ and $x, y \in M, d(x, y) < \delta_s(\epsilon) \implies d'(s(x), s(y)) < \epsilon$.*

When we will be dealing with metric structures in the coming chapters, we will without loss of generality, assume the diameter of each metric space is 1 and the range of all the relations to be $[0, 1]$. We will see in Section 8.2 that the above assumption will help us to give a much simple logical framework to the notion of metric structures.

8.2 Continuous logic

In the previous section, we saw that metric structures occur in various areas of mathematics. In order to formalize metric structures and develop various model-theoretic results associated to metric structures, continuous logic in the framework of metric structures was developed. Continuous logic proved to be very useful because various well-known theorems of first-order logic, like completeness theorem, compactness theorem, downward Löwenheim-Skolem theorem, etc. have modified counterparts in continuous logic. In this section, we shall briefly discuss continuous logic. For further details, one might refer to [19] and [20].

Definition 8.2.1 (Continuous signature). *The signature (language) L of continuous logic is a quadruple $L = (\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{F}, \eta, \mathcal{G})$ such that*

- \mathcal{R} contains a distinguished binary predicate d .
- $\mathcal{R} \cap \mathcal{F} = \emptyset$, where \emptyset denotes empty set.
- $\eta : \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$.
- $\mathcal{G} = \{\delta_s : (0, 1] \rightarrow (0, 1] : s \in \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{F}\}$.

\mathcal{R} is the set of **relation symbols**, \mathcal{F} is the set of **function symbols**, and $(\mathcal{R} \setminus \{d\} \cup \mathcal{F})$ is the set of **non-logical symbols** of L . The arity of a relation or function symbol is given by $\eta(s)$. \mathcal{G} consists of functions associated to each predicate and function symbol and these functions will be interpreted as the moduli of uniform continuity of the interpretations of the symbols they are associated to in the structures. The **cardinality of the signature** L , denoted by $|L|$, is the cardinality of the set of non-logical symbols of L .

The connectives for continuous logic are all continuous functions $u : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1], \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$. We observe that we are considering ‘too many’ connectives. However, one can take a few connectives and ‘approximate’ formulas in continuous logic. For more details regarding this fact, one can refer to [19]. Variables are same as in classical logic and continuous logic has two quantifiers: *sup*, *inf*. As the names suggest, these quantifiers are interpreted as the usual supremum and infimum in the structures. The last sentence will become clear as we proceed.

Definition 8.2.2 (Terms, formulas, Sentences). *For an signature L , terms and formulas in continuous logic are defined inductively as follows:*

- *Variables and 0-ary function symbols are L -terms. If $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is an n -ary function symbol and $t_1, t_2 \dots t_n$ are L -terms, then $f(t_1, t_2 \dots t_n)$ is an L -term.*
- *Atomic L -formulas are expressions of the form $P(t_1, t_2 \dots t_n)$ where $P \in \mathcal{R}$ is an n -ary predicate symbol and $t_1, t_2 \dots t_n$ are L terms.*
- *Formulas are built using connectives and quantifiers on Atomic formulas.*
 - *Atomic formulas are formulas.*
 - *If $\phi_1, \phi_2 \dots \phi_n$ are formulas and $u : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a connective , then $u(\phi_1, \phi_2 \dots \phi_n)$ is a formula.*
 - *If $\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots x_n)$ is a formula where $x_1, x_2, \dots x_n$ are free variables, then $\sup_{x_1} \phi(x_1, x_2, \dots x_n)$ and $\inf_{x_1} \phi(x_1, x_2, \dots x_n)$ are formulas.*
- *A formula with no occurrences of free variables is called a sentence.*

Let L be a continuous signature. Now the concept which bridges the gap between continuous logic and metric structures is defined as follows:

Here we will mainly deal with single sorted metric structures i.e. the set I in Definition 8.1.1 is a singleton. So we denote the relations and functions by the sets R, F respectively.

Definition 8.2.3 (L-Structure). *A metric structure M is an L -structure if there exists a injective function $\rho : \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{F} \rightarrow R \cup F$ such that*

- *For each $f \in \mathcal{F}$, ρ assigns a $\eta(f)$ -function $f^M : M^{\eta(f)} \rightarrow M$ of F .*
- *For each $P \in \mathcal{R}$, ρ assigns a $\eta(P)$ -predicate $P^M : M^{\eta(P)} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ of P .*

These assignments are done in such a way that for each $g \in \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{F}$, δ_g is a modulus of uniform continuity for $\rho(g)$.

One can say that ρ gives meanings to the symbols in the formal language.

Definition 8.2.4 (Theory). *A theory T consists of a signature L along with a collection of sentences in L called the axioms of T .*

Definition 8.2.5 (Model). *An L -structure is said to be model M of theory T if for every axiom ϕ , the interpretation of ϕ in M , i.e. $\phi^M = 0$.*

8.3 Continuous model theory

We will do a brief overview of continuous model theory and state the results that will be needed in the subsequent sections. For a detailed exposition of continuous model theory, one might refer to [19].

Definition 8.3.1 (Embeddings and isomorphisms). *Let L be a signature for metric structures and suppose M and N are L -structures. An embedding from M into N is a metric space isometry $T : (M, d_M) \rightarrow (N, d_N)$ that commutes with the interpretations of the function and predicate symbols of L in the following sense:*

- Whenever f is an n -ary function symbol of L and $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in M$, we have

$$f^N(T(a_1), T(a_2), \dots, T(a_n)) = T(f^M(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n));$$

- Whenever c is a constant symbol c of L , we have $c^N = T(c^M)$; and whenever P is an n -ary predicate symbol of L and $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in M$, we have

$$P^N(T(a_1), T(a_2), \dots, T(a_n)) = P^M(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n).$$

An isomorphism is a surjective embedding.

Definition 8.3.2. *Suppose that M and N are L -structures.*

- M and N are elementarily equivalent if $\sigma^M = \sigma^N, \forall L$ -sentences σ .
- If $M \subseteq N$ we say that M is an elementary substructure of N , and write $M \subseteq' N$, if whenever $\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is an L -formula and $a_1 \dots a_n$ are elements of M , we have $\phi^M(a_1 \dots a_n) = \phi^N(a_1 \dots a_n)$. In this case, we also say that N is an elementary extension of M .
- A function F from a subset of M into N is an elementary map from M into N if whenever $\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is an L -formula and $a_1 \dots a_n$ are elements of the domain of F , we have $\phi^M(a_1 \dots a_n) = \phi^N(F(a_1) \dots F(a_n))$.
- An elementary embedding of M into N is an elementary map from all of M into N .

Definition 8.3.3. *Suppose C is a class of L -structures. We say that C is axiomatizable if there exists a set T of L -sentences such that $M \models T \iff M \in C$.*

We will now see some ways of building new models out of existing models.

An often used construction in model theory is the direct limit of a directed system of models. A directed set is a partially ordered set $(D, <)$ such that for every $i, j \in D$ there is a $k \in D$ such that $i \leq k$ and $j \leq k$. A **directed system of models** is a collection of models $\{M_i\}_{i \in D}$ together with elementary embeddings $e_{i,j} : M_i \rightarrow M_j$ such that $e_{i,k} = e_{j,k} \circ e_{i,j}, \forall i < j < k$.

For simplicity, one can think of a particular case of substructures i.e. we have $\{M_i\}_{i \in D}$ such that $\forall i, j \in D, i < j \implies M_i \subseteq M_j$. Let $M = \bigcup_{i \in D} M_i; P^M = \bigcup_{i \in D} P^{M_i}$, etc. Now, we state the following lemma:

Lemma 8.3.4. *If $\{M_i, e_{i,j}\}_{i \in D}$ is a directed system of models, then there exists a model M , unique upto isomorphism, and elementary embeddings $e_i : M_i \rightarrow M$ such that $M = \bigcup_{i \in D} e_i(M_i)$ and $e_i = e_j \circ e_{i,j}, \forall i < j$.*

This model M is called the **direct limit** of $\{M_i, e_{i,j}\}_{i \in D}$ and is often denoted by $\lim_{\rightarrow i} M_i$.

Definition 8.3.5 (Filter and ultrafilter). *A filter on a nonempty set S is a collection F of subsets of S such that*

- $S \in F$ and $\emptyset \notin F$,
- $X, Y \in F \implies X \cap Y \in F$,
- $X, Y \subseteq S, X \in F, X \subseteq Y \implies Y \in F$.

A filter U on a set S is an ultrafilter if for every $X \subseteq S$, either $X \in U$ or $S \setminus X \in U$.

Ultrafilter limits: Let X be a topological space and let $\{x_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a family of elements of X . If D is an ultrafilter on I and $x \in X$, we write $\lim_{i, D} x_i = x$ and say that x is a *D-limit* of $\{x_i\}_{i \in I}$ if for every neighborhood U of x , the set $\{i \in I | x_i \in U\}$ is in the ultrafilter D . Using general topology one can show that X is a compact, Hausdorff space if and only if for every family $\{x_i\}_{i \in I}$ in X and every ultrafilter D on I the *D-limit* of $\{x_i\}_{i \in I}$ exists and is unique.

Let $(M_i, d_i) | i \in I$ be a family of bounded metric spaces, all having diameter $\leq K$. Let D be an ultrafilter on I . We define a function d on the Cartesian product $M' = \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ by $d'(x, y) = \lim_{i, D} d_i(x_i, y_i)$, where $x = \{x_i\}_{i \in I}, y = \{y_i\}_{i \in I}$. This *D-limit* exists and is unique because it is taken in $[0, K]$. One can also check that (M', d') is a pseudometric

space. So, we take the natural quotient to build a metric space from this pseudometric space and call this space (M, d) .

Definition 8.3.6 (Utraproduct and ultrapower). *The space M (denoted as $(\prod_{i \in I} M_i)_D$) with the induced metric d is called the D -ultraproduct of $((M_i, d_i) | i \in I)$.*

If $\forall i \in I, (M_i, d_i) = (N, \bar{d})$, we say that $(\prod_{i \in I} M_i)_D$ is the D -ultrapower of N and denote it by $(N)_D$.

One of the reasons for considering the modulus of uniform continuity and boundedness in continuous logic is due to the way ultraproducts are constructed. This is done so that if the ultraproduct is constructed using L-structures, then it is an L-structure as well. Ultraproducts have many interesting properties, two of them are stated as follows:

We shall need these properties in the following chapters.

Theorem 8.3.7. *Let M be an L-structure and $(M)_D$ is an ultrapower of M . Then the diagonal embedding $T : M \rightarrow (M)_D$ defined as $T(x) = (x)_D$ is an elementary embedding.*

Theorem 8.3.8. *M and N are elementarily equivalent if and only if M admits an elementary embedding into an ultrapower of N .*

Chapter 9

Formalization of p.m.p. actions and free actions

Ergodic theory mostly deals with study of group actions on measure spaces. A central theme of the study of ergodic theory is the notion of probability measure preserving actions, commonly known as *p.m.p.* actions. We recall the definition of *p.m.p.* actions.

Definition 9.0.9 (*p.m.p. Action*). *Let (P, σ, μ) be a probability space and Γ be a countable group. An action $\Gamma \curvearrowright (P, \sigma, \mu)$ is said to be a probability-measure preserving action if Γ acts by measure-preserving transformations (For each $g \in \Gamma$ $g: P \rightarrow P$ is a bijection such that g and g^{-1} are measurable and $\mu(gA) = \mu(A)$ for all $A \in \sigma$).*

Using continuous logic, the theory PMP_{Γ} (which has been explained in [7]) has been used to formalize the notion of *p.m.p.* actions. This chapter explores this formalization and discusses the student's intuition behind a theorem which plays a significant role for developing PMP_{Γ} . The references studied for this chapter are [20], [5], [7] and [17].

9.1 Measure algebra of a measure space

We first introduce the notion of Boolean rings.

Definition 9.1.1 (Boolean Rings). *A unital ring R with every element idempotent ($\forall a \in R, a^2 = a$) is said to be a Boolean ring.*

An example of a Boolean ring is the ring $(P(X), \Delta, \cap)$, where $P(X)$ is the power set of a set X . So a Boolean ring is a set R having a distinguished elements $0, 1$ along with two binary operations '+' and '.' satisfying the following:

- Ring axioms:
 - R is abelian group under ‘+’.
 - R is monoid under ‘.’.
 - In R , ‘.’ distributes with respect to ‘+’.
- $\forall x(x.x = x)$

Now, we can define the following operations in R using ‘+’ and ‘.’:

- $\wedge : R \times R \rightarrow R$ defined as $\wedge(x, y) = x.y, \forall x, y \in R$.
- $\vee : R \times R \rightarrow R$ defined as $\vee(x, y) = x + y + x.y \forall x, y \in R$.
- $.^c : R \rightarrow R$ defined as $x^c = 1 + x$.

Now $(R, \vee, \wedge, .^c, 0, 1)$ has a special structure defined as follows:

Definition 9.1.2 (Boolean algebra). *A Boolean algebra is a set that includes two distinguished constants 0 and 1 and on which there are defined two binary operations \wedge and \vee , a unary operation $.^c$ which satisfy the following rules:*

1. $\forall x(x \vee x = x)$
2. $\forall x(x \wedge x = x)$
3. *Commutativity:* $\forall x \forall y(x \vee y = y \vee x)$
4. *Commutativity:* $\forall x \forall y(x \wedge y = y \wedge x)$
5. *Absorption:* $\forall x \forall y((x \wedge y) \vee y = y)$
6. *Absorption:* $\forall x \forall y((x \vee y) \wedge y = y)$
7. *Associativity:* $\forall x \forall y \forall z((x \vee y) \vee z = x \vee (y \vee z))$
8. *Associativity:* $\forall x \forall y \forall z((x \wedge y) \wedge z = x \wedge (y \wedge z))$
9. *Distributivity:* $\forall x \forall y \forall z(x \vee (y \wedge z) = (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z))$
10. *Distributivity:* $\forall x \forall y \forall z(x \wedge (y \vee z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z))$
11. *Complements:* $\forall x(x \vee x^c = 1)$

12. Complements: $\forall x(x \wedge x^c = 0)$

13. $0 \neq 1$

An example of a Boolean algebra is the power set of a non-empty set S along with $\cup := \vee; \cap := \wedge; 0 := \phi; 1 := S; \cdot^c$ is usual complementation.

A Boolean algebra becomes partially ordered if we define $x \leq y$ to be $x \wedge y = x$. Let $x \setminus y := x \wedge y^c$.

Boolean algebras can be represented as Boolean rings via the following:

- $a + b := a \Delta b$
- $a \cdot b := a \wedge b$

So we will use Boolean algebras or Boolean rings accordingly depending on the context.

Definition 9.1.3 (Boolean σ -algebra). *A Boolean algebra B is said to be a Boolean σ -algebra if for each sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \omega}$ in B there is a least element $x \in B$ such that $x_n \leq x, \forall n \in \omega$. We call x to be $\sup_n x_n$.*

Definition 9.1.4 (Measure algebra). *A measure algebra is a pair (A, ν) where A is a Boolean σ -algebra and $\nu : A \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ is a function such that*

1. $\nu(0) = 0$
2. If $\{a_n\}_{n \in \omega}$ is a disjoint sequence in A ($a_i \wedge a_j = 0, i \neq j$) then $\nu(\sup_n a_n) = \sum_{n \in \omega} \nu(a_n)$
3. $a=0 \iff \nu(a) = 0$.

Using a measure space (P, σ, μ) , one can construct a measure algebra as well as a complete metric space as follows:

We define a relation $\sim \subseteq \sigma \times \sigma$ as $A \sim B \iff \mu(A \Delta B) = 0$.

- \sim is an equivalence relation.

Proof. \sim is clearly reflective and symmetric. For transitivity, let $A, B, C \in \sigma$ such that $A \sim B$ and $B \sim C$. We have $0 = \mu(A \Delta B) = \mu(A \setminus B) + \mu(B \setminus A) \implies \mu(A \setminus B) = \mu(B \setminus A) = 0$. Similarly, $\mu(B \setminus C) = \mu(C \setminus B) = 0$. Since, $A \setminus C \subseteq (A \setminus B) \cup (B \setminus C)$ and $C \setminus A \subseteq (C \setminus B) \cup (B \setminus A)$, $\mu(A \Delta C) = \mu(A \setminus C) + \mu(C \setminus A) \leq \mu(A \setminus B) + \mu(B \setminus C) + \mu(C \setminus B) + \mu(B \setminus A) = 0 \implies A \sim C$.

We call the collection of equivalence classes to be M . $\forall [A], [B] \in M, [A]^c := [A^c]; [A] \vee [B] := [A \cup B]; [A] \wedge [B] := [A \cap B]$. One can check that these are well defined. Also, for $\{[A_n]\}_{n \in \omega}$, a sequence in $M, \vee_{n \in \omega} [A_n] := [\cup_{n \in \omega} A_n]; \wedge_{n \in \omega} [A_n] := [\cap_{n \in \omega} A_n]$. These are also well defined.

- $B = (M, [\phi], [P], \wedge, \vee, \neg)$ is a Boolean σ algebra.

Proof. By the above definitions, B is clearly a Boolean Algebra. Now let $\{[A_i]\}_{i \in \omega}$ be a sequence in B . Let $A = \vee_{i \in \omega} [A_i]. \forall i \in \omega, [A_i] \cap A = [A_i] \wedge (\cup_{n \in \omega} [A_n]) = [\vee_{n \in \omega} (A_i \cap A_n)] = [A_i] \implies [A_i] \leq A \implies A$ is an upper bound. Let $C = [C']$ be another upper bound of the sequence. Then $A \wedge C = [\vee_{n \in \omega} A_n] \wedge [C'] = [\cup_{n \in \omega} (A_n \cap C')] = \vee_{n \in \omega} ([A_n] \wedge C) = \vee_{n \in \omega} [A_n] = A \implies A$ is the least upper bound. So B is a Boolean σ algebra.

We define a map $\mu' : M \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ as $\mu'([A]) = \mu(A)$. One can check that μ' is well defined, strictly positive and countably additive and hence, (M, μ') is a **measure algebra**.

We define $d : M \times M \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ as $d([A], [B]) = \mu(A \Delta B)$.

- d is a metric.

Proof. Non-negativity, coincidence and symmetry follows from the definition. For the triangle inequality, $d([A], [B]) + d([B], [C]) = \mu(A \Delta B) + \mu(B \Delta C) = \mu(A \setminus B) + \mu(B \setminus A) + \mu(B \setminus C) + \mu(C \setminus B) \geq \mu(A \setminus C) + \mu(C \setminus A) [\because A \setminus C \subseteq (A \setminus B) \cup (B \setminus C)] = \mu(A \Delta C)$, thus proving that d is a metric.

- (M, d) is a complete metric space.

We shall briefly outline the proof here. For further details, one can refer to [20] (Proposition 4.7). We start by choosing a Cauchy sequence $\{a_n\}_{n \in \omega}$ in M and observe that there is a non-decreasing sequence $\{N_k \in \omega\}_{k \in \omega}$ such that for all $k \in \omega, \exists$ minimal N_k such that $\forall m, n \geq N_k, d(a_m, a_n) < 2^{-k}. \forall k, c_k := a_{N_k}$. Then $\sum_{k \in \omega} d(c_k, c_{k+1}) \leq \sum_{k \in \omega} 2^{-k} < \infty$. Let $p_0 := \vee_{n \in \omega} \wedge_{m \geq n} c_m, p_1 := \wedge_{n \in \omega} \vee_{m \geq n} c_m$. Since B is σ -complete, $p_0, p_1 \in B$. Also, using countable additivity of μ and some limiting arguments, one can show that $p_0 = p_1$. In fact, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} c_n = p_0$, thus showing that d is complete.

9.2 The Stone representation theorem of a measure algebra

Definition 9.2.1 (Stone space). *Given a Boolean ring B , the Stone space of B is the set Z of nonzero ring homomorphisms from B to \mathbb{Z}_2 .*

We have seen that for a set S , its power set $P(S)$ has a Boolean algebra structure $(P(S), \cup, \cap, \phi, Z, \cdot)$. So we can talk about the Boolean ring $(P(Z), \Delta, \cap)$. In fact, the Stone representation theorem as follows establishes a connection between a Boolean ring and its corresponding Stone space via the power set ring described above.

Theorem 9.2.2. *The map $\phi : (B, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (P(Z), \Delta, \cap)$ defined as $a \rightarrow a' = \{f \in Z \mid f(a) = 1\}$ is an injective ring homomorphism.*

Definition 9.2.3 (Boolean Algebra homomorphism). *Given Boolean Algebras A and B , a function $\pi : A \rightarrow B$ is a Boolean homomorphism if $\pi(A \Delta B) = \pi(a) \Delta \pi(b)$ and $\pi(a \wedge b) = \pi(a) \wedge \pi(b)$, $\forall a, b \in A$ and $\pi(1_A) = \pi(1_B)$.*

Definition 9.2.4 (σ -ideal of σ -algebra). *Given a σ -algebra S of subsets of a set X , $I \subseteq S$ is said to be a σ -ideal if it contains the empty set; for all $a \in I, b \in S$ if $b \subseteq a$ then $b \in I$ and I is closed under countable unions.*

The following theorem allows us to express the Stone space of the underlying Boolean σ -algebra of a measure algebra as a measure space and this measure space has a special isomorphism property which plays an important role in formalization of *p.m.p.* actions as we shall see later:

Theorem 9.2.5 (Stone representation theorem of a measure algebra). *Let (F, ν) be a measure algebra. Then the stone space of the underlying Boolean σ -algebra becomes a measure space whose measure algebra is isomorphic, as a measure algebra, to (F, ν) .*

We shall provide an outline of the proof along with an intuition we tried to think of behind the construction of the proof. For explicit details of the proof, one can refer to [20]. Let us call the underlying Boolean σ -algebra to be $(A, 0, 1, \wedge, \vee, \neg)$. Now, for establishing a link between a Boolean Algebra and its corresponding Stone space, we have the Stone representation theorem. So, we define $\epsilon = \{a' \subseteq Z \mid a \in F\}$. And we observe that ϵ forms a basis of a topology of Z . From the Stone representation theorem, we already have that

$A \cong_\phi \epsilon$ as Boolean algebras. But what happens to the image of supremum of a sequence in A under ϕ ? So, we take a sequence $\{a_n\}_{n \in \omega}$ in A and let $a = \sup_n a_n \implies a' = \overline{\bigcup_{n \in \omega} a'_n}$ (in the topology given by ϵ). We collect the ‘extra’ elements in a set as follows: Let $C := a' \setminus \bigcup_{n \in \omega} a'_n$. One observes that C is nowhere dense. We need to ‘get rid’ of this C somehow. And a common way of doing so is by ‘quotienting’. We know that when a Boolean σ -algebra is quotiented by a σ -ideal, then we get a Boolean σ -algebra. So, we consider the σ -ideal M consisting of all nowhere dense sets. Since, we already have a map ϕ from the Stone representation theorem, we will try to develop a map similar to ϕ . We will look for a “small enough” σ -algebra on Z (to ensure surjectivity of the new map) containing ϵ such that M is a σ -ideal in it, so that C gets identified to $\mathbf{0}$ in the quotient Boolean σ -algebra and it becomes isomorphic to A . So we define $S = \{a' \Delta B \mid a' \in \epsilon, B \in M\}$ and we see that S is indeed a σ -algebra and M is a σ -ideal in it. Now we define the relation $\sim \subseteq S \times S$ as $P \sim Q \iff P = Q \Delta B$, for some $B \in M$. We have that S/M is a Boolean σ -algebra and the map $f : A \rightarrow S/M; f(a) = [a']$ is a Boolean σ -algebra isomorphism. For constructing the measure space, we already have that S is a σ -algebra. So, we define $\nu' : S \rightarrow [0, \infty]; \nu'(E) = \nu(f^{-1}(E))$ and see that (Z, S, ν') is a measure space with measure algebra $(S/M, \mu)$ where $\mu([E]) := \nu'(E)$. Finally, we can show that $(S/M, \mu) \cong (F, \nu)$ as measure algebras.

9.3 The theory PMP_Γ

Let Γ be a countable, discrete group. We define a continuous signature/language \mathbf{L} as follows:

- $R = \{d, \mu\}; F = \Gamma \cup \{\vee, \wedge, \neg, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}\}$
- $\eta = \{(d, 2), (\mu, 1), (\mathbf{0}, 0), (\mathbf{1}, 0), (\wedge, 2), (\vee, 2), (\neg, 1)\} \cup \{(g, 1) \mid g \in \Gamma\}$
- $G = \{\Delta_s : (0, 1] \rightarrow (0, 1] \mid s \in R \cup F; \Delta_d(\epsilon) = \Delta_\vee(\epsilon) = \Delta_\wedge(\epsilon) = \frac{\epsilon}{2}; \Delta_\neg(\epsilon) = \Delta_\mu(\epsilon) = \Delta_g(\epsilon) = \epsilon; \Delta_{\mathbf{0}}(\epsilon) = \Delta_{\mathbf{1}}(\epsilon) = 1\}$

Note: G has been defined in such a way because it has been proven that for measure algebras of measure spaces, the above modulus of uniform continuities hold. Hence, by Stone representation theorem for measure algebras, they must hold for all measure algebras.

With the above signature, we define a theory PMP_Γ whose axioms are as follows:

- Boolean Algebra axioms:

1. $\sup_x d(x \vee x, x)$
2. $\sup_x d(x \wedge x, x)$
3. $\sup_x \sup_y d(x \vee y, y \vee x)$
4. $\sup_x \sup_y d(x \wedge y, y \wedge x)$
5. $\sup_x \sup_y d((x \wedge y) \vee y, y)$
6. $\sup_x \sup_y d((x \vee y) \wedge y, y)$
7. $\sup_x \sup_y \sup_z d((x \wedge y) \wedge z, x \wedge (y \wedge z))$
8. $\sup_x \sup_y \sup_z d((x \vee y) \vee z, x \vee (y \vee z))$
9. $\sup_x \sup_y \sup_z d((x \wedge y) \vee z, (x \vee z) \wedge (y \vee z))$
10. $\sup_x \sup_y \sup_z d((x \vee y) \wedge z, (x \wedge z) \vee (y \wedge z))$
11. $\sup_x d(x \vee (\neg x), \mathbf{1})$
12. $\sup_x d(x \wedge (\neg x), \mathbf{0})$

- Measure axioms:

1. $\mu(\mathbf{0})$
2. $\neg\mu(\mathbf{1})$
3. $\sup_x \sup_y (\mu(x \wedge y) \doteq \mu(x))$
4. $\sup_x \sup_y (\mu(x) \doteq \mu(x \vee y))$
5. $\sup_x \sup_y |(\mu(x) \doteq \mu(x \wedge y)) - (\mu(x \vee y) \doteq \mu(x))|$

- Connection between d and μ

1. $\sup_x \sup_y |d(x, y) - \mu(x \Delta y)|$

- *p.m.p.* axioms: Let $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n \in \Gamma$.

1. For each $g \in \Gamma$, g is an automorphism.
2. (schema) $A_{g_1.g_2\dots g_n=1_\Gamma} : \sup_a d(g_1.g_2\dots g_n(a), 1_\Gamma(a))$

Here $a \doteq b = a - b$ (if $a \geq b$); 0 (if $a < b$). Now we shall prove the following:

Theorem 9.3.1. $M \models PMP_\Gamma \iff M$ is a p.m.p. action of Γ .

Proof. (\Leftarrow): Let $\Gamma \curvearrowright (X, \Sigma, \mu)$ be a p.m.p. action on a probability space. Now $M = (A, 0, 1, \wedge, \vee, \neg, \mu')$ is the measure algebra of (X, Σ, μ) . Clearly, M satisfies all Boolean algebra and measure axioms. Also, we have seen before that (A, d) is a complete metric space. And $diam(A) = 1$ [$\because \mu(X) = 1$]. Now for each $g \in \Gamma, x (= [p]) \in A$, we define a map $(g, x) \rightarrow [g.p]$. This map is a surjective Boolean algebra homomorphism which follows from the definition of the symbols. And $d([g.p], [g.q]) = \mu(g.p \Delta g.q) = \mu(g.(p \Delta q))$ [\because p.m.p.] $= \mu(p \Delta q)$ [\because measure preserving] $= d([p], [q]) \implies$ the map defined above is an isometry. Hence, all the axioms of PMP_Γ are satisfied $\implies M \models PMP_\Gamma$.

(\implies): Let $M \models PMP_\Gamma. M = (A, 0, 1, \wedge, \vee, \neg, \mu)$. By the axioms, we have that M has a Boolean algebra structure and μ is finitely additive probability measure because $\mu(x \wedge y) + \mu(x \vee y) = \mu(x) + \mu(y)$. This happens because, from measure axiom 3. and 4. we have $\mu(x \wedge y) \leq \mu(x)$ and $\mu(x \vee y) \geq \mu(y)$ and axiom 5. gives us that $\mu(x) - \mu(x \wedge y) = \mu(x) \dot{-} \mu(x \wedge y) = \mu(x \vee y) \dot{-} \mu(y) = \mu(x \vee y) - \mu(y)$. From the axioms, we have $d(a, b) = \mu(a \Delta b)$. By Boolean algebra axioms 11.,6. we have that $1 \wedge x = (x^c \vee x) \wedge x = x \implies x \leq 1 \implies \mu(x) \leq \mu(1)$. In fact, using finite additivity of μ , one can show that μ is 1-Lipschitz as follows: $\mu(x) = \mu(x \setminus y) + \mu(x \wedge y)$ and $\mu(y) = \mu(y \setminus x) + \mu(y \wedge x) \implies |\mu(x) - \mu(y)| = |\mu(x \setminus y) + \mu(y \setminus x)|$ Also $0 \leq 2\mu(x \setminus y) \leq 2\mu(x \setminus y) + 2\mu(y \setminus x) \implies -(\mu(x \setminus y) + \mu(y \setminus x)) \leq \mu(x \setminus y) - \mu(y \setminus x) \leq \mu(x \setminus y) + \mu(y \setminus x) \implies |\mu(x) - \mu(y)| = |\mu(x \setminus y) - \mu(y \setminus x)| \leq \mu(x \setminus y) + \mu(y \setminus x) = \mu(x \Delta y) = d(x, y)$.

Now we will show that any increasing sequence in A is necessarily a Cauchy sequence. Let $\{x_n\}$ be an increasing sequence in A that is not Cauchy. Then $\exists \epsilon > 0$ such that $\forall N \in \mathbb{N}, \exists m, n > N$ such that $d(x_m, x_n) > \epsilon$. We choose $n_1 < n_2$ such that $d(x_{n_1}, x_{n_2}) > \epsilon$. Let $N_2 := n_2 + 1$, we again choose $N_1 < n_3 < n_4$ such that $d(x_{n_3}, x_{n_4}) > \epsilon$ and we keep repeating this. In general, let $N_k = n_{2k} + 1$ and we choose $N_k < n_{2k+2} < n_{2k+3}$ such that $d(x_{n_{2k+2}}, x_{n_{2k+3}}) > \epsilon$. For all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we let $y_k = x_{n_k}$ and observe that $\forall i \in \mathbb{N}, d(y_{2i+1}, y_{2i+2}) > \epsilon$. So we choose a natural number $K > \frac{1}{\epsilon}$. Now, before proceeding further we state the following result: "Let $x, y, z \in A. x \leq y \leq z \implies z \setminus x = (z \setminus y) \vee (y \setminus x)$ and $(z \setminus y) \wedge (y \setminus x) = 0$." Since $\{y_k\}$ is an increasing sequence, $\mu(y_1 \Delta y_{2K+1}) = \mu(y_1 \setminus y_{2K+1}) (= 0) + \mu(y_{2K+1} \setminus y_1) = \mu(y_{2K+1} \setminus y_{2K}) + \mu(y_{2K} \setminus y_1) = \mu(y_{2K+1} \setminus y_{2K}) + \mu(y_{2K} \setminus y_{2K-1}) + \mu(y_{2K-1} \setminus y_1) = \dots = \sum_{i=1}^{2K} \mu(y_{i+1} \setminus y_i) = \sum_{i=1}^{2K} \mu(y_{i+1} \Delta y_i)$ [$\because \mu(y_i \setminus y_{i+1}) = 0$] $= \sum_{i=1}^{2K} d(y_{i+1}, y_i) \geq \sum_{i=1}^{K-1} d(y_{2i+1}, y_{2i+2}) > K\epsilon > 1$, which is contradictory to μ being a finite 'probability' measure. So, $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Since (A, d) is a complete

metric space, for all increasing sequences $\{x_n\}$, $\exists x \in A$ such that $x_n \rightarrow x$.

Now we shall show that A is a Boolean σ -Algebra. Let $\{a_n\}$ be a sequence in A . Let $\forall n \geq 0, b_n = \bigvee_{k \leq n} a_k \implies \forall n, a_n \leq b_n, b_n \leq b_{n+1}$. Since $\{b_n\}$ is increasing, by our previous arguments, $\exists b \in A, b_n \rightarrow b$.

Claim: $b = \sup_n a_n$.

Proof of Claim: We first show that b is an upper bound. If not, i.e. $\exists n \in \omega$ such that $b < b_n \implies b \wedge b_n = b$ and $b \neq b_n \implies \epsilon := d(b, b_n) > 0$. Let $m \geq n, m \in \omega \implies b < b_n \leq b_m \implies d(b, b_m) = \mu(b_m, b) = \mu(b_m, b_n) + \mu(b_n, b) \geq \mu(b_n, b) = \epsilon \implies d(b, b_m) \geq \epsilon, \forall m \geq n$ which is contradictory. Hence, b is an upper bound for $\{a_n\}$. Now let $c \in A$ be an upper bound of $\{a_n\} \implies b_0 = a_0 \leq c$. For any $n \in \omega, b_n \leq c, b_{n+1} = b_n \vee a_{n+1} \leq c [: a_n \leq c]$. Let $\epsilon > 0. \because b_n \rightarrow b, \exists N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n > N, d(b, b_n) < \epsilon$. Now we know that $(b_n \wedge c) \Delta (b \wedge c) = (b \Delta b_n) \wedge c \leq b \Delta b_n \implies \forall n > N, d(b_n \wedge c, b \wedge c) \leq \mu(b \Delta b_n) < \epsilon \implies b_n \wedge c \rightarrow b \wedge c \implies b = \lim_n b_n = \lim_n (b_n \wedge c) = b \wedge c \implies b \leq c \implies b = \sup_n a_n$, thus proving our claim.

Claim: μ is σ -additive.

Proof of Claim: Let $\{a_n\}$ be a disjoint sequence in A . Since μ is finitely additive, $\mu(\bigvee_{k \leq n} a_k) = \sum_{k \leq n} \mu(a_k), \forall n \implies \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(\bigvee_{k \leq n} a_k) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k \leq n} \mu(a_k) = \sum_{k \in \omega} \mu(a_k) = \mu(\bigvee_{k \in \omega} a_k) = \mu(b_n) := \bigvee_{k \leq n} a_k. \because A$ is σ -complete, $b_n \rightarrow \bigvee_{i \in \omega} a_i (= c)$. Since μ is 1-Lipschitz, $|\mu(b_n) - \mu(c)| \leq d(b_n, c) \rightarrow 0 \implies \mu(\bigvee_{i \in \omega} a_i) = \lim_n \mu(b_n) = \lim_n \mu(\bigvee_{k \leq n} a_k) = \sum_{k \in \omega} \mu(a_k)$, thus proving our claim.

Since A is a Boolean σ - algebra and μ is countably additive, (A, μ) is a measure algebra and by Stone representation theorem for measure algebras, it follows that M is a probability algebra. Now as in [17], we see that the action obtained from the *p.m.p.* axioms on M descends to a *p.m.p.* action on the underlying Stone space which can be realized as a probability space via Stone representation theorem of a measure algebra. \square

Hence, we have formalized the notion of *p.m.p.* actions via the theory PMP_Γ .

Theorem 9.3.2. *If $\mathcal{X} \models PMP_\Gamma$ and \mathcal{Y} is a substructure of \mathcal{X} , then we claim that \mathcal{Y} is a closed, Γ invariant subalgebra of \mathcal{X} .*

Proof. Γ invariance is clear because \mathcal{Y} is a structure, hence, $\gamma^{\mathcal{Y}} : \mathcal{Y} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}, \forall \gamma \in \Gamma$. Also, \mathcal{Y} is a complete metric space. Hence, \mathcal{Y} is closed subset of \mathcal{X} . Now, again, since \mathcal{Y} is a substructure, hence, it is closed under \cup, \cap, \neg . So, we have

$$\neg^{\mathcal{X}}(i(A)) = i(\neg^{\mathcal{Y}}(A)), \forall A \in \mathcal{Y}$$

where i is the inclusion map. Therefore, $[\phi], [X] \in \mathcal{Y}$. Let $[A_n] \in \mathcal{Y}, n \in \mathbb{N}$. Clearly, $\forall n, \bigcup_{k=1}^n [A_k] \in \mathcal{Y}$. Now $\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} [A_k] \in \mathcal{X}$. Now, any increasing sequence in \mathcal{X} is Cauchy. Here, $\{\bigcup_{k=1}^n [A_k]\}_{n \geq 1}$ is increasing, hence, Cauchy. And the limit of this sequence is $\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} [A_k]$. Since \mathcal{Y} is complete, the limit is in \mathcal{Y} . Hence, \mathcal{Y} is a sub σ -algebra of \mathcal{X} . \square

Now we have a *p.m.p.* action for \mathcal{X} of Γ written as $\Gamma \curvearrowright (X, \sigma, \mu)$ and we also have, $\Gamma \curvearrowright (X, \sigma', \mu)$ for \mathcal{Y} where σ' is a sub- σ -algebra. Clearly, \mathcal{Y} is a factor of \mathcal{X} . Hence, substructures of PMP_{Γ} are also models of PMP_{Γ} .

9.4 Free actions and their formalization

In this section, we consider standard probability spaces. We recall the definition of free actions.

Definition 9.4.1. *The p.m.p. action $\Gamma \curvearrowright (X, \sigma, \mu)$ is said to be free if there is a Γ -invariant set $X_0 \subseteq X$ with $\mu(X_0) = 1$ such that if $sx = x$ for some $s \in \Gamma, x \in X_0$ then $s = \mathbb{1}_{\Gamma}$.*

We now define a theory $FPMP_{\Gamma}$ which has the same language and axioms as PMP_{Γ} along with the following axioms:

For every $\gamma \in \Gamma$ of finite order n , the axiom,

$$\text{inf}_a \max \{ \{ |\mu(a) - \frac{1}{n}| \} \cup \{ \gamma^i a \cap \gamma^j a \mid 0 \leq i \neq j \leq n \} \}$$

If γ is of infinite order, then we add this axiom for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. We claim that any free action satisfies the axioms. For showing this, we need a few pre-requisites from [6].

Let (X, σ, μ) be a probability space and $Aut(X)$ be the set of all measure preserving automorphisms of X .

Definition 9.4.2. *If $T \in Aut(X)$ and $T^n x = x$, for some $x \in X$ then T is said to be periodic at x . And the period of T at x is the smallest positive integer n such that $T^n x = x$.*

Definition 9.4.3. *T is said to be periodic in X if $\exists n \in \mathbb{N}$, such that $T^n = I$. And the least such n is the period of T .*

Definition 9.4.4. *T is almost nowhere periodic/antiperiodic if $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mu(\{x \in X \mid T^n x = x\}) = 0$.*

We now have the following lemmas:

Lemma 9.4.5. *If T is periodic of period n a.e., then \exists a measurable set E of measure $\frac{1}{n}$ such that the sets $E, T(E), T^2(E) \dots T^{n-1}(E)$ are pairwise disjoint.*

Proof. We are going to prove this lemma by induction. If $n = 1$, we clearly see that we don't need to prove anything, since in this case we can take E to be the whole space X . If $n = 2$, it is clear that $\exists E_1$ such that $\mu(E_1 \setminus T(E_1)) > 0$, since otherwise the fact that the period of $T = 2$ would be violated. Then we can set $F_1 = E_1 \setminus T(E_1)$. Clearly this satisfies the disjointness condition. For the time being let us take the disjointness condition in our stride. If suppose now that for $n = k$, the fact has been established. Then for $n = k + 1$, we have that we can find by the previous case F_k such that the pairwise disjointness condition holds for $F_k, \dots, T^{k-1}(F_k)$ are pairwise disjoint. Then, we can surely get $E_{k+1} \subseteq F_k$ such that $\mu(E_{k+1} \setminus T^{k+1}(E_{k+1})) > 0$ (exists because the period of T is $k + 1$). Clearly if we set $F_{k+1} = E_{k+1} \setminus T^{k+1}(E_{k+1})$, we have the required disjointness condition for $n = k + 1$ also. Thus by induction we see that if T is periodic of period n , we get the existence of a non measure zero set E such that $E, \dots, T^{n-1}(E)$ are pairwise disjoint. We can therefore choose E to be the maximal such subset of X which will give us this disjointness condition. Now if we get that $\mu(E) < \frac{1}{n}$, then we rerun this argument on the space $X \setminus \bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} T^i(E)$ to obtain $E' \subseteq X \setminus \bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} T^i(E)$ with the same disjointness property. Now, $E \cup E'$, can therefore be seen to easily violate the maximality of E . Therefore, $\mu(E) \geq \frac{1}{n}$. Now, if it was $> \frac{1}{n}$, by the measure preserving property of T , and disjointness, we would be able to contradict the fact that X is a probability space. \square

Lemma 9.4.6. *(Rokhlin's Lemma) If T is antiperiodic then for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and every $\epsilon > 0$, \exists measurable set E such that $E, T(E) \dots T^{n-1}(E)$ are pairwise disjoint and $\mu(\bigcup_{k=0}^{n-1} T^k(E)) > 1 - \epsilon$.*

Proof. Given T is antiperiodic, we shall use the argument in the above lemma, to obtain F , such that $F, \dots, T^{n \cdot n_0 - 1}(F)$ are pairwise disjoint, and $\mu(F) \leq \frac{1}{n \cdot n_0}$, where n_0 is large enough for $\frac{1}{n_0}$ to be $< \epsilon$. Without loss of generality we take F to be the maximal such. If $F_0 \subseteq T^{n \cdot n_0 - 1}(F)$ such that $\mu(F_0) > 0$, then there must be a j such that $\mu(T^j(F_0) \cap F) > 0$, since otherwise $F \cup F_0$ would contradict the maximality of F . (Choosing an appropriate subset of F_0 instead of F_0 if necessary). So, if we let $F_j = \{x \in T^{n \cdot n_0 - 1}(F) : T^j(x) \in F \text{ but, } T^i(x) \notin F \text{ where } 1 \leq i < j\}$. Due to the above arguments, we have that the F_j 's almost cover $T^{n \cdot n_0 - 1}(F)$. Let us now consider the following array:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
TF_2 & & \\
& & \\
TF_3 & T^2F_3 & \\
\vdots & \vdots & \\
TF_{pn} & T^2F_{pn} \cdots T^{pn-1}F_{pn} &
\end{array}$$

It is very easy to see that any two sets in the same column of the array are disjoint and taking inverse images of two sets in different columns under suitable powers of T , we get that they are subsets of two different sets in the collection $F, \dots, T^{n.n_0-1}$. So, two sets in different columns of the array must also be disjoint. A close inspection reveals that the sets in the array are also disjoint from $T^k(F)$ for every k such that $0 \leq k \leq n.n_0 - 1$. The reasoning for that is as follows:

If, $k > i$, then $T^i(F_j) \cap T^k(F) \subseteq T^i(T^{n.n_0-1}(F) \cap T^{k-i}(F))$.

Again if, $k \leq i$, then $0 \leq i - k < j$. Then $T^{i-k}(F_j) \cap F$ is empty, and therefore $T^i(F_j) \cap T^k(F)$ is also empty. Using these arguments, we can define a set $F' = \bigcup_{k=0}^{n.n_0-1} T^k(F) \cup \bigcup_{1 \leq i < j \leq n.n_0} T^i(F_j)$, which can be easily shown to be almost invariant under T , and therefore by anti-periodicity of measure 1.

Define E to be $\bigcup_{k=0}^{n_0-1} T^{kn}(F) \cup \bigcup_{i+n-1 < j} T^i(F_j)$. A simple check shows that $E, \dots, T^{n-1}(E)$ are pairwise disjoint. Let, $\bigcup_{k=0}^{n-1} T^k(E)$ be called V . Then, clearly $F' \setminus V \subseteq \bigcup_{i < n, j \leq n_0} T^i(F_j)$. So, $\mu(F' \setminus V) \leq \sum_{j=1}^{n_0} (n \cdot \mu(F_j)) = n \cdot \mu(F) = \frac{1}{n_0} < \epsilon$. So, $\mu(V) = 1 - \mu(F' \setminus V) > 1 - \epsilon$. \square

We are done with the pre-requisites. Applying these two lemmas, we prove the following:

Theorem 9.4.7. *Any free p.m.p. action satisfies the above axioms of $FPMP_\Gamma$.*

Proof. Let $\Gamma \curvearrowright (X, \sigma, \mu)$ be a p.m.p. action. Now for $\gamma \in \Gamma, \gamma \in \text{Aut}(X)$. If $o(\gamma) = n$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ then γ is periodic of period n . Now, we apply Lemma 9.4.5 to get E_γ . Also, if the corresponding model in PMP_Γ is \mathcal{X} , then γ induces an automorphism in \mathcal{X} which we again denote by γ .

Now $\mu([E_\gamma]) = \frac{1}{n}$ and $\mu(\gamma^i[E_\gamma] \cap \gamma^j[E_\gamma]) = \mu([\gamma^i E_\gamma \cap \gamma^j E_\gamma]) = 0$
 $\therefore \text{inf}_a \max\{|\mu(a) - \frac{1}{n}|\} \cup \{\gamma^i a \cap \gamma^j a | 0 \leq i \neq j \leq n\} = 0$ in \mathcal{X} .

Now if γ is of infinite order then fix $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Clearly, γ is antiperiodic. By Lemma

9.4.6, for all $\epsilon = \frac{1}{k}$, we get the corresponding $E_{nk} \in \sigma$.

Now $1 + \frac{1}{k} > \mu(\bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} T^i(E_{nk})) > 1 - \frac{1}{k}$.

$\implies \frac{1+\frac{1}{k}}{n} > \mu(E_{nk}) > \frac{1-\frac{1}{k}}{n} \implies |\frac{1}{n} - \mu(E_{nk})| < \frac{1}{kn}$.

And $\mu(\gamma^i E_{kn} \cap \gamma^j E_{kn}) = 0, \forall i \neq j$

Similarly as before, we denote the induced automorphism in \mathcal{X} by γ and see that

$|\frac{1}{n} - \mu([E_{nk}])| < \frac{1}{kn}$ and $\mu(\gamma^i[E_{kn}] \cap \gamma^j[E_{kn}]) = 0, \forall i \neq j$

We see that $\forall \epsilon' > 0, \exists k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\frac{1}{kn} < \epsilon'$.

And $\max\{|\mu([E_{nk}]) - \frac{1}{n}| \cup \{\mu(\gamma^i[E_{nk}] \cap \gamma^j[E_{nk}]) | 0 \leq i \neq j \leq n\}\} < \frac{1}{kn} < \epsilon'$

$\therefore \inf_a \max\{|\mu(a) - \frac{1}{n}| \cup \{\mu(\gamma^i a \cap \gamma^j a) | 0 \leq i \neq j \leq n\}\} = 0$ in $\mathcal{X}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Hence, all the axioms of $FPMP_\Gamma$ are satisfied. \square

We will now see that the converse of the above theorem also holds.

Theorem 9.4.8. *If $\mathcal{X} \models FPMP_\Gamma$ then \mathcal{X} is the measure algebra of a probability space (X, σ, μ) on which Γ acts freely.*

Proof. Now $\mathcal{X} \models FPMP_\Gamma \implies \mathcal{X} \models PMP_\Gamma$. So, we get a underlying probability space (X, σ, μ) on which Γ acts by measure- preserving transformations.

Now, we claim that $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma, \mu(\{x \in X | \gamma.x = x\}) = 0$.

Fix $\gamma \in \Gamma$. If $o(\gamma) = n$ or the order is infinite, we have

$\inf_a \max\{|\mu(a) - \frac{1}{n}| \cup \{\mu(\gamma^i a \cap \gamma^j a) | 0 \leq i \neq j \leq n\}\} = 0$ in \mathcal{X} .

\implies For each $k \in \mathbb{N}, \exists \bar{a}_k \in \mathcal{X}$ such that

$\max\{|\mu(\bar{a}_k) - \frac{1}{n}| \cup \{\mu(\gamma^i \bar{a}_k \cap \gamma^j \bar{a}_k) | 0 \leq i \neq j \leq n\}\} < \frac{1}{k}$

$\implies \mu(\bar{a}_k) < \frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{k}$ and $\mu(\gamma^i \bar{a}_k \cap \gamma^j \bar{a}_k) < \frac{1}{k}$.

$\implies |\mu(a_k) - \frac{1}{n}| < \frac{1}{k}$ and $\mu(\gamma^i a_k \cap \gamma^j a_k) < \frac{1}{k}$.

Now, $\mu(\bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} \gamma^i a_k) \geq n\mu(a_k) - n(\sum_{i \neq j} \mu(\gamma^i a_k \cap \gamma^j a_k)) \geq n(\frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{k}) - \frac{n^2}{k}$.

$\implies \mu(\bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} \gamma^i a_k) \geq 1 - \frac{n}{k} - \frac{n^2}{k}$.

Let $A_k := \bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} \gamma^i a_k$ and $\epsilon_k = \mu(A_k^c)$.

Clearly, $\epsilon_k \leq n(\frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{n})$.

$\therefore k \rightarrow \infty \implies \epsilon_k \rightarrow 0$.

Now $\{x \in X | \gamma.x = x\} \subseteq \bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} (\gamma^i a_k \cap a_k) \cup A_k^c, \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$.

$\therefore \mu(\{x \in X | \gamma.x = x\}) \leq \frac{n}{k} + \epsilon_k, \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$.

$\therefore \mu(\{x \in X | \gamma.x = x\}) = 0$.

Hence, the action is free. \square

Chapter 10

Existential theory and weak containment

The notion of **weak containment** for measure-preserving actions was introduced by Kechris [9].

Definition 10.0.9. Let Γ be a discrete group and let \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} be two measure-preserving actions of Γ . We say \mathcal{X} is weakly contained in \mathcal{Y} ($\mathcal{X} <_w \mathcal{Y}$) if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and finitely many $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} \in \mathcal{X}$ and $\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{n-1} \in \Gamma$ there are $b_0, b_1, \dots, b_{n-1} \in \mathcal{Y}$ such that $|\mu(a_i \cap \gamma_l a_j) - \mu(b_i \cap \gamma_l b_j)| \leq \epsilon$ for every $i, j < n$ and $l < k$.

Definition 10.0.10. The existential theory of a structure M , denoted by $Th_{\exists}(M)$, is given by the set of statements of the form $\inf_{\bar{a}} \phi(\bar{a})$ true in M where ϕ is a quantifier-free formula.

Lemma 10.0.11. Let \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} be two p.m.p. actions of Γ . Then the following are equivalent:

(i) $\mathcal{X} <_w \mathcal{Y}$.

(ii) $Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{X}) \subseteq Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{Y})$ or one can say that $\mathcal{Y} \models Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{X})$.

(iii) There is an elementary extension (equivalently, an ultrapower) \mathcal{Y}' of \mathcal{Y} such that $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}'$.

Proof. (ii) \implies (i) : Let $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} \in \mathcal{X}$ and $\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{k-1} \in \Gamma$ for some $n, k \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $k_{ijl} = \mu(a_i \cap \gamma_l a_j)$ where $0 \leq i, j \leq n-1; 0 \leq l \leq k-1$. We take the following formula in the language of PMP_{Γ} :

$$\phi = \sum_{i,j,l} |\mu(x_i \cap x_j) - k_{ijl}|$$

Clearly, $\inf_{(\bar{x}=x_0, x_2, \dots, x_{n-1})} \phi(\bar{x}) \in Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{X}) \implies \inf_{(\bar{x})} \phi(\bar{x}) \in Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{Y})$.

\therefore For all $\epsilon > 0, \exists b_0, b_1 \dots b_{n-1} \in \mathcal{Y}$ such that $\phi(b_0, b_1 \dots b_{n-1}) < \epsilon$

$$\implies \sum_{i,j,l} |\mu(b_i \cap \gamma_l b_j) - k_{ijl}| < \epsilon$$

$$\implies \forall 0 \leq i, j \leq n-1; 0 \leq l \leq k-1, |\mu(b_i \cap \gamma_l b_j) - k_{ijl}| < \epsilon$$

$$\implies \forall 0 \leq i, j \leq n-1; 0 \leq l \leq k-1, |\mu(b_i \cap \gamma_l b_j) - \mu(a_i \cap \gamma_l a_j)| < \epsilon.$$

Hence, $\mathcal{X} <_w \mathcal{Y}$.

(i) \implies (ii): This can be proved by considering the various possibilities of formulas in this structure. Suppose we have the formula $\inf_a \mu(\gamma.a) = 0$ Then $\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists a \in \mathcal{X}$ such that $\mu(\gamma.a) < \frac{\epsilon}{2} \implies \exists b \in \mathcal{Y}$ such that $|\mu(\gamma.a) - \mu(\gamma.b)| < \frac{\epsilon}{2} \implies \mu(\gamma.b) < \epsilon$. So, $\inf_a \mu(\gamma.a) \in Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{X}) \implies \inf_a \mu(\gamma.a) \in Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{Y})$. The case of d follows from the axiom connecting μ and d and by using $\mu(a^c) = 1 - \mu(a)$ and De Morgan's law for writing unions in terms of intersections, we can prove rest of the cases.

(iii) \implies (ii) : $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}' \implies \mathcal{X}$ is a closed, Γ -invariant subalgebra of \mathcal{Y} . Then clearly, $\inf_{\bar{x}} \phi^{\mathcal{Y}}(\bar{x}) \leq \inf_{\bar{x}} \phi^{\mathcal{X}}(\bar{x})$.

$\implies Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{X}) \subseteq Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{Y}')$. Now, we take \mathcal{Y}'' which is clearly an ultrapower of \mathcal{Y}' . From Theorem 8.3.7, we have elementary embeddings $\mathcal{Y} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}'$ and $\mathcal{Y}' \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}''$ which gives us an elementary embedding $\mathcal{Y} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}''$. Now \mathcal{Y}'' is an ultrapower of \mathcal{Y}' so we can say that \mathcal{Y} embeds elementarily into an ultrapower of $\mathcal{Y}' \implies \mathcal{Y} \equiv \mathcal{Y}'$ (Theorem 8.3.8) $\implies Th(\mathcal{Y}) = Th(\mathcal{Y}')$.

Hence, we have $Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{X}) \subseteq Th_{\exists}(\mathcal{Y})$.

(ii) (\iff) (i) \implies (iii) : We consider the language $L(\mathcal{X}) = L \cup \mathcal{X}, \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, x$ is a constant symbol. And if $a \in \mathcal{X}, \gamma \in \Gamma$, we denote $\gamma(a)$ as a_{γ} . Now we consider the following axioms : $d(\gamma(a), a_{\gamma}) (= 0)$. Then by suitably choosing the interpretations of the constant symbols, clearly they can be made finitely satisfiable. In fact using the weak containment, we get for any $a \in \mathcal{X}$, good enough $b \in \mathcal{Y}$ such that $|\mu(a) - \mu(b)| < \epsilon$. So if we consider $\{Y_{\alpha} | \alpha < \mathcal{X}\}$ to be a large enough collection of $L(\mathcal{X})$ structures with each $Y_{\alpha} = \mathcal{Y}$ then any finite subcollection of our collection of axioms will be satisfiable at some large enough α (where the interpretations are appropriate) and with ϵ small enough. Then if we let \mathcal{Y}' to be the ultraproduct of these Y_{α} 's, we have the desired result. \square

Definition 10.0.12. *Two models of PMP_Γ are weakly equivalent if they have the same existential theories.*

Let W be the space of weak equivalence classes of models of PMP_Γ . Now, W can be identified with the space of existential theories consistent with PMP_Γ . We observe that if $M, N \models PMP_\Gamma$ such that $Th_\exists(M) = Th_\exists(N)$, then if ϕ is an existential formula, $\phi^M = \phi^N$. So, one can define a function $f_\phi : W \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as $f([M]) = \phi^M$. We define **logic topology** on W to be the weakest topology which makes f_ϕ continuous for all existential formula ϕ . A subbasis of this topology is as follows:

$$B = \{f_\phi^{-1}((a, b)) \mid \phi \text{ is existential and } (a, b) \subseteq \mathbb{R}\}.$$

Since, for $[M] \in W, \phi$ existential, if $\phi^M \in (a, b)$, then $[M] \in f_\phi^{-1}(a, b)$.

Definition 10.0.13. *A system \mathcal{X} is said to be ergodic if every invariant subset is trivial. i.e., if $[S] \in \mathcal{X}$ is such that if $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma, [\gamma S] = [S]$, then $[S] = [\phi]$ or $[X]$.*

Definition 10.0.14. *A system \mathcal{X} is said to be strongly ergodic if for a sequence $\{a_n\}$ in \mathcal{X} , if $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma, \mu(a_n \Delta \gamma a_n) \rightarrow 0$ then $\mu(a_n)(1 - \mu(a_n)) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.*

Proposition 10.0.15. *\mathcal{X} is strongly ergodic if for every $\epsilon > 0$ there are $\delta > 0$ and finitely many $\gamma_0, \gamma_1 \dots \gamma_{k-1} \in \Gamma$ such that whenever $\epsilon < \mu(a) < 1 - \epsilon, a \in \mathcal{X}$, we have $\max_{i < k} d_\mu(a, \gamma_i a) \geq \delta$.*

Proof. Let $\{[A_n]\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in \mathcal{X} such that $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma, \mu([A_n] \Delta \gamma [A_n]) \rightarrow 0$. If $\mu(A_n)$ doesn't converge to 0 or 1 then $\exists \epsilon > 0$ such that $\epsilon < \mu(A_n) < 1 - \epsilon$ for infinite many n . Therefore, $\exists \delta > 0; \gamma_0, \gamma_1 \dots \gamma_{k-1} \in \Gamma$ such that $\max_{i < k} d_\mu([A_n], \gamma_i [A_n]) \geq \delta^*$ for infinite many n .

Since $\{\gamma_0 \dots \gamma_{k-1}\}$ is a finite set and the natural numbers n for which (*) holds (let us call this set S) are infinite, $\exists 0 \leq i_0 \leq k - 1$ and $S' \subseteq S, (|S'| = \omega)$ such that $d_\mu([A_n], \gamma_{i_0} [A_n]) \geq \delta, \forall n \in S'$

$\implies \mu(A_n \Delta \gamma_{i_0} A_n) \geq \delta, \forall n \in S'$, which is a contradiction to our assumption, since S' is infinite. Hence, $\mu(A_n)$ converges to 0 or 1. Thus, \mathcal{X} is strongly ergodic. \square

Chapter 11

Compact extensions and distal systems

This chapter and the next one has been primarily studied from [7], [10]. We have assumed and stated some results from the references and have attempted to study some of the proofs in [7] in more detail.

11.1 Conditional expectation

Let Γ be a countable, discrete group and $\mathcal{X} \models PMP_\Gamma$. Let $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ be a substructure of \mathcal{X} . This implies that \mathcal{Z} is a closed, Γ -invariant subalgebra of \mathcal{X} , or a factor of \mathcal{X} because of the following theorem:

Theorem 11.1.1. *Let $\Gamma \curvearrowright (X, \mu)$ be a p.m.p. action and let \mathcal{C} be a Γ -invariant sub- σ algebra of B_X (Borel σ algebra). Then there exists a p.m.p. action $\Gamma \curvearrowright (Y, \nu)$ and a Γ factor map $\pi : X \rightarrow Y$ such that $\pi^{-1}(B_Y) = \mathcal{C}$ modulo null sets.*

So, if (X, B, μ) is an underlying probability space of \mathcal{X} , then \exists an underlying probability space (X, C, μ') of \mathcal{Z} where C is a sub- σ algebra of B and $\mu' = \mu|_C$. So, we write μ' as μ .

Now, for every element $f \in L^1(X, B, \mu)$, \exists a unique $E_C(f) \in L^1(X, C, \mu)$ such that

$$\int_X E_C(f)g d\mu = \int_X fg d\mu, \forall g \in L^\infty(X, C, \mu).$$

We often alternatively use the notation $E(f|C)$ for $E_C(f)$. For showing that the above fact is indeed true, we refer to the following theorems, the proofs of which can be found in [15]:

Theorem 11.1.2. Suppose $1 \leq p < \infty$, μ is a σ -finite positive measure on X , and Φ is a bounded linear functional on $L^p(X, B, \mu)$. Then there is a unique $g \in L^q(X, B, \mu)$, where q is the exponent conjugate to p , such that

$$\Phi(f) = \int_X fgd\mu \quad (f \in L^p(X, B, \mu)) \quad (1)$$

Moreover, if Φ and g are related as in (1), then we have

$$\|\Phi\| = \|g\|_q.$$

Theorem 11.1.3. Let μ be a positive, σ -finite measure on a σ -algebra C in a set X , and let ν be a complex measure on C . Then if ν is absolutely continuous with respect to μ , then \exists a unique $h \in L^1(X, C, \mu)$ such that

$$\nu(A) = \int_X h\chi_{Ad}\mu.$$

Uniqueness of $E_C(f)$:

Proof. Using Theorem 11.1.2, we conclude that the map $\psi : L^\infty(X, C, \mu) \rightarrow L^1(X, C, \mu)^*$ defined as $\psi(g)(f) = \int_X fgd\mu$ is an isometric isomorphism. So, if for $f \in L^1(X, B, \mu)$, $\exists E_C(f), E_C(f)' \in L^1(X, C, \mu)$ such that

$$\int_X E_C(f)gd\mu = \int_X E_C(f)'gd\mu, \quad \forall g \in L^\infty(X, C, \mu)$$

then we have that every element of $L^1(X, C, \mu)^*$ maps $E_C(f), E_C(f)'$ to the same point. $\implies E_C(f) = E_C(f)'$. \square

Existence of $E_C(f)$:

Proof. We consider the finite complex measure on (X, C) given by $\nu(A) = \int_X f\chi_{Ad}\mu$. Now clearly, ν is absolutely continuous with respect to μ . Applying Theorem 11.1.3, we get that for every $f \in L^1(X, B, \mu)$ ($\implies f \in L^1(X, C, \mu)$), $\exists h \in L^1(X, C, \mu)$ such that $\nu(A) = \int_X h\chi_{Ad}\mu, \forall A \in C \implies \int_X f\chi_{Ad}\mu = \int_X h\chi_{Ad}\mu, \forall A \in C$

Since simple functions are dense in $L^\infty(X, C, \mu)$, we have

$$\int_X fgd\mu = \int_X hgd\mu, \quad \forall g \in L^\infty(X, C, \mu).$$

We take $E_C(f) = h$. \square

We thus, obtain a *positive linear* map $E_C : L^1(X, B, \mu) \rightarrow L^1(X, C, \mu)$ called the **conditional expectation**. (positivity meaning here that $f \geq 0 \implies E_C(f) \geq 0$) where linearity follows from the uniqueness of $E_C(f)$, $f \in L^1(X, B, \mu)$ and distribution of the integral over addition and positivity follows from the property of the Radon-Nickodym derivative.

11.2 A conditional inner product

Definition 11.2.1. Let $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ be an extension of measure algebras. A Hilbert subspace $M \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{X})$ is a \mathcal{L} -module if it is closed under multiplication by functions of $L^\infty(\mathcal{L})$. The \mathcal{L} -module generated by a set $S \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{X})$ is the closed span of $L^\infty(\mathcal{L})S$.

Given $f, g \in L^2(\mathcal{X})$, we define $\langle f, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} := E(f\bar{g}|\mathcal{L}) \in L^1(\mathcal{L})$ (the conditional expectation of $f\bar{g}$ relative to \mathcal{L})

A set $S \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{X})$ is \mathcal{L} -**orthonormal** if $\langle f, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} = 0$ for distinct $f, g \in S$, and $\langle f, f \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}$ is a characteristic function for each $f \in S$.

If $f \in L^2(\mathcal{X})$, its \mathcal{L} -**support** (denoted by $\text{supp}_{\mathcal{L}} f$) is the support of the function $\langle f, f \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}$, which is an element of \mathcal{L} . We will write $\chi_{\mathcal{L}}(f)$ for the characteristic function of $\text{supp}_{\mathcal{L}} f$.

We say that S is a \mathcal{L} -**basis** for a \mathcal{L} -module M if it is \mathcal{L} -orthonormal, generates M , and each element of S has full \mathcal{L} -support.

The following lemma summarizes several properties of the conditional inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}$:

Lemma 11.2.2. Let $\{e_i : i < n\}$ be a finite, generating, \mathcal{L} -orthonormal set for a \mathcal{L} -module $M \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{X})$ and let $f, g \in M$. Then the following statements hold:

(i) (Cauchy-Schwarz) $|\langle f, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}|^2 \leq \langle f, f \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} \langle g, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}$.

(ii) $\text{supp} \langle f, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} \subseteq \text{supp}_{\mathcal{L}} f \cap \text{supp}_{\mathcal{L}} g$. In particular,

$$\langle f, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} = \langle f, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} \chi_{\mathcal{L}}(f) \chi_{\mathcal{L}}(g)$$

(iii) $f = \sum_{i < n} \langle f, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} e_i$.

Proof. (i) has a standard proof which follows from the fact that conditional expectation is a positive linear map. ([11] Pg 198).

(ii) From (i), we have $\langle f, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} \neq 0 \implies \langle f, f \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}, \langle g, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} \neq 0$.

Hence, $\text{supp} \langle f, g \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} \subseteq \text{supp}_{\mathcal{L}} f \cap \text{supp}_{\mathcal{L}} g$.

(iii) Using (i), we see that $\int_X |\langle f, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}|^2 d\mu = \int_X |\langle f, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}|^2 |e_i|^2 d\mu$

$$\leq \int_X \langle f, f \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} \langle e_i, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} |e_i|^2 d\mu \leq \int_X \langle f, f \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} |e_i|^2 d\mu$$

[$\because \langle e_i, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}$ is a characteristic function.]

$$= \int_X E(|f|^2|\mathcal{L}) |e_i|^2 \leq \|f\|^2. \text{ Hence, } \langle f, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} e_i \in L^2(\mathcal{X}).$$

Also, we have $\langle e_i, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} e_i = e_i$. This implies, when $f = \sum_{i < n} a_i e_i$ with

$a_i \in L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$, (iii) holds because $\sum_{j < n} \langle \sum_{i < n} a_i e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} e_j$
 $= \sum_{j < n} \sum_{i < n} a_i \langle e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} e_j = \sum_{i < n} a_i e_i = f$. Since, $\{e_i : i < n\}$ is a generating set, (iii)
holds $\forall f \in M$. □

Lemma 11.2.3. *Let $\{e_i | i < n\}$ and $\{f_j | j < m\}$ be two generating \mathcal{Z} -orthonormal sets for a \mathcal{Z} -module M . Let $a_{ij} = \langle e_i, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}}$ and $A = (a_{ij})_{i < n, j < m}$. Then the following hold:*

(i) *The entries of A are in $L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$.*

(ii) *$AA^* = \text{diag}(\chi_{\mathcal{Z}} e_0, \dots, \chi_{\mathcal{Z}} e_{n-1})$ and $A^*A = \text{diag}(\chi_{\mathcal{Z}} f_0, \dots, \chi_{\mathcal{Z}} f_{m-1})$.*

(iii) *$\sum_{i < n} \langle e_i, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \sum_{j < m} \langle f_j, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \sum_{i,j} |a_{ij}|^2$*

Proof. (i) Since $\{f_j | j < m\}$ is a generating set, $e_i = \sum_{j < m} b_j^i f_j$,

$\forall i < n$, where $b_j^i \in L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$. So, $a_{ij} = \langle e_i, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \langle \sum_{k < m} b_k^i f_k, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \sum_{k < m} b_k^i \langle f_k, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} \in L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$ [$\cdot \langle f_k, f_k \rangle$ is a characteristic function.]

(ii) Let $AA^* = (b_{kl})_{k,l < m}$. We know that,

$$AA^* = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \cdots & a_{nm} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \overline{a_{11}} & \overline{a_{21}} & \cdots & \overline{a_{n1}} \\ \overline{a_{12}} & \overline{a_{22}} & \cdots & \overline{a_{n2}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \overline{a_{1n}} & \overline{a_{2n}} & \cdots & \overline{a_{nn}} \end{pmatrix}$$

So, $b_{kl} = \sum_{j < m} \langle e_k, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} \overline{\langle e_l, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}}}$

$= \langle e_k, \sum_{j < m} \langle e_l, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}}$ [Using (i) of lemma 11.2.3 and finiteness of μ]
 $= \langle e_k, e_l \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}}$ [From lemma 11.2.2(iii)] $\implies AA^* = \text{diag}(\chi_{\mathcal{Z}} e_0, \dots, \chi_{\mathcal{Z}} e_{n-1})$.

Similarly, $A^*A = (\langle f_k, f_l \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}})_{k,l < n} = \text{diag}(\chi_{\mathcal{Z}} f_0, \dots, \chi_{\mathcal{Z}} f_{m-1})$.

(iii) Using Lemma 11.2.2(iii), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i < n} \langle e_i, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} &= \sum_{i < n} \langle e_i, \sum_{j < m} \langle e_i, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} \\ &= \sum_{i < n, j < m} \langle e_i, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} \overline{\langle e_i, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}}} = \sum_{i < n, j < m} |a_{ij}|^2. \end{aligned}$$

With similar arguments, we can show that $\sum_{j < m} \langle f_j, f_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \sum_{i,j} |a_{ij}|^2$ □

We will be mainly focusing in Γ -invariant and finitely generated \mathcal{Z} -modules. We state the following from [10] which will be used in the proof of Lemma 11.2.6:

Proposition 11.2.4. *The action $G \curvearrowright (X, B, \mu)$ is ergodic if and only if the restriction of the Koopman representation to the orthogonal complement of the constant functions is ergodic.*

Proposition 11.2.5. *For all $f \in L^1(X, B, \mu)$, if $G \curvearrowright (X, B, \mu)$ is pmp, and C (a sub- σ algebra of B) is Γ -invariant, then $E_C(\gamma.f) = \gamma.E_C(f)$, $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma$, and the action is the Koopmann representation.*

Lemma 11.2.6. *Let \mathcal{X} be a Γ -system and let \mathcal{Z} be an ergodic factor thereof. Then, every finitely generated Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -module $M \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{X})$ admits a finite \mathcal{Z} -basis.*

Proof. Let M be generated by a finite set $\{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$. By Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization process, we define the following: Let $h_1 = f_1$, $h_2 = f_2 - P_{\langle f_1 \rangle_{L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})}} f_2, \dots, h_n = f_n - P_{\langle f_1, \dots, f_{n-1} \rangle_{L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})}} f_n$, where $\langle f_1, \dots, f_i \rangle_{L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})}$, $1 \leq i \leq n$, denotes the \mathcal{Z} -submodule generated by $\{f_1, \dots, f_i\}$ and $P_{\langle f_1, \dots, f_i \rangle_{L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})}}$ is the orthogonal projection on $\langle f_1, \dots, f_i \rangle_{L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})}$.

Clearly, $\langle h_i, h_j \rangle_{L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})} = 0$, $i \neq j$ and $M = \bigoplus_{i=1}^n M_{h_i}$, where M_h is the \mathcal{Z} -module generated by h . Let $S_i = \text{supp}_{\mathcal{Z}} h_i$ and $e_i = (\langle h_i, h_i \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}})^{-\frac{1}{2}} h_i$ and e_i vanishes outside S_i . Then $\int_X |e_i|^2 d\mu = \int_{S_i} \frac{|h_i|^2}{\langle h_i, h_i \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}}} d\mu = \mu(S_i)$. Hence, $e_i \in L^2(\mathcal{X})$ and $\{e_i | i < n\}$ is a generating \mathcal{Z} -orthonormal system for M .

Claim: For every $\gamma \in \Gamma$, $\{\gamma.e_i | i < n\}$ is orthonormal and generating.

Proof of claim: We are given that $\{e_i | i < n\}$ is orthonormal and generating. So, $f \in M \implies f = \sum_{i < n} a_i e_i$, $a_i \in L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$. By the *p.m.p.* assumption, the map $\gamma : L^2(\mathcal{X}) \rightarrow L^2(\mathcal{X})$ (obtained from the Koopmann representation) is surjective. Since, $\gamma.(fg) = (\gamma.(f))(\gamma.(g))$, we have $\gamma.f = \sum_{i < n} (\gamma.a_i)(\gamma.e_i)$. Also, $\gamma.a_i \in L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$ since the action $\Gamma \curvearrowright (X, C, \mu')$ is *p.m.p.* So, we have $\{\gamma.e_i | i < n\}$ is generating set for M .

Now, we will use Proposition 11.2.5 for showing the orthonormal condition: Since, \mathcal{Z} is an ergodic factor, C is clearly Γ -invariant.

So, $\langle \gamma e_i, \gamma e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = E(\gamma.(e_i \bar{e}_j) | \mathcal{Z}) = \gamma.E(e_i \bar{e}_j | \mathcal{Z}) = \langle e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}}$.

Using the fact that $\{e_i | i < n\}$ is orthonormal, we conclude that $\{\gamma.e_i | i < n\}$ is orthonormal, hence, *proving the above claim.*

Now, we have two orthonormal, generating sets $\{e_i, i < n\}$ and $\{\gamma.e_i, i < n\}$. Using Lemma 11.2.3(iii) and Proposition 11.2.5, we get that

$$\sum_{i < n} \mathbb{1}_{S_i} = \sum_{i < n} \langle e_i, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \sum_{i < n} \langle \gamma e_i, \gamma e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \sum_{i < n} \gamma. \langle e_i, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \gamma. \sum_{i < n} \langle e_i, e_i \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} = \gamma. (\sum_{i < n} \mathbb{1}_{S_i})$$

$\implies \sum_{i < n} \mathbb{1}_{S_i}$ is Γ -invariant. Using the ergodicity assumption and proposition 11.2.4, we have $\sum_{i < n} \mathbb{1}_{S_i} = k$ (constant function). Let $[n]_k$ be the set of all k -element subsets of n .

For $\alpha \in [n]_k$, let $A_\alpha = \bigcap_{i \in \alpha} S_i$. For $i < k$, define $\sigma_i(\alpha)$ to be the i -th element of α (by

ordering it using the ordering of \mathbb{N} .) For $i < k$, define $e'_i = \sum_{\alpha \in [n]_k} \mathbb{1}_{A_\alpha} e_{\sigma_i(\alpha)}$

Claim: $\{e'_i | i < k\}$ is a \mathcal{L} -basis for M .

Proof of claim: Let $\alpha, \beta \in [n]_k$. Now $\alpha \neq \beta \implies A_\alpha \cap A_\beta = \emptyset$ [$\because \forall x \in X, x$ can be present in exactly ' k ' many S_i 's]

$$\implies \langle \mathbb{1}_{A_\alpha} e_{\sigma_i(\alpha)}, \mathbb{1}_{A_\beta} e_{\sigma_j(\beta)} \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} = 0 \quad \forall i, j < k.$$

$$\text{And when } \alpha = \beta, \text{ for } i \neq j, \langle e_{\sigma_i(\beta)}, e_{\sigma_j(\beta)} \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} = 0$$

$$\implies \langle \mathbb{1}_{A_\alpha} e_{\sigma_i(\alpha)}, \mathbb{1}_{A_\beta} e_{\sigma_j(\beta)} \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} = 0$$

So, we conclude that $\langle e'_i, e'_j \rangle_{\mathcal{L}} = 0, \quad \forall i, j < k, i \neq j.$

And $\langle e'_i, e'_i \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}$ has full \mathcal{L} -support.

Also, $\{e'_i | i < k\}$ is generating because $e_{i_0} = \sum_{\alpha \in [n]_k, i_0 \in \alpha} \mathbb{1}_{A_\alpha} e_{i_0}, \quad \forall i_0 < n.$

Hence, our claim as well as the lemma is proved. \square

Definition 11.2.7. A unitary representation $\pi : \Gamma \rightarrow B(H)$ is ergodic if there are no nonzero Γ -invariant vectors in H .

Proposition 11.2.8. Let \mathcal{X} be an ergodic Γ -system, $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ be a factor, and $M \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{X})$ be a finitely generated Γ -invariant \mathcal{L} -module. Then M admits a finite basis and the elements of any such basis are in $L^\infty(\mathcal{X})$.

Proof. The existence of a finite basis has been proved in Lemma 11.2.6. Let $\{e_i | i < n\}$ be a basis of M . If $\gamma \in \Gamma$, then $\{\gamma.e_i | i < n\}$ is again a basis of M . (using Proposition 11.2.5 and the arguments in the proof of Lemma 11.2.6). For $x \in X$, we define

$$u_\gamma(x) = \begin{pmatrix} \langle \gamma e_0, e_0 \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) & \langle \gamma e_0, e_1 \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) & \cdots & \langle \gamma e_0, e_{n-1} \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) \\ \langle \gamma e_1, e_0 \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) & \langle \gamma e_1, e_1 \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) & \cdots & \langle \gamma e_1, e_{n-1} \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \langle \gamma e_{n-1}, e_0 \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) & \langle \gamma e_{n-1}, e_1 \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) & \cdots & \langle \gamma e_{n-1}, e_{n-1} \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) \end{pmatrix}$$

By Lemma 11.2.3(ii), $u_\gamma(x)$ is a unitary matrix almost surely and the function u_γ is \mathcal{L} -measurable. Also, $\sum_{j < n} \langle \gamma e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) e_j(x) = ((\gamma e_i).(\sum_{i,j < n} \langle e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}))(x) = (\gamma.e_i \mathbb{1}_X)(x) = \gamma.e_i(x)$. So we have,

$$(11.1) \quad \sum_{j < n} \langle \gamma e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{L}}(x) e_j(x) = \gamma.e_i(x)$$

Now we consider the function $\theta : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ defined by

$\theta(x) = \sum_{i < n} |e_i(x)|^2 = \langle E(x), E(x) \rangle$, where $E = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$ and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes the usual inner product on \mathbb{C}^n . We have almost surely,

$\theta(\gamma^{-1}x) = \langle E(\gamma^{-1}(x)), E(\gamma^{-1}(x)) \rangle = \langle (\gamma E)(x), (\gamma E)(x) \rangle$
 $= \langle u_\gamma(x)E(x), u_\gamma(x)E(x) \rangle = \langle E(x), E(x) \rangle$ [·: u_γ is unitary and using Equation 11.1].

$\implies \theta$ is Γ -invariant and given that \mathcal{X} is ergodic, θ is constant [using Proposition 11.2.4].

If $\theta = k(\in \mathbb{R}^+)$ then $\forall x \in X, |e_i(x)|^2 \leq k \implies e_i$ is bounded

$\implies e_i \in L^\infty(\mathcal{X}), \forall i < n.$ □

11.3 Compact extensions

Definition 11.3.1. *An extension $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{Z}$ is compact if $L^2(\mathcal{X})$ decomposes as a direct sum of finitely generated, Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -modules.*

A factor generated by compact factors is a compact factor as well. In general, the following holds:

Proposition 11.3.2. *Let \mathcal{X} be an ergodic system. Suppose $Z_i \subseteq Y_i \subseteq \mathcal{X}, i \in I$, are factors such that each extension $Z_i \subseteq Y_i$ is compact. Then the factor $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ generated by all the Y_i is a compact extension of the factor \mathcal{Z} generated by all the Z_i .*

Proof. By definition, for each $i \in I, L^2(Y_i) = \bigoplus_{M \in M_i} M$, where M is a finitely generated Γ -invariant Z_i -module. Using Lemma 11.2.6, we choose a finite Z_{i_1} -basis in $L^\infty(\mathcal{X})$ for $M_1 \in M_{i_1}$ and call it $\{e_0, \dots, e_{n-1}\}$. Similarly we choose a Z_{i_2} -basis for $M_2 \in M_{i_2}$ and call it $\{f_0, \dots, f_{m-1}\}$. Let $M_1 M_2$ be the \mathcal{Z} -module generated by the products $\{e_p f_q : p < n, q < m\}$ (which are orthonormal and hence, in $L^\infty(\mathcal{X})$ by Proposition 11.2.8). Similarly, we define the product modules $M_1 M_2 \dots M_k$ over \mathcal{Z} for any given $M_j \in M_{i_j}$. These modules are Γ -invariant by construction. We will have $L^2(\mathcal{Y}) = \sum \{M_1 \dots M_k : k \in \mathbb{N}, M_j \in M_{i_j} \text{ for some } i_j \in I\}$ and $L^2(\mathcal{Y})$ can be expressed as a direct sum of these modules by an orthogonalization process (from the theory of modules) using Zorn's Lemma. This can be done as follows. We take all submodules of $L^2(\mathcal{Y})$ which can be written as direct sum of finitely generated Γ -invariant submodules. This collection is non-empty. We define a partial order on this collection by inclusion and clearly, every chain has an upper bound. So by Zorn's Lemma we get a maximal element M . Now if $M \neq L^2(\mathcal{Y})$, then there exists $M_1 M_2 \dots M_k$ such that $M_1 M_2 \dots M_k \not\subseteq M$. Let $N = M \cap M_1 M_2 \dots M_k$. If $N = \{0\}$, then maximality is contradicted and we are done. If $N \neq \{0\}$, N is finitely generated because $M_1 M_2 \dots M_k$ is finitely generated and it is Γ invariant because both M

and $M_1M_2\dots M_k$ are finitely generated. Let G be a finitely generated subset of N . We can extend G to a finitely generating set for $M_1M_2\dots M_k$. By Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization, let this collection be transformed to $G' \sqcup S'$ (after removing all linear dependencies). Then $M_1M_2\dots M_k = spG' \oplus spS' = N \oplus spS'$. Now as N and $M_1M_2\dots M_k$ are Γ -invariant, so is spS' which is finitely generated as well. So $M \oplus spS' \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{Y})$, contradicting maximality. \square

Corollary 11.3.3. *Let \mathcal{X} be an ergodic system and $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ be a factor of \mathcal{X} . Then there exists a factor \mathcal{Y} of \mathcal{X} such that $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$, the extension $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ is compact, and every compact extension of \mathcal{Z} in \mathcal{X} is contained in \mathcal{Y} .*

Proof. We see that $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Z}$ is a compact extension (existence) and using Proposition 11.3.2, the factor generated by all possible compact extensions of \mathcal{Z} , is our required compact extension. \square

Note: \mathcal{Y} is called the **maximal compact extension** of \mathcal{Z} in \mathcal{X} .

Lemma 11.3.4. *Suppose we have $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ and the extension $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is compact. Then the extensions $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ and $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ are compact.*

Proof. We observe that the projection of a finitely generated Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -module in $L^2(\mathcal{X})$ to $L^2(\mathcal{Y})$ is again a finitely generated Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -module $\implies \mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ is a compact extension.

For the extension $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ this is clear because $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ and if $L^2(\mathcal{X})$ can be expressed as a direct sum of Γ -invariant, finitely generated \mathcal{Z} -modules then $L^2(\mathcal{X})$ can be expressed as a sum of Γ -invariant, finitely generated \mathcal{Y} -modules and by applying the orthogonalization process as done in Proposition 11.3.2, we conclude the proof. \square

Let N be a finitely-generated Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -module and let $E = (e_0, \dots, e_{n-1})$ is a \mathcal{Z} -basis for N . We define the **matrix co-efficients** $m_E : \Gamma \rightarrow M_n(L^\infty(\mathcal{Z}))$ (using the fact that $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma, \gamma.E$ is a basis and Lemma 11.2.3(i)) by

$$m_E(\gamma) = (\langle \gamma.e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}})_{i,j < n}$$

Lemma 11.3.5. *Suppose $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a compact extension with \mathcal{X} ergodic. Let $E = (e_1, \dots, e_n)$ be a \mathcal{Z} -orthonormal basis for a finitely-generated Γ -invariant module $M \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{X})$. Then the set $\{E' \in L^2(\mathcal{X})^{\oplus n} : m_E = m_{E'}\}$ spans a subspace of $L^2(\mathcal{X})^{\oplus n}$ of dimension at most n .*

Proof. Let $E' = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$ be a tuple with $m_E = m_{E'}$.

Claim: The function $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ defined as $f(x) = \langle E(x), E'(x) \rangle$ is Γ -invariant ($\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ is standard inner product on \mathbb{C}^n).

Proof of claim: Let $\gamma \in \Gamma$ and $i, j < n$, the conditional expectations

$\langle \gamma \cdot e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $\langle \gamma \cdot e'_i, e'_j \rangle_{\mathcal{X}}$ are equal. Hence the \mathcal{X} -measurable map $u_\gamma : X \rightarrow U(n)$ given as $u_\gamma(x) = (\langle \gamma \cdot e'_i, e'_j \rangle_{\mathcal{X}})_{i,j < n}$ satisfies $(\gamma E)(x) = u_\gamma(x)E(x)$ and also $(\gamma E')(x) = u_\gamma(x)E'(x)$.

[From Equation 11.1]. Thus, $\langle E(\gamma^{-1}x), E'(\gamma^{-1}x) \rangle = \langle u_\gamma(x)E(x), u_\gamma E'(x) \rangle$

$= \langle u_\gamma u_\gamma^* E(x), E'(x) \rangle = \langle E(x), E'(x) \rangle \implies \gamma \cdot f = f$, proving the claim.

Now, by ergodicity assumption and Proposition 11.2.4, we conclude that f is a constant function.

Now we consider $n+1$ tuples E_0, \dots, E_n , with $m_{E_i} = m_E$. The matrix

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \langle E_0(x), E_0(x) \rangle & \langle E_0(x), E_1(x) \rangle & \cdots & \langle E_0(x), E_n(x) \rangle \\ \langle E_1(x), E_0(x) \rangle & \langle E_1(x), E_1(x) \rangle & \cdots & \langle E_1(x), E_n(x) \rangle \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \langle E_n(x), E_0(x) \rangle & \langle E_n(x), E_1(x) \rangle & \cdots & \langle E_n(x), E_n(x) \rangle \end{pmatrix}$$

doesn't depend on x be the previous claim. We observe that $E_i(x) \in \mathbb{C}^n, \implies \{E_i(x) | 0 \leq i \leq n\}$ is linearly dependent and using properties of inner product and evaluation of determinants, we conclude that $\text{rank}(M) \leq n$.

$\implies \exists \lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_n$ (not all 0) such that

$$\lambda_0 \begin{pmatrix} \langle E_0(x), E_0(x) \rangle \\ \langle E_1(x), E_0(x) \rangle \\ \vdots \\ \langle E_n(x), E_0(x) \rangle \end{pmatrix} + \lambda_1 \begin{pmatrix} \langle E_0(x), E_1(x) \rangle \\ \langle E_1(x), E_1(x) \rangle \\ \vdots \\ \langle E_0(x), E_1(x) \rangle \end{pmatrix} \dots + \lambda_n \begin{pmatrix} \langle E_0(x), E_n(x) \rangle \\ \langle E_1(x), E_n(x) \rangle \\ \vdots \\ \langle E_n(x), E_n(x) \rangle \end{pmatrix} = \bar{0}$$

\implies For almost every $x \in X, \sum_{j=0}^n \lambda_j \langle E_i(x), E_j(x) \rangle = 0$

$\implies \sum_{j=0}^n \lambda_j E_j \in L^2(\mathcal{X})^{\oplus n}$ is orthogonal to each E_j ,

$\implies \sum_{j=0}^n \lambda_j E_j = 0$ [$\because \langle \sum_{j=0}^n \lambda_j E_j(x), \sum_{j=0}^n \lambda_j E_j(x) \rangle = 0$]

$\implies E'_i$'s are linearly dependent.

Since the $n+1$ tuple was arbitrarily chosen, the proof is done. \square

Definition 11.3.6 (Automorphism group). *The group of all automorphisms of a measure algebra that commute with the action of Γ is said to be the automorphism group.*

If \mathcal{X} is a Γ -system, we will denote by $\text{Aut}(\mathcal{X})$ the group of automorphisms of \mathcal{X} . We equip $\text{Aut}(\mathcal{X})$ with the *pointwise convergence topology* on \mathcal{X} (i.e. the topology inherited

from the product space $\mathcal{X}^{|\mathcal{X}|}$, which makes it into a topological group.

If $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a factor, we will denote

$$\text{Aut}_{\mathcal{Z}}(\mathcal{X}) = \{\sigma \in \text{Aut}(\mathcal{X}) \mid \sigma(a) = a, \forall a \in \mathcal{Z}\}$$

We state the following facts about automorphism groups:

- $\text{Aut}_{\mathcal{Z}}(\mathcal{X})$ is a closed subgroup of $\text{Aut}(\mathcal{X})$.
- $\text{Aut}(\mathcal{X})$ can also be viewed as a closed subgroup of the unitary group $U(L^2(\mathcal{X}))$.

Proposition 11.3.7. *If $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a compact extension with \mathcal{X} ergodic, then $\text{Aut}_{\mathcal{Z}}(\mathcal{X})$ is compact.*

Proof. Since $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a compact extension, $L^2(\mathcal{X})$ can be written as direct sum of finitely-generated, Γ -invariant, \mathcal{Z} -modules. Now $f \in L^2(\mathcal{X}) \implies f$ can be written as a finite linear combination of the elements of the modules in the direct sum. By taking the sum of these modules, we obtain a finitely-generated, Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -module M containing f . Let $E = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$ be a \mathcal{Z} -basis for M . Now, $E' \in \text{Aut}_{\mathcal{Z}}(\mathcal{X}).E \implies m_E = m_{E'}$. (Using uniqueness of conditional expectation function.)

By Lemma 11.3.5, $\text{Aut}_{\mathcal{Z}}(\mathcal{X}).E$ is contained in a finite-dimensional subspace of $L^2(\mathcal{X})^{\oplus n} \implies$ orbit of f is contained in a finite dimensional subspace of $L^2(\mathcal{X}) \implies \because f$ was arbitrarily chosen, this holds for every element of $L^2(\mathcal{X})$. So $\text{Aut}_{\mathcal{Z}}(\mathcal{X})$, being a closed subgroup of a product of finite-dimensional unitary groups, is compact. \square

Definition 11.3.8. *An isomorphism between Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -modules is a linear isometry that commutes with the action of Γ and multiplication by elements of $L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$.*

We observe an isomorphism between \mathcal{Z} -modules preserves the conditional inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}}$. And if E is a \mathcal{Z} -basis of a module M and E' is a \mathcal{Z} -basis of a module M' , then there is an isomorphism between M and M' that maps E to E' iff $m_E = m_{E'}$. We have the following consequence of the previous lemma:

Proposition 11.3.9. *Suppose $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a compact extension with \mathcal{X} ergodic, and let $L^2(\mathcal{X}) = \bigoplus_{i \in I} M_i$ be a decomposition into finitely generated, Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -modules. Then, for each $i \in I$, the number of \mathcal{Z} -modules appearing in the decomposition that are isomorphic to M_i is bounded by the size of a \mathcal{Z} -basis of M_i and is therefore finite. In particular, $|\mathcal{X}| \leq (|\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0)^{\aleph_0}$.*

Proof. If possible, let $M_0, M_1, \dots, M_n \subseteq L^2(\mathcal{X})$ be isomorphic, finitely generated, invariant submodules of $L^2(\mathcal{X})$ that are pairwise orthogonal. Let $E \in L^2(\mathcal{X})^{\oplus n}$ be a \mathcal{Z} -basis of M_0 and let $f_i : M_0 \rightarrow M_i$ be isomorphisms. Since isomorphism preserves $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} \implies f_0(E), f_1(E), \dots, f_n(E)$ are mutually orthogonal \mathcal{Z} -bases of size n and $m_{f_i(E)} = m_{f_j(E)}, \forall 0 \leq i, j \leq n$ which contradicts Lemma 11.3.5.

For the particular case, let $\kappa = |\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0$. Now, an isomorphism class of Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -module is solely determined by its matrix coefficients $\langle \gamma \cdot e_i, e_j \rangle_{\mathcal{Z}} \in L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$ for some \mathcal{Z} -basis (e_0, \dots, e_{n-1}) due to preservation of conditional inner product. Also, using the fact that cardinal of $L^\infty(\mathcal{Z})$ is κ^{\aleph_0} , we conclude that there are at most κ^{\aleph_0} isomorphism classes of finitely generated, invariant \mathcal{Z} -modules of $L^2(\mathcal{X})$. From the first part of this proof, we have that each module can appear only finitely many times in the decomposition of $L^2(\mathcal{X})$ and has density character $|\mathcal{Z}|$, we have $|\mathcal{X}| = |L^2(\mathcal{X})| \leq \kappa^{\aleph_0} \cdot \kappa = \kappa^{\aleph_0}$. \square

11.4 Distal extensions

In this section, we shall study about distal extensions.

Definition 11.4.1 (Distal Extensions). *An extension $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is said to be distal if it can be obtained as tower of compact extensions i.e., if there is an ordinal number α and intermediate extensions $\{\mathcal{X}_\beta\}_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ such that*

- $\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{X}_0 \subseteq \mathcal{X}_\beta \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{\beta'} \subseteq \mathcal{X}_\alpha = \mathcal{X}$ for $\beta \leq \beta' \leq \alpha$,
- Each extension $\mathcal{X}_\beta \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{\beta+1}$ is compact,
- $\lambda \leq \alpha$ is a limit ordinal $\implies \mathcal{X}_\lambda$ is generated by the factors $\mathcal{X}_\beta, \beta < \lambda$.

We say that $\{\mathcal{X}_\beta\}_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ is a *distal tower* for the extension $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$. The minimal length α of such a tower is the **rank of the distal extension**, denoted by $rk(\mathcal{X}/\mathcal{Z})$. If \mathcal{Z} is the trivial system, then \mathcal{X} is a distal system, and we denote the rank simply by $rk(\mathcal{X})$. Similar to a result of compact extensions, we have the following:

Proposition 11.4.2. *Let \mathcal{X} be an ergodic system. Suppose $\mathcal{Z}_i \subseteq \mathcal{Y}_i \subseteq \mathcal{X}, i \in I$, are factors such that each extension $\mathcal{Z}_i \subseteq \mathcal{Y}_i$ is distal. Then the factor $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ generated by all the \mathcal{Y}_i is a distal extension of the factor \mathcal{Z} generated by all the \mathcal{Z}_i . Moreover, $rk(\mathcal{Y}/\mathcal{Z}) \leq \sup_{i \in I} rk(\mathcal{Y}_i/\mathcal{Z}_i)$. In particular, given an extension $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ with \mathcal{X} ergodic, there is a largest immediate distal extension of \mathcal{Z} in \mathcal{X} .*

Proof. Let $\alpha = \sup_{i \in I} rk(\mathcal{Y}_i / \mathcal{Z}_i)$ and for each $i \in I$, we choose a distal tower $\{\mathcal{Y}_{i,\beta}\}_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ for the extension $\mathcal{Z}_i \subseteq \mathcal{Y}_i$. We do so by taking all entries after a certain ordinal to be equal to \mathcal{Y}_i whenever the need arises. This can be better explained with the following diagram:

Given $\beta \leq \alpha$, let \mathcal{Y}_β be the factor generated by all the $\mathcal{Y}_{i,\beta}$, for $i \in I$. Then using Proposition 11.3.2, we conclude that the new tower $\{\mathcal{Y}_\beta\}_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ obtained is a distal tower for $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y} \implies rk(\mathcal{Y} / \mathcal{Z}) \leq \alpha = \sup_{i \in I} rk(\mathcal{Y}_i / \mathcal{Z}_i)$.

The particular case follows by observing that $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Z}$ is a compact extension and hence, we have a distal tower in \mathcal{X} with base \mathcal{Z} . Now we take all such towers in \mathcal{X} with base \mathcal{Z} and apply the process in the previous paragraph to obtain the largest immediate distal extension of \mathcal{Z} in \mathcal{X} . \square

Corollary 11.4.3. *If $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is an ergodic, distal extension, then $rk(\mathcal{X} / \mathcal{Z}) \leq (|\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0)^+$.*

Proof. Let W be a factor of \mathcal{X} generated by \mathcal{Z} and an element of \mathcal{X} . Clearly, the extension $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq W$ is distal and each such factor W has density character at most $|\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0 \implies rk(W / \mathcal{Z}) \leq (|\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0)^+$. On the other hand, these factors generate \mathcal{X} , so from Proposition 11.4.2, we have $rk(\mathcal{X} / \mathcal{Z}) \leq (|\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0)^+$. \square

We now have the following lemma:

Lemma 11.4.4. *Let $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ be a distal extension with \mathcal{X} ergodic and let \mathcal{Y} be a separable factor of \mathcal{X} . Then there are separable factors $\mathcal{Z}' \subseteq \mathcal{Y}' \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ with $\mathcal{Z}' \subseteq \mathcal{Z}$, $\mathcal{Y}' \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ and such that the extension $\mathcal{Z}' \subseteq \mathcal{Y}'$ is distal; moreover, $rk(\mathcal{Y}' / \mathcal{Z}') \leq rk(\mathcal{X} / \mathcal{Z})$.*

Proof. We proceed by transfinite induction on the distal rank $\alpha = rk(\mathcal{X}/\mathcal{Z})$. Let $\{\mathcal{X}_\beta\}_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ be a distal tower for the extension $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$.

In the base case for $\alpha = 0$, we have $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{Z}$. So, we take $\mathcal{Z}' = \mathcal{Y}' = \mathcal{Y}$ and observe that the extension $\mathcal{Y}' \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ is compact and hence $rk(\mathcal{Y}'/\mathcal{Z}') = rk(\mathcal{X}/\mathcal{Z}) = 0$. Now, as induction hypothesis, we assume that for all distal towers $\{\mathcal{X}_\beta\}_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ of rank $< \alpha$, the above assertion is true. Now, we divide the proof in two cases:

1. α is a successor ordinal: Let $\alpha = \beta + 1$, β is an ordinal. Now the extension $\mathcal{X}_\beta \subseteq \mathcal{X}_\alpha$ is compact, so there are finitely generated Γ -invariant \mathcal{X}_β modules M_i such that $L^2(\mathcal{X}_\alpha) = \bigoplus_{i \in I} M_i$. Since \mathcal{Y} is a separable factor we have that $L^2(\mathcal{Y})$ is also separable. So there exists a countable subset $J \subseteq I$ such that $L^2(\mathcal{Y}) \subseteq \bigoplus_{i \in J} M_i$. We fix an M_i and a corresponding \mathcal{X}_β basis $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$. Since Γ is countable and \mathcal{Y} is separable, one can find a separable factor $W \subseteq \mathcal{X}_\beta$ such that the W -module M'_i generated by e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n is Γ -invariant and contains the intersection $L^2(\mathcal{Y}) \cap M_i$. Also since J is countable, we can take W which works for every element of J by taking the factor generated from the factors for every element of J . Let $M = \bigoplus_{i \in J} M'_i$. By adding all the product modules (as defined in Proposition 11.3.2) we see that M defines a separable factor $(\mathcal{Y} \subseteq) \mathcal{Y}_0 \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ such that $M = L^2(\mathcal{Y}_0); W \subseteq \mathcal{Y}_0$ is a compact extension. We apply the inductive hypothesis to get a distal extension $\mathcal{Z}' \subseteq \mathcal{Y}_1$ of separable factors of \mathcal{X}_β such that $\mathcal{Z}' \subseteq \mathcal{Z}$ and $W \subseteq \mathcal{Y}_1$, and moreover $rk(\mathcal{Y}_1/\mathcal{Z}') \leq \beta$. Let \mathcal{Y}' be the factor generated by \mathcal{Y}_0 and \mathcal{Y}_1 . Then \mathcal{Y}' is separable, contains \mathcal{Y} , and is a compact extension of \mathcal{Y}_1 , with $rk(\mathcal{Y}'/\mathcal{Z}') \leq \alpha$. Hence, we have obtained the required \mathcal{Z}' and \mathcal{Y}' .
2. α is a limit ordinal: We can choose countable many ordinals $\beta_n < \alpha, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that \mathcal{Y} is generated by $\mathcal{Y} \cap \mathcal{X}_{\beta_n}$. By the inductive hypothesis, we have separable distal extensions $\mathcal{Z}_n \subseteq \mathcal{Y}_n$, of rank less than α , with $\mathcal{Z}_n \subseteq \mathcal{Z}$ and $\mathcal{Y} \cap \mathcal{X}_{\beta_n} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}_n$. Since, $\mathcal{Z}_n, \mathcal{Y}_n$ and \mathbb{N} is countable, then if $\mathcal{Z}', \mathcal{Y}'$ are the factors generated by the $\mathcal{Z}_n, \mathcal{Y}_n$ respectively, they are separable. Also $\mathcal{Z}' \subseteq \mathcal{Z}, \mathcal{Y}' \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ and the extension $\mathcal{Z}' \subseteq \mathcal{Y}'$ is distal of rank atmost α by Proposition 11.4.2.

Hence, the inductive step is proved and we conclude the proof of this lemma. □

The following proposition says that factors of distal systems are distal:

Proposition 11.4.5. *Suppose $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ and \mathcal{X} is ergodic. Then the extension $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is distal iff the extensions $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ are distal.*

Proof. If the extensions $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ are distal, then we concatenate the towers of these extensions and obtain a tower of compact extensions for $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$. Hence, $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a distal extension.

Now, if $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a distal extension and let $\{\mathcal{X}_\beta\}_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ be a corresponding tower. So, one can choose ordinals $\gamma, \gamma + 1$ such that $\mathcal{X}_\gamma \subseteq \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{\gamma+1}$, where γ may be a limit ordinal well. Now the extension $\mathcal{X}_\gamma \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{\gamma+1}$ is compact, and by Lemma 11.3.4, we have that $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{\gamma+1}$ is a compact extension. Hence the tower with base \mathcal{Y} followed by $\mathcal{X}_{\gamma+1}$ concatenated with $\{\mathcal{X}_\beta\}_{\gamma+1 \leq \beta \leq \alpha}$ is a tower of compact extensions and we conclude that $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is distal. Also, we claim that if $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a distal extension then $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ is a distal extension. Let $\mathcal{X}_1 \mathcal{X}_2$ denote the factor generated by $\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_2$. We prove that if $W \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a separable factor, then $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{L}W$ is distal. By Lemma 11.4.4, there are separable factors $\mathcal{L}' \subseteq W' \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ with $\mathcal{L}' \subseteq \mathcal{L}, W \subseteq W'$ such that $\mathcal{L}' \subseteq W'$ is a distal extension. Then one can show that $\mathcal{L}' \subseteq \mathcal{L}'W$ is a distal extension. Using Proposition 11.4.2, for the distal extensions $\mathcal{L}' \subseteq \mathcal{L}'W, \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{L}'$ we have $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{L}'W$ is distal. Since, for each separable factor W of \mathcal{Y} , $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{L}'W$ is distal, using Proposition 11.4.2, $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ is distal. \square

We end this section by stating the following amalgamation result:

Proposition 11.4.6. *Let $i_1 : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_1$ and $i_2 : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_2$ be embeddings of ergodic systems. Then there is an ergodic system \mathcal{Y} and embeddings $j_1 : \mathcal{X}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ and $j_2 : \mathcal{X}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ such that $j_1 \circ i_1 = j_2 \circ i_2$. If \mathcal{Y} is moreover generated by $j_1(\mathcal{X}_1)$ and $j_2(\mathcal{X}_2)$, we say that it is an ergodic joining of \mathcal{X}_1 and \mathcal{X}_2 over \mathcal{L} .*

Chapter 12

Universal ergodic distal systems

In this chapter, we shall see the construction the largest ergodic distal extension of an ergodic system using continuous model theory. We have tried to explain the universal tower construction ([7]) in more details and provided several diagrams in this chapter to explain the proofs.

12.1 The universal tower

Lemma 12.1.1. *Let \mathcal{Z} be an ergodic system. Then the family of compact, ergodic extensions of \mathcal{Z} has the following properties:*

1. *It is directed: If $i_1 : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_1$ and $i_2 : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_2$ are compact, ergodic extensions of \mathcal{Z} , then there exists a compact, ergodic extension $j : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_3$ and embeddings $j_1 : \mathcal{X}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_3$ and $j_2 : \mathcal{X}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_3$ such that $j_1 \circ i_1 = j_2 \circ i_2$.*
2. *It is closed under direct limits.*

Proof. 1. From Proposition 11.4.6, by taking the joining of \mathcal{X}_1 and \mathcal{X}_2 over \mathcal{Z} which is ergodic and using the fact that $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}_1$ and $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}_2$ are compact extensions, we see that $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq j_1(\mathcal{X}_1)j_2(\mathcal{X}_2)$ is a compact extension using Proposition 11.3.2.

2. Let $\mathcal{X} = \varinjlim \mathcal{X}_\alpha$. One can identify the factors \mathcal{X}_α with subsets of \mathcal{X} (follows from definition of \mathcal{X}). Then \mathcal{X} is generated by the \mathcal{X}_α s and $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}_\alpha$ are compact extensions. So by Proposition 11.3.2, $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a compact extension. Now if we consider the zero-mean invariant vectors in $L^2(\mathcal{X})$, their projections on each of the $L^2(\mathcal{X}_\alpha)$ s are also invariant and since \mathcal{X}_α is ergodic, these projections are all

equal to 0. And since $L^2(\mathcal{X}_\alpha)$ s generate $L^2(\mathcal{X}) \implies L^2(\mathcal{X})$ contains no non-zero zero-mean invariant vectors $\implies \mathcal{X}$ is ergodic. □

We have the following definition:

Definition 12.1.2 (Coalescent). *A system \mathcal{X} is said to be coalescent over a factor \mathcal{Z} if every \mathcal{Z} -embedding $\mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ (i.e., a self-embedding fixing \mathcal{Z} pointwise) is an isomorphism.*

Now the following theorem is needed for the construction that we are aiming for in this chapter:

Theorem 12.1.3. *Let \mathcal{Z} be any ergodic Γ -system. Then there exists a unique compact, ergodic extension $i_0 : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}$ with the following property:*

If $i : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is any compact, ergodic extension, then there exists an embedding $j : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}$ such that $i_0 = j \circ i$. Moreover $|\widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}| \leq (|\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0)^{\aleph_0}$ and $\widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}$ is coalescent over \mathcal{Z} .

Proof. The existence of $\widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}$ can be shown using Proposition 11.3.9 and Lemma 12.1.1. Proposition 11.3.9 allows us to construct a set of representatives of all \mathcal{Z} -isomorphism classes of compact, ergodic extensions of \mathcal{Z} because there are at most $(|\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0)^{\aleph_0}$ isomorphism classes of finitely generated, Γ -invariant \mathcal{Z} -modules and each of these modules can occur finitely many times in the L^2 space of a compact extension of \mathcal{Z} . Hence, we can write the set as $\{\mathcal{X}_\alpha | \alpha < \kappa\}$, for some cardinal κ . Now, we will construct a sequence $(\mathcal{X}'_\beta)_{\beta < \kappa}$ of compact, ergodic extensions of \mathcal{Z} using these representatives and Lemma 12.1.1 as follows:

- $\mathcal{X}'_0 := \mathcal{X}_0$.
- For successor ordinals, $\mathcal{X}'_{\beta+1} :=$ Any amalgam of $\mathcal{X}_\beta, \mathcal{X}'_\beta$; the existence of which has been shown in Lemma 12.1.1 (1).
- For limit ordinal λ , $\mathcal{X}'_\lambda := \lim_{\rightarrow \alpha < \lambda} \mathcal{X}'_\alpha$ using Lemma 12.1.1 (2).

We observe that by this construction, we have $\forall \beta < \beta' \leq \kappa, \mathcal{X}_\beta \subseteq \mathcal{X}'_\beta$ and $\mathcal{X}'_\beta \subseteq \mathcal{X}'_{\beta'}$. We now define $\widetilde{\mathcal{Z}} = \mathcal{X}'_\kappa$. Now $\widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}$ is clearly a compact, ergodic extension of \mathcal{Z} and $|\widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}| \leq (|\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0)^{\aleph_0}$. For the uniqueness part, it is enough to show that $\widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}$ is coalescent over \mathcal{Z} . Now if $\phi : \widetilde{\mathcal{Z}} \rightarrow \widetilde{\mathcal{Z}}$ is an embedding fixing \mathcal{Z} but is not surjective, we will use

maximality of $\widetilde{\mathcal{L}}$ to arrive at a contradiction. Let $\kappa = |\widetilde{\mathcal{L}}|$. We will use the previous lemma and construct a directed system $(\mathcal{L}_\alpha | \alpha < \kappa^+)$ of compact ergodic extensions of \mathcal{L} and show that the density character of the direct limit of this system exceeds κ . The construction of the directed system is as follows: For each $\alpha < \kappa^+$, we take $\mathcal{L}_\alpha = \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}$ and the maps $\phi : \mathcal{L}_\alpha \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_{\alpha+1}$. For limit ordinal λ , we take the direct limit \mathcal{L}'_λ of the directed system constructed before the limit ordinal occurred and since \mathcal{L}'_λ is also embedded in $\widetilde{\mathcal{L}}$ and $\forall \alpha < \lambda, \mathcal{L}_\alpha \rightarrow \mathcal{L}'_\lambda$, we have $\mathcal{L}_\alpha \rightarrow \mathcal{L}'_\lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_\lambda, \forall \alpha < \lambda$ giving us the required maps for \mathcal{L}_λ in the directed system. Now $|\lim_{\rightarrow \alpha < \kappa^+} \mathcal{L}_\alpha| = \kappa^+$, giving us the required contradiction. \square

We have the following consequence from the uniqueness:

Corollary 12.1.4. *Every automorphism of \mathcal{L} extends to an automorphism of $\widetilde{\mathcal{L}}$.*

Proof. If ϕ is an automorphism, then $j : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is a compact, ergodic extension iff $j \circ \phi : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is a compact, ergodic extension. Also we have, $i := i_0 \circ \phi$ is a compact, ergodic extension.

Claim: $i = i_0$.

Proof of claim: Let $j : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ be a compact, ergodic extension. Then $j \circ \phi^{-1} : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is a compact, ergodic extension. Now, applying Theorem 12.1.3, we get a map $k : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}$ such that $i_0 = k \circ j \circ \phi^{-1} \implies i = i_0 \circ \phi = k \circ j$. So, by uniqueness of i_0 , we have $i = i_0$, thus proving the claim.

Again applying Theorem 12.1.3, we get a map $\psi : \widetilde{\mathcal{L}} \rightarrow \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}$ such that $i_0 = \psi \circ i$. We have the following commutative diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 \widetilde{\mathcal{L}} & \xrightarrow{\psi} & \widetilde{\mathcal{L}} \\
 \uparrow i_0 & \nearrow i & \uparrow i_0 \\
 \mathcal{L} & \xrightarrow{\phi} & \mathcal{L}
 \end{array}$$

Now $i = i_0 \implies \psi(i_0(z)) = i(z) = i_0(z)$.

Hence, ψ fixes \mathcal{L} , so by coalescence, ψ is an automorphism.

Also, $\psi(i_0(z)) = i(z) = i_0(\phi(z)) \implies \psi$ extends ϕ . \square

We can use Theorem 12.1.3 and define an **ergodic distal extension** $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$ for each ordinal number α in a natural way:

- $D_0(\mathcal{Z}) = \mathcal{Z}$;
- $D_{\alpha+1}(\mathcal{Z}) = \widetilde{D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})}$;
- $D_\lambda(\mathcal{Z}) = \lim_{\rightarrow \beta < \lambda} \widetilde{D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})}$ if λ is a limit ordinal.

Uniqueness of Distal tower: The tower $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$ is unique upto \mathcal{Z} -isomorphism. This can be proved by transfinite induction. The identity map $id : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{Z}$ is a compact, ergodic extension. If α is an ordinal and $(D_\beta)_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ and $(D'_\beta)_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ are two towers constructed as above, and there are isomorphisms $D_\beta \rightarrow D'_\beta$ for each $\beta < \alpha$. Then if α is a successor ordinal, we use Corollary 12.1.4 to get an isomorphism $\psi : \widetilde{D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})} \rightarrow \widetilde{D'_\beta(\mathcal{Z})}$, where $\alpha = \beta + 1$ which is an extension of the isomorphism at the β level. If α is a limit ordinal, then from Theorem 12.1.3, the uniqueness of i_0 and the fact that α is a directed set, we have that the towers $(D_\beta)_{\beta < \alpha}$, $(D'_\beta)_{\beta < \alpha}$ are directed systems. Then in the direct limit, one can “glue” the isomorphisms obtained at the previous levels to obtain an isomorphism $D_\alpha \rightarrow D'_\alpha$. Hence, by transfinite induction, we have shown the uniqueness of the tower. We also observe that the isomorphism $D_\alpha \rightarrow D'_\alpha$ restricts to a \mathcal{Z} -isomorphism $D_\beta \rightarrow D'_\beta$, for each $\beta < \alpha$. Clearly, each distal extension $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$ is of rank at most α .

We now see an important conclusion of Theorem 12.1.3 i.e. The Universal Tower.

Theorem 12.1.5. *Let \mathcal{Z} be an ergodic system. Then the system $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$ is universal for the ergodic, distal extensions of \mathcal{Z} of rank at most α , i.e., any such system is a factor of $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$. Moreover, $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$ is coalescent over \mathcal{Z} and hence unique with this universal property.*

Proof. Let $(\mathcal{X}_\beta)_{\beta \leq \alpha}$ be a distal tower over \mathcal{Z} of length α with \mathcal{X}_α ergodic. We will see a construction using induction of a sequence of embeddings $i_\beta : \mathcal{X}_\beta \rightarrow D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})$. We start with $i_0 = id$. Now, we assume that we already have $i_{\beta'} : \mathcal{X}_{\beta'} \rightarrow D_{\beta'}(\mathcal{Z}), \forall \beta' < \alpha$. If α is a successor ordinal and $\alpha = \beta + 1$ for some β , then applying Proposition 11.4.6, we find an ergodic joining \mathcal{Y} of $i : \mathcal{X}_\beta \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_{\beta+1}$ and $i_\beta : \mathcal{X}_\beta \rightarrow D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})$. Now, since \mathcal{Y} is generated by $j_1(\mathcal{X}_{\beta+1}), j_2(D_\beta(\mathcal{Z}))$, using Proposition 11.3.2, we have that \mathcal{Y} is a compact extension of $D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})$. Using Theorem 12.1.3, we obtain an embedding $j' : \mathcal{Y} \rightarrow D_{\beta+1}(\mathcal{Z})$. And the map $j' \circ j_1$ is our required embedding i.e. $i_{\beta+1} := j' \circ j_1$. The above construction has been illustrated as follows:

If α is a limit ordinal, one takes $i_\alpha := \bigcup_{\beta < \alpha} i_\beta$ and checks that this is the required embedding. Hence, using transfinite induction, we have proved the first assertion.

For the moreover assertion, we will see that each self-embedding of $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$ fixing \mathcal{Z} is an isomorphism. We proceed by induction on α . The case of $\alpha = 0$ is trivial. Now, we assume that the above statement holds $\forall \beta' < \alpha$. Let $\phi_\alpha : D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z}) \rightarrow D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$ be a \mathcal{Z} -embedding.

Claim: $\phi_\alpha(D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})) \subseteq D_\beta(\mathcal{Z}), \forall \beta < \alpha$.

Proof of claim: We see that the system W generated by $\phi_\alpha(D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})), D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})$ inside $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$ is a distal extension of \mathcal{Z} of rank atmost β , by Proposition 11.4.2 and using the fact that ϕ_α is an embedding. Hence, W is a factor of $D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})$ by the universal property proved above. Thus, we have embeddings $D_\beta(\mathcal{Z}) \rightarrow W \rightarrow D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})$. By induction hypothesis, we have that these embeddings are surjective (composition is an isomorphism), hence the claim is proved.

Again we have that ϕ_α is an embedding and hence, by induction hypothesis, it is a \mathcal{Z} -isomorphism. So, we have $\phi_\alpha(D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})) = D_\beta(\mathcal{Z}), \forall \beta < \alpha$. If $\alpha = \beta + 1$, then the surjectivity follows from Theorem 12.1.3 (coalescence fact). And the case of limit ordinal can be handled by the equality result derived from the above claim. \square

The above proof implies that if $\beta < \alpha$ and \mathcal{Y} is a distal extension of \mathcal{Z} of rank atmost β such that $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$, then $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})$. Thus, within $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Z})$, the system $D_\beta(\mathcal{Z})$ can be defined as the **maximal intermediate distal extension** of \mathcal{Z} of rank atmost α .

12.2 Some applications of the universal tower

Theorem 12.2.1. *Let \mathcal{Z} be an ergodic system and let $\kappa = |\mathcal{Z}| + \aleph_0$. Then we have $D_{\kappa+1}(\mathcal{Z}) = D_{\kappa^+}(\mathcal{Z})$, i.e., $D_{\kappa^+}(\mathcal{Z})$ is the largest ergodic, distal extension of \mathcal{Z} .*

Proof. We have, from Corollary 11.4.3 that $rk(D_{\kappa+1}(\mathcal{Z})/\mathcal{Z}) \leq \kappa^+$.

\implies From Theorem 12.1.5, $D_{\kappa+1}(\mathcal{Z})$ is a factor of $D_{\kappa}(\mathcal{Z})$. But we already have that $D_{\kappa}(\mathcal{Z})$ is a factor of $D_{\kappa+1}(\mathcal{Z})$. So, we have $D_{\kappa+1}(\mathcal{Z}) = D_{\kappa^+}(\mathcal{Z})$. \square

Let $D_{\alpha}(\Gamma) := D_{\alpha}(1)$, i.e. the trivial 1- point system. It is natural to ask what about the distal rank of $D_{\omega_1}(\Gamma)$ since $\omega_1 = \kappa^+$. For $\Gamma = \mathbb{Z}$, (Theorem 12.2.3) this is answered by a construction of Belezny and Foreman [7] and the following proposition:

Proposition 12.2.2. *Suppose Γ is a countable group and $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ are Γ -systems with \mathcal{X} ergodic and the extensions $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ distal. Then $rk(\mathcal{Y}/\mathcal{Z}) \leq rk(\mathcal{X}/\mathcal{Z})$.*

Theorem 12.2.3. *$D_{\alpha}(\mathbb{Z}) \subsetneq D_{\alpha+1}(\mathbb{Z})$ for all $\alpha < \omega_1$ i.e., $rk(D_{\omega_1}(\mathbb{Z})) = \omega_1$.*

Proof. Belezny and Foreman have built examples of ergodic, distal systems of arbitrarily high countable rank. Using Proposition 12.2.2, we have that the rank of a distal system is atleast as large as the rank of any of its factors. Since, all these towers are embedded in the universal tower, we have that $D_{\alpha}(\mathbb{Z}) \subsetneq D_{\alpha+1}(\mathbb{Z}), \forall \alpha < \omega_1 \implies rk(D_{\omega_1}(\mathbb{Z})) = \omega_1$. \square

Definition 12.2.4. *An ergodic system \mathcal{X} is said to be **2-simple** if whenever $\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_2$ are two isomorphic copies of \mathcal{X} inside a larger ergodic system, then $\mathcal{X}_1 = \mathcal{X}_2$.*

Proposition 12.2.5. *For every ordinal $\alpha \leq \omega_1$, $D_{\alpha}(\Gamma)$ is 2-simple.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{X} = D_{\alpha}(\Gamma)$ and let $\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_2$ are two copies of \mathcal{X} in an ergodic system \mathcal{Y} . Then the system generated by $\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_2$ is of rank atmost α (using Proposition 11.4.2). By universality of \mathcal{X} , $\mathcal{X}_1 \mathcal{X}_2$ is embedded in \mathcal{X} . And by coalescence of \mathcal{X} , we have $\mathcal{X}_1 = \mathcal{X}_2$. where $i= 1, 2$. \square

$$\mathcal{X} \xrightarrow{\text{isomorphism}} \mathcal{X}_i \xrightarrow{\text{embed}} \mathcal{X}_1 \mathcal{X}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{embed}} \mathcal{X}$$

We have the following theorem by Veech [7]:

Theorem 12.2.6. *A seperable, ergodic, simple system is either compact or weakly mixing.*

Along with this and Proposition 12.2.5, we use the fact that if an ergodic system \mathcal{X} is not weakly mixing (for example: distal) then 2-simplicity implies simplicity to conclude the following:

Corollary 12.2.7. *Suppose that $D_2(\Gamma)$ is a separable system. Then $D_2(\Gamma) = D_1(\Gamma)$ and every distal Γ -system is compact.*

We conclude this section with the following observation:

Proposition 12.2.8. *Let $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ be an extension of ergodic systems. Then for every ordinal α , $D_\alpha(\mathcal{X})$ is a factor of $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Y})$.*

Proof. Let W be an ergodic joining of \mathcal{Y} and $D_\alpha(\mathcal{X})$ over \mathcal{X} . Using Proposition 11.4.2, the extension $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq W$ is distal and has rank at most α . By the universal property of $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Y})$, W is a factor of $D_\alpha(\mathcal{Y})$.

A figure for the above proof is given below. Here j_1, j_2 refer to the embeddings as in Proposition 11.4.6.

□

Part 3

Conclusion

Through this thesis, we have seen a glimpse of the significance of logics and its applications in mainstream mathematics. One can think of logics and model theory as a tool for providing an aerial view of various intricacies and mysteries of mathematics as well as attempting to build a strong foundation for mathematics. One can further explore these areas of research by investigating various unanswered questions and by coming up with new ideas. We would like to conclude this thesis by indicating a few directions which one might consider as a topic for further research:

- Naimark's problem: The Naimark's problem asks whether every C^* algebra that has only one irreducible representation up to unitary equivalence is isomorphic to the algebra of compact operators on any Hilbert space. The article [1] shows that $\diamond \rightarrow \neg(\text{Naimark's assertion})$. It is still not known whether a positive answer to Naimark's question is relatively consistent with ZFC.
- One can explore the applications of model-theoretic framework to group actions on C^* algebras, a research field which saw the contributions of many eminent researchers like Ilijas Farah and also investigate the possibilities of similar constructions as in [7] in case of noncommutative ergodic theory as well as the theory of joining for Von Neumann algebras.
- In Solovay's model, we studied how the the measurability of reals is affected in a particular model of set theory. For this purpose one generally considers ω^ω to represent the reals. Another popular way of representing reals is by considering $[\omega]$, the collection of infinite subsets of ω . Slightly different kinds of questions arise out

of these different representations of reals. For example, The splitting number s_ω is the min cardinality of a set $S \subseteq [\omega]$ for which, given any $a \in [\omega]$, $\exists b \in S$, such that $a \cap b$ and $b \setminus a$, both have cardinality ω . Now, if $\neg \text{CH}$ holds, then, $\aleph_1 \leq s_\omega \leq 2^\omega$. Now, if we ask the same question but this time replace ω by any infinite cardinal κ (that is ask the same question in case of generalised reals instead of ordinary reals), then we have remarkably different results. $s_\kappa \geq \kappa$ iff κ is strongly inaccessible and $> \kappa$ iff κ is weakly compact. So are there any other sort of cardinals related to reals, which behave so differently in case of generalised reals? ([12])

- While preparing this thesis, the student has come up with the following question: We have come across several results showing how independent statements of ZFC like CH and diamond principle have certain effects on $B(H)$. Apart from norm topology on $B(H)$, $B(H)$ has strong and weak topology. Now, C^* algebras are norm-closed $*$ -subalgebras of $B(H)$ and the Naimark's problem is a consequence of the diamond principle on C^* algebras. And Von Neumann algebras are C^* algebras that are closed subspaces of $B(H)$ with weak topology (equivalently, closed under strong topology). So, the student was thinking that are there consequences of various independent statements on Von Neumann algebras that are different from C^* algebras? In short, can we 'merge' or 'distance' C^* algebras and Von Neumann algebras using independent statements?

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